

22-24 APRIL 2026

i3S & SUPERBOCK ARENA
PORTO, PORTUGAL

INSTITUTO
DE INVESTIGAÇÃO
E INOVAÇÃO
EM SAÚDE
UNIVERSIDADE
DO PORTO

XXXII
PORTO CANCER MEETING

*Bridging research
and policy in
hereditary cancer*

abstract book

A joint conference
with Preventable

XXXII PORTO CANCER MEETING

22-24 APRIL 2026

i3S & SUPERBOCK ARENA
PORTO, PORTUGAL

[PCM.I3S.UP.PT](https://pcm.i3s.up.pt)

PCM'S APP

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Welcome

THE PORTO CANCER MEETING

It is our great pleasure to welcome you to the XXXII Edition of the Porto Cancer Meeting. This renowned international meeting has been organized since 1990 by the Institute of Molecular Pathology and Immunology of the University of Porto, well-known as Ipatimup. The Porto Cancer Meeting is now a flagship meeting of the Institute for Research and Innovation in Health – i3S – the largest health research institute in Portugal.

This scientific event will be part of the celebrations of the 10th Anniversary of i3S, highlighting a decade of scientific excellence, collaboration, and societal impact.

THE XXXII PORTO CANCER MEETING THEME IN 2026

This Porto Cancer Meeting will be dedicated to heritable cancers, lying at the interface between basic research and real-world applications in the form of health policies. Hereditary cancers are less common than sporadic cancers, tend to develop at a younger age, and often impact multiple family members, posing significant social, clinical, and economic challenges. They require specialized and multidisciplinary care, because prevention and treatment can be complex. However, as these cancers are caused by inherited genetic changes, genetic testing can identify the underlying risk. This enables proactive monitoring, early diagnosis, and application of preventive and more personalized measures, as well as targeted treatments.

To discuss challenges and opportunities in the field of inherited cancers, the XXXII Porto Cancer Meeting scientific program in 2026 will revolve around the genetics and

biology of these cancers, their distinctive clinical pathways of care, social intricacies, and cost of healthcare for patients, hospitals and the society as a whole. This year, the Porto Cancer Meeting will embrace the final conference of the EU-funded project Preventable [www.preventable.eu], which has established pathways of care from several rare tumour risk syndromes, their respective costs and cost-effectiveness, as well as guidelines to improve communication between the various stakeholders moving around this ecosystem.

A special flavour brought in by the Preventable EU project into the Porto Cancer Meeting, is the presence of patients and families suffering from rare tumour risk syndromes, from many European countries, who have actively participated in the project, further extending the real impact of this event.

This meeting brings together Patients and Patients' representatives, Healthcare Professionals, Scientists working in Basic, Clinical, Health Economics and Social Sciences aspects of heritable cancers, as well as Policy Officers and Health Managers from the European Health Management Association - EHMA, Decision-makers from Europe, and beyond. It will also mark the launch of the 'Preventable Learning Hub' at the i3S website, a novel online resource of educational contents, designed specifically for at-risk individuals and their families, but also for healthcare providers and policymakers, integrating expert perspectives, real-life testimonies, visual infographics and guidelines, to promote knowledge, better decision-making, and evidence-based practices.

This joint conference between the Porto Cancer Meeting and the Preventable EU project will start at the i3S, in the afternoon of the 22nd of April 2026, with a welcome to participants by the Organizers and the i3S, a keynote lecture and a Porto d'Honra, as part of the celebration of the 10th Anniversary of the i3S.

The conference will continue on the 23rd of April, at the Super Bock Arena Conference Centre, in the heart of Porto, for another two days, and till the end of the 24th of April.

The program was designed to attract a diverse range of participants to foster multidisciplinary discussions that

advance the field and support sustainable, resilient health systems for individuals at high risk of cancer. The joint Conference serves as a platform for renowned researchers, professionals, and patients to discuss recent advances in hereditary cancer research, disease management, healthcare costs, and prevention and treatment strategies.

Centred around the theme “Bridging Research and Policy in Hereditary Cancer Prevention and Care,” the XXXII Porto Cancer Meeting emphasizes the urgent need for innovative, scalable solutions to ensure accessible, equitable, and sustainable care for patients with tumour risk syndromes across Europe.

The long-term goal is to move beyond simply managing these rare patients, to actively shape disease prevention, early diagnosis, and healthcare resilience at all levels, supported by forefront scientific discoveries, that allows moving from ‘one solution fits all’ to ‘patient-centred care settings’.

The Organizing Committee looks forward to welcome all participants, speakers and patients to the historic and vibrant city of Porto, a World Heritage Site by UNESCO.

Carla Oliveira

Conference Chair, on behalf of the Organizing Committee

Local Organizing Committee

CARLA OLIVEIRA Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde (i3S), Portugal • **SARA PEREIRA** i3S, Portugal • **LILIANA SOUSA** i3S, Portugal • **SILVANA LOBO** i3S, Portugal • **DANIEL FERREIRA** i3S, Portugal
NUNO MARCOS Institute of Molecular Pathology and Immunology of the University of Porto (Ipatimup), Portugal • **ANA GOMES** Ipatimup, Portugal • **IGOR LOPES** Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI), Portugal
• **SÉRGIO OLIVEIRA** European Health Management Association (EHMA), Belgium • **BÁRBARA PELETEIRO** Unidade Local de Saúde São João (ULSSJ), Portugal

Scientific Committee

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ALEXIS STRADER European Health Management Association (EHMA), Belgium • **JUDITH BALMAÑA** Vall d’Hebron Institute of Oncology (VHIO), Spain • **RICARDO AMORIM** i3S, Portugal • **TAMARA MILAGRE** EVITA Patients Association, Portugal • **NICOLINE HOGERBRUGGE** European Reference Network (ERN) GENTURIS, The Netherlands • **SUSANA SAMPAIO OLIVEIRA** Faculdade Economia da Universidade do

Local Organizing Committee

Carla Oliveira

INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGAÇÃO E INOVAÇÃO EM SAÚDE (I3S), PT

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INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGAÇÃO E INOVAÇÃO EM SAÚDE (I3S), PT

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Ana Gomes

IPATIMUP - INSTITUTE OF MOLECULAR PATHOLOGY AND IMMUNOLOGY OF U. PORTO, PT

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SOCIEDADE PORTUGUESA DE INOVAÇÃO, PT

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Tamara Milagre

EVITA PATIENTS ASSOCIATION, PT

Nicoline Hoogerbrugge

EUROPEAN REFERENCE NETWORK GENTURIS, NE

Susana Sampaio Oliveira

FACULDADE ECONOMIA DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO, PT

Joana Paredes

INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGAÇÃO E INOVAÇÃO EM SAÚDE (I3S), PT

Sandra Tavares

INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGAÇÃO E INOVAÇÃO EM SAÚDE (I3S), PT

Location and Venue

On 22nd April, the meeting will be held at **i3S – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde** (Rua Alfredo Allen, 208; 4200-135 Porto, Portugal).

On 23rd and 24th April, the meeting will be held at **Super Bock Arena** (Jardins do Palácio de Cristal, R. de D Manuel II Porta 03, 4050-346 Porto). To access the venue, use Gate 1.

Palácio de Cristal parking (entrance at R. Jorge de Viterbo Ferreira 189, 4050-313 Porto, just in front of ICBAS/ Faculty of Pharmacy of University of Porto) is the closer option and it is located 8 minutes walking from the venue.

Travel Information

traveling to

i3S Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde

ARRIVING BY PLANE

From Francisco Sá Carneiro Airport (Porto) to i3S by metro:

Take Line E at the Airport station.

Direction: Estádio do Dragão.

Stop: 'Trindade' station.

At Trindade change to Line D.

Direction: Hospital São João.

Stop: 'Pólo Universitário'.

Average time: **45 minutes.**

For more information:

<https://en.metrodoporto.pt/>

ARRIVING BY TRAIN

From Campanhã or São Bento train stations, Metro or Bus are available to reach i3S. Metro is the easiest way.

From Campanhã Train Station

Metro: All lines (A, B, C, E and F):

Destination Station: Trindade;

Then change to line D - yellow |

Direction: Hospital São João;

Stop: 'Pólo Universitário'.

From São Bento Train Station

Metro: Take Line D - Yellow line.

Direction: Hospital São João;

Stop: 'Pólo Universitário'

(no connections - direct line).

For more information: [https://](https://en.metrodoporto.pt/)

en.metrodoporto.pt/

traveling to

Super Bock Arena

ARRIVING BY PLANE

From Francisco Sá Carneiro

Airport (Porto) to Super Bock Arena by metro:

Take Line E at the Airport station.

Direction: Estádio do Dragão.

Stop: 'Casa da Música' station (no

connections - direct line). Average

time: **22 minutes.** For more info:

<https://en.metrodoporto.pt/>.

From Casa da Música Metro station,

it is a 25-minute walk to Super Bock

Arena ([details here](#)). Alternatively,

there are Bus options (please see

the Bus options available depending

on your arrival hour [here](#))

ARRIVING BY TRAIN

From Campanhã Train Station

Check the available transportation

depending on your arrival hour [here](#).

From São Bento Train Station

Check the available transportation

depending on your arrival hour [here](#).

There are plenty of taxi options at the

airport and train station, immediately

available either at the arrival exit or

through a [pre-booking system](#), in

case of the airport. Bolt/ Uber/ etc

are also available and you need to

look for information inside the airport

to find the specific pick-up location.

Social Program

23rd April 2026 | 19h30 | Dinner at BH Foz Restaurant*

Avenida do Brasil 498, 4150-025 Porto

Transportation from the meeting venue to the dinner venue will be provided by the event by bus at 19:00.

The meeting point is at the entrance of Gate 1 of Super Bock Arena at 18:50.

*The participation in the dinner is subject to registration and payment. The transportation back will not be provided. However, Porto is well served with transportation by Bolt/ Uber, taxis and bus.

Informations

- Registration Desk** On 22nd April, the registration desk will be open from 15h00 to 15h30, at the **main entrance of i3S**. On 23rd April, the registration desk will be open from 8h30 to 9h00, at **gate 1 of Super Bock Arena**.
- Name Badges** For identification and security purposes, participants must wear their name badges when in the venues. The use of the badge is mandatory for the access to the coffee breaks and lunches.
- Presentation instructions**
- KEYNOTE SESSIONS**
Two 1-hour keynote sessions start and close the PCM scientific program. Lectures will last for 35 minutes followed by a 20-minute discussion.
- PLENARY SESSIONS**
Three Plenary sessions with two invited speakers each, will take place during the PCM, opening and closing the activities of the 23rd April, and opening the activities of the 24th April. Invited Speakers will have 30 minutes to present their work, and the discussion will take place after the two presentations in each Plenary Session, in a 20-minute round table with chairs and experts.
- PARALLEL SESSIONS**
Eight Parallel sessions with three selected speakers (from abstract submission) each, will take place during the PCM. Oral communications should last up to 15 minutes, and the discussion will take place following the three selected presentations in each Parallel Session, in a 20-minute round table with chairs and experts.
- GET2GETHERS WITH PATIENTS**
Two 75-minutes Get2Gether sessions with patients will take place during the PCM after lunch on the 23rd and 24th April.

These interactive sessions, tailored to discuss patient-centered subjects, will bring together patients, patients' representatives, PREVENTABLE project members and PCM participants. Any presentation should be provided to the session chairs on site, in a USB key, 15 minutes before the session start.

Information for all Speakers

Speakers for the 22nd April should hand in their presentations, in a USB key, in the auditorium of i3S before 15h00.

23rd April

Speakers for the sessions held in the **Auditorium** should hand in their presentations in the Auditorium at the Super Bock Arena, at 8h30 (morning sessions) and 13h00 (afternoon sessions). Speakers for the sessions held in the **Room 1** should hand in their presentations in the Room 1 at the Super Bock Arena, at 8h30 (morning sessions) and 13h00 (afternoon sessions).

24th April

Speakers for the sessions held in the **Auditorium** should hand in their presentations in the Auditorium at the Super Bock Arena, at 8h30 (morning sessions) and 13h00 (afternoon sessions).

Speakers for the sessions held in the **Room 1** should hand in their presentations in the Room 1 at the Super Bock Arena, at 8h30 (morning sessions) and 13h00 (afternoon sessions).

Speakers will be requested to provide their presentation in a USB key. A data show and personal computer will be at the presenters' disposal. A technician will be available to make sure that you have successfully uploaded your presentation. Please note that if you need to use your own laptop, this needs to be tested before sessions start, ideally during a break.

Poster Presentations

Posters should have 1.20m high and 0.90m wide, and will be presented on the designated poster area in two sessions:

Session 1 | 23rd April, 13:15-14:30

Session 2 | 24th April, 13:15-14:30

Authors are requested to put up their posters before Session 1 and should remove them at the end of Poster Session 2.

Please check in the **Poster Communication's List**, at the end of the abstract book, which session you will be presenting in.

Internet Access

Wireless Internet is available for free in both venues:

i3S Network:

i3S_Temp | Password: Password2015

Super Bock Arena Network

Super Bock Arena: Free open Wi-Fi | Password: Not required

Parking

Please note that i3S and Super Bock Arena do not offer parking space.

Program

DAY 1

APRIL 22ND | VENUE: i3S

15:00 - 15:30

REGISTRATION

15:30 - 16:00

Auditoria Mariano Gago
(main) & Corino de Andrade

OPENING SESSION

Chairs: Carla Oliveira & Tamara Milagre

Porto Cancer Meeting & Ipatimup

Manuel Sobrinho Simões, Director of Ipatimup, PT

Porto Cancer Meeting & i3S

Claudio Sunkel, Director of i3S, PT

The Preventable project: A real-world data opportunity

Carla Oliveira, Chair Porto Cancer Meeting & Coordinator PREVENTABLE

16:15 - 18:15

Auditoria Mariano Gago
(main) & Corino de Andrade

KEYNOTE SESSION 1

Chair: Carla Oliveira

16:15 - 17:15

Keynote Lecture 1Investing in Healthcare for those at High Hereditary
Risk of CancerNicoline Hoogerbrugge, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen &
ERN Genturis former Coordinator, NL

PREVENTABLE Learning Hub - A clinical story PHTS (video)

17:15 - 18:15

Roundtable | From Health Research to Policy: closing the gap to enhance inherited cancer care**Panel Moderator**

Teresa Firmino, Science Editor of Jornal Público, PT

Panelists

Enrique Terol, Health Counsellor, Permanent Representation of Spain to the EU

Álvaro Santos Almeida, Executive Director of NHS, PT

Nicoline Hoogerbrugge, ERN Genturis former Coordinator, NL

Carla Oliveira, PREVENTABLE Coordinator, i3S & Ipatimup, PT

Tamara Milagre, President EVITA Patient Association, PT

Alexandre Quintanilha, Coordinator 10th Anniversary of i3S, PT19:00 - 20:30
i3S Hall

PORTO DE HONRA AND LIGHT DINNER

DAY 2**APRIL 23RD | Venue: Super Bock Arena**

08:30 - 09:00

REGISTRATION

09:00 - 18:00
Learning Hub Room**PREVENTABLE LEARNING HUB EXHIBITION**09:00 - 10:30
Auditorium**PLENARY SESSION I***Health Economics and Clinical Research*

Chairs Céu Mateus & Judith Balmaña

09:00 - 09:10

A clinical story – HDGC (video)

09:10 - 09:40

Addressing the cancer burden: challenges and opportunities in prevention and early detection

Liora Bowers, OECD, FR

09:40 - 10:10	<p>Health data-driven research: impacts in cancer management and outcomes Eva Morris, Oxford University, UK</p>
10:10 - 10:30	<p>Roundtable</p> <p>Facilitator Alexis Strader, EHMA</p> <p>Participants Céu Mateus, Liora Bowers, Judith Balmaña, Eva Morris & HDGC Patient Representative</p>
10:30 - 11:00	COFFEE BREAK
11:00 - 12:15 Auditorium	<p>PARALLEL SESSION I</p> <p><i>Proactive Prevention, Cancer Progression and Resistance</i></p> <p>Chairs Ana Azevedo, Alexander Sun Zhang, Joana Paredes & PHTS Patient Representative</p>
11:00 - 11:10	A clinical story - PHTS (video)
11:10 - 11:25	<p>SO1 - From treatment to proactive prevention in Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes: evidences from the PREVENTABLE multicentric cohort Sara B. Pereira, i3S, PT</p>
11:25 - 11:40	<p>SO2 - ETV6: JAK2 fusion promotes central nervous system invasion in a pre-clinical model of B-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia Telma Costa, i3S, PT</p>
11:40 - 11:55	<p>SO3 - Macrophage-driven mechanisms of radiotherapy resistance in triple-negative breast cancer Ana Borges, i3S, PT</p>

11:55 - 12:15

Roundtable**Participants**

Session Chairs and Session Speakers

11:00 - 12:15

Room 1

PARALLEL SESSION II*Preventive Care: Costs, Outcomes and Communication***Chairs** Stefan Aretz, Katja Verbeek
& PJS Patient Representative

11:00 - 11:10

A clinical story - PJS (video)

11:10 - 11:25

SO4 - Preventive management of CDH1 carriers improves survival and reduces healthcare costs: a European multicenter real-world study

Ricardo Amorim, i3S, PT

11:25 - 11:40

SO5 - Barriers and enablers influencing clinical teams recommendations of RTRS care pathways: A qualitative study

Susana Mourão, CHRC, NOVA Medical School, PT

11:40 - 11:55

SO6 - Healthcare cost of cancer surveillance vs. treatment in Peutz-Jeghers syndrome: Real-world evidence from the PREVENTABLE project

Amalia Nanciu, University Hospital Bonn, DE

11:55 - 12:15

Roundtable**Participants**

Session Chairs and Session Speakers

12:15 - 13:15

LUNCH

13:15 - 13:35

Auditorium

CORPORATE SATELLITE 1 - ILC satellite symposium:
New era of cancer biology with Aviti24**Agnieszka Ciesielska** Senior Technical Sales Scientist Element Biosciences

13:15 - 13:35

Room 1

CORPORATE SATELLITE 2 - Cureety satellite symposium:
Early Symptom Detection in Oncology: Improving Patient Safety
and Optimizing Clinical Workflows Through Telemonitoring
Maria Neto Cureety

13:15 - 14:30

Poster Room

POSTER SESSION 1**13:15 - 14:30**

Get2Gether Room

GET2GETHER 1 WITH PATIENTS*Genetic Testing and Family Communication*

Chairs Luzia Garrido, Marion Rolain, Maiara Moreto,
Ana Gomes & Adriana Costal

Participants

PREVENTABLE syndromes Patients and Patient Representatives

14:30 - 15:45

Auditorium

PARALLEL SESSION III*Translational Advances and cost of care
in TP53-Related Cancers*

Chairs Ricardo Amorim, Svetlana Lagercrantz & Patient Representative

14:30 - 14:40

A clinical story - LFS (video)

14:40 - 14:55

SO7 - Clinical Outcomes and Cost-effectiveness of Preventive
Surveillance versus Treatment in Li-Fraumeni Syndrome:
Results from the European PREVENTABLE Project
Marion Rolain, Université de Rouen Normandie, FR

14:55 - 15:10

SO8 - IARC dataset curation reveals new genotype-
phenotype associations in Heritable TP53-Related Cancers
Alexandre Dias, i3S, PT

15:10 - 15:25

SO9 - Deciphering the impact of cancer cell's secretome and
its derived peptide VGF on breast cancer brain metastasis
Rita Carvalho, i3S, PT

15:25 - 15:45

Roundtable**Participants**

Session Chairs and Session Speakers

14:30 - 15:45

Room 1

PARALLEL SESSION IV*PHTS and Lynch syndromes:
Biomarkers, Care Uptake and Costs***Chairs** Janneke Schuurs-hoeijmakers, Ida Schrøder
& PHTS Patient Representative

14:30 - 14:40

A clinical story - PHTS (video)

14:40 - 14:55

S10 - Costs of cancer prevention versus cancer treatment in
PTEN Hamartoma Tumor Syndrome: EU PREVENTABLE project
Katja Verbeek, Radboud University Medical Center, NL

14:55 - 15:10

S11 - Liquid Biopsy-Based MSI Detection in Lynch Syndrome:
Platform Comparison and Diagnostic Performance
Davide Ferrari, Fondazione IRCCS Istituto Nazionale dei Tumori, IT

15:10 - 15:25

S12 - Barriers and enablers influencing patients uptake of
RTRS care pathways: A qualitative study
Maiara Moreto, NOVA Medical School, PT

15:25 - 15:45

Roundtable**Participants**

Session Chairs and Session Speakers

15:45 - 16:30

COFFEE BREAK

16:30 - 18:00

Auditorium

PLENARY SESSION II*Social Sciences & Basic Research***Chairs** Marta Marques, Sandra Tavares & LFS Patient Representative

16:30 - 16:40	A clinical story - LFS (video)
16:40 - 17:10	Using behaviour change frameworks to understand patient and provider behaviours: A Systems perspective to improving health care and outcomes Fabiana Lorencatto, University College London, UK
17:10 - 17:40	The p53 Tumor Suppressor Network Scott W. Lowe, Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center, USA
17:40 - 18:00	Roundtable Facilitator Sérgio Oliveira, EHMA Participants Marta Marques, Sandra Tavares, Fabiana Lorencatto, Scott W. Lowe & LFS Patient Representative
19:00	DEPARTURE BY BUS TO THE CONFERENCE DINNER
19:30	CONFERENCE DINNER

DAY 3

APRIL 24TH | Venue: Super Bock Arena

09:00 - 18:00 Learning Hub Room	PREVENTABLE LEARNING HUB EXHIBITION
09:00 - 10:30 Auditorium	PLENARY SESSION III <i>Health management & Communication</i> Chairs Alexis Strader, Nuno Marcos, Nichole Holm & Patient Representative
09:00 - 09:10	A clinical story - HLRCC (video)
09:10 - 09:40	Towards a Rare Diseases Strategy at Global and EU level: state of play Enrique Terol, Health Counsellor, Permanent Representation of Spain to the EU

09:40 - 10:10	<p>What works and why? Evidence-based cancer risk communication for shared decisions Yasmina Okan. Universitat Pompeu Fabra, ES</p>
10:10 - 10:30	<p>Roundtable</p> <p>Facilitator Maral Aghababai, EHMA</p> <p>Participants Alexis Strader, Nichole Holm, Enrique Terol, Yasmina Okan, HLRCC Patient Representative</p>
10:30 - 11:00	COFFEE BREAK
11:00 - 12:15 Auditorium	<p>PARALLEL SESSION V</p> <p><i>When Early is Too Late: Killing Cancers</i> Chairs Amalia Nanciu, Andrew Titman & HDGC Patient Representative</p>
11:00 - 11:10	A clinical story - HLRCC (video)
11:10 - 11:25	<p>S13 - Real-world data to evaluate care pathways and costs in hereditary leiomyomatosis and renal cell cancer syndrome: PREVENTABLE study Laura Duran-Lozano, VHIO Vall d'Hebron Institut d'Oncologia, ES</p>
11:25 - 11:40	<p>S14 - Pancreatic enhancer deletion drives acinar cell plasticity and neoplastic transformation through chromatin remodeling Marta Duque, i3S, PT</p>
11:40 - 11:55	<p>S15 - Cost-effectiveness modelling in rare tumour risk syndromes (RTRS) - results and challenges Céu Mateus, Lancaster University, UK</p>
11:55 - 12:15	<p>Roundtable</p> <p>Participants Session Chairs and Session speakers</p>

11:00 - 12:15

Room 1

PARALLEL SESSION VI*Melanoma and Blood Cancers: Risks, Care Costs and Outcomes***Chairs** Hildegunn Vetti, Laura Duran-Lozano & FM Patient Representative

11:00 - 11:10

A clinical story - FM (video)

11:10 - 11:25

S16 - Familial Melanoma: an Evaluation of clinical outcome and healthcare costs in the EU PREVENTABLE project

Birte Lundhaug, Haukeland University Hospital, NO

11:25 - 11:40

S17 - Atypical Cases of POT1 Tumor Predisposition Syndrome - Multicentric Repor

Isabel Serra Nunes, Centro de Genética Médica Dr. Jacinto Magalhães, PT

11:40 - 11:55

S18 - Thymopoiesis and thymic structural alterations after T-cell lymphoblastic lymphoma regression

Juliana Cunha, i3S, PT

11:55 - 12:15

Roundtable**Participants**

Session Chairs and Session speakers

12:15 - 13:15

LUNCH

13:15 - 14:30

Poster Room

POSTER SESSION 2**13:15 - 14:30**

Get2Gether Room

GET2GETHER 2 WITH PATIENTS*Financial burden and Social stigma***Chairs** Nuno Ribeiro, Carolina di Fabrizio, Liliana Sousa & Vitor Neves**Participants**

PREVENTABLE syndromes Patients and Patient Representatives

14:30 - 15:45

Auditorium

PARALLEL SESSION VII*HDGC: Risk, Tumour Initiation and Cost-effectiveness***Chairs** Bárbara Peleteiro, Claude Houdayer & HDGC Patient Representative

14:30 - 14:40

A clinical story - HDGC (video)

14:40 - 14:55

S19 Cost-effectiveness model care pathways of Rare Tumour Risk Syndrome - the case of Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer
Andrew Titman, Lancaster University, UK

14:55 - 15:10

S20 - Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer onset: a matter of extrusion imbalances driven by E-cadherin and Filamin A interactions

Soraia Melo, i3S, PT

15:10 - 15:25

S21 - CTNNA1 germline alterations are positively associated with hereditary diffuse gastric cancer development

Silvana Lobo, i3S, PT

15:25 - 15:45

Roundtable**Participants**

Session Chairs and Session speakers

14:30 - 15:45

Room 1

PARALLEL SESSION VIII*Care Pathways within and beyond Europe: Costs and Forgetfulness***Chairs** Sara Pereira, Joan Brunet & BHDS Patient representative

14:30 - 14:40

A clinical story - BHDS (video)

14:40 - 14:55

S22 - Clinical Impact and Healthcare Expenditure of Prevention versus Treatment in Birt-Hogg-Dubé Syndrome: Findings from the EU PREVENTABLE Project

Adriana Costal Tirado, IDIBGI-Girona Biomedical Research Institute Dr. Josep Trueta, ES

14:55 - 15:10	S23 - Contributing to cancer equity: omics characterization and establishment of patient-derived cancer models from sub-Saharan African patients Luísa Pereira, i3S, PT
15:10 - 15:25	S24 - Outcomes of distress assessment in carriers of a pathogenic variant related to Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer: a retrospective study Paula Rodrigues, IPO, PT
15:25 - 15:45	Roundtable Participants Session Chairs and Session speakers
15:45 - 16:30	COFFEE BREAK
16:30 - 17:30 Auditorium	KEYNOTE SESSION II Chairs Carla Oliveira, Sara Pereira & Liliana Sousa
16:30 - 17:30	Keynote Lecture 2 Genome-Wide Liquid Biopsy for Personalized Cancer Interception Zachariah Foda, Johns Hopkins, USA
17:45 - 18:15 Auditorium	AWARDS AND FAREWELL Claudio Sunkel, Carla Oliveira

Invited Speakers' Biographies

Nicoline Hoogerbrugge

Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen,
The Netherlands

Prof Nicoline Hoogerbrugge, MD, PhD, is affiliated to the Department of Human Genetics, Radboud University Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands. She is a clinical expert in hereditary cancer, with special expertise in PHTS (PTEN hamartoma tumour syndrome), hereditary breast and ovarian cancer and hereditary gastrointestinal cancer. She has initiated and chaired the European Reference Network on Genetic Tumour Risk Syndromes (ERN GENTURIS) (www.genturis.eu). Over the last 10 years, her research has mainly focused on finding more knowledge on the phenotype and cancer risks of PHTS, new genetic factors for gastrointestinal cancer and the implementation of current knowledge on hereditary cancer in daily practice.

Teresa Firmino

Jornal Público, Portugal

Teresa Firmino has a degree in Mass Media Communication from Lisbon New University. She is science journalist at newspaper Público since 1992. Since 2012 is the Science editor of Público. During 2008-2009, she was fellow at the Knight Science Journalism Fellowships at Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA. In 2025, the American Association Cancer Research (AACR) awarded her co-author work “Farewell, my stomach” with the “June L. Biedler Prize for Cancer Journalism”. In 2025, “Farewell, my stomach” was also awarded by the Portuguese Cancer League. In 2023, she received the Cultural Journalism Award by the Portuguese Society of Authors (SPA) for her work on scientific culture as science journalist. In 2017, she received the Media Ciência Viva Award, for an “exceptional work on promoting science and technology on Portuguese mass media”. She published four books of scientific dissemination (three as co-author). Her most recent book is *The Future of the Planet - So Much is in Our Hands*, (2020), published in Portuguese by the Fundação Francisco Manuel dos Santos.

Enrique Terol

Health Counsellor, Permanent Representation of Spain to the EU, Spain

Enrique Terol works as Health Counsellor in the Permanent Representation of Spain to the European Union and represents the interests of Spain in the area of health. He is MD, specialized in Family and Community Medicine, MSc and PhD in Public Health and has followed specialisation courses on healthcare management and quality of healthcare. His professional experience includes the clinical practice, managerial positions as Medical Director and CEO of Primary and Specialised Healthcare in private and public institutions and healthcare planning. He was Deputy General Director of Quality and Health Planning of the Ministry of Health of Spain between 2004 and 2008 in charge of the development inter alia of the Spanish Strategy of ischemic heart disease, Diabetes, Mental health, Rare Diseases and Patient safety. He worked as Health Attaché in the Spanish Permanent Representation to the EU and coordinator of the area of Health in the Spanish Presidency of the EU between 2008 and 2011. From 2011 to 2020, he worked as Seconded National Expert and as Policy officer in DG SANTE developing the legal and organisational bases for and the set-up and implementation of the European Reference Networks (ERN) for complex and rare diseases under the framework of the Directive of Cross-border Health. Between 2021 and 2022 worked as team leader in the Medical Service of the European Commission. Since 2022 he works as Health counsellor at Spanish Permanent Representation and coordinated the health area during the Spanish Presidency of the EU in 2023.

Álvaro Santos Almeida

Executive Directorate of the Portuguese
National Health System, Portugal

Álvaro Almeida is Executive Director of the Portuguese National Health Service at DE-SNS (Direção Executiva do Serviço Nacional de Saúde). He is also Associate Professor at Universidade do Porto, Faculdade de Economia, and Professor of Economics and Health Systems at Porto Business School. Álvaro holds a PhD in Economics from the London School of Economics and Political Science and a master's and first degree in Economics from Universidade do Porto. Álvaro has expertise in health economics and healthcare management. Previously, he was a Member of the Portuguese Parliament, Porto City Councilor, President of the Regional Health Administration of the North of Portugal, President of the Portuguese Healthcare Regulatory Authority, Consultant to the Portuguese Ministry of Health, and Economist at the International Monetary Fund in Washington DC. He has published in several economics and health journals and was awarded the Gold Medal for Distinguished Services for the Ministry of Health.

Carla Oliveira

i3S – Instituto de Investigação e Inovação em Saúde,
Porto, Portugal

Carla Oliveira is Principal Investigator and Group Leader at i3S, Professor at the Faculty of Medicine of Porto University, and consultant for hereditary cancer syndromes at Ipatimup Diagnostics (Portugal). Graduated in Biochemistry (1996), earned a PhD in Human Biology (2002, Cambridge and Porto), and completed postdoctoral training in Paris and Vancouver. She leads a research group from 2013 at i3S, and gained international recognition for discoveries on *CDH1* and *CTNNA1*-related diseases, hereditary diffuse gastric cancer, genotype-phenotype correlations, and development of stomach-on-a-chip models. She serves as Secretary General of European Society of Human Genetics Executive Committee (2017–2027), Chair of its Scientific Program Committee (2026–2030), and Portuguese National Coordinator of ERN-GENTURIS. She leads the EU PREVENTABLE project on cost of prevention in cancer-predisposed carriers. She has secured over €17M in funding, delivered 180+ talks, published 225 papers (H-index 77; >25,000 citations), and trained over 75 researchers, including over 30 students towards MSc and PhD.

Tamara Hussong Milagre

EVITA Patients Association, Lisbon, Portugal

Tamara Hussong Milagre is a leading advocate for hereditary cancer, known for empowering patients and influencing healthcare policy in Europe. She founded and presides over EVITA Association - Hereditary Cancer, supporting Portuguese families since 2011. She serves as an ePAG representative at ERN GENTURIS, contributing to the HBOC/Prostate group and taskforces on care, education and registries. Her training includes the ESO Master Class, the EUPATI Patient Expert program and the EURORDIS Leadership School. Tamara collaborates with Infarmed and is part of the EFPIA Oncology Platform Sounding Board. She co-founded the Hereditary Cancer Syndromes group of the Portuguese Society of Oncology and contributes to PT_MedGen, the Portuguese Cancer Mission Hub and the Institute of Evidence-Based Health. Internationally, she engages in working groups on metastatic breast cancer and genomic medicine. In 2020, she received the Medal of Scientific Merit.

Alexandre Quintanilha

10th Anniversary of i3S Coordinator, Porto, Portugal

His parents (father from the Azores, mother from Berlin) always fostered his curiosity. Spent the first 25 years of his life in Southern Africa, the following 20 years in the Bay Area, California and the last 35 in Portugal. Was lucky enough to have led numerous research groups that allowed him to share ideas with inspiring people. With a Ph.D. in theoretical physics, he quickly moved to biophysics and physiology, focusing on oxidative stress to living organisms and our understanding of Risk. Launched and ran several multidisciplinary research centers and institutes, as well as new graduate and undergraduate courses at UC Berkeley, the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory and the University of Porto. Chaired several Research Committees at OECD, ESF, EU and Portugal. As a member of Parliament, he helped to consolidate knowledge-based policies.

Liora Bowers

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), Paris, France

Liora Bowers is a Policy Analyst at the OECD's Health Division, where she works in partnership with the European Commission to assess trends and developments in cancer care as part of the European Cancer Inequalities Registry.

She also leads efforts on international benchmarking of cancer care quality indicators at the OECD. She has deep experience gained at leading policy research institutes in California and Israel, where she worked on issues such as health system financing, delivery system reform, and social inequalities.

Liora holds a BS in International Economics from Georgetown University and an MBA and Masters in Public Health from University of California, Berkeley.

Eva Morris

Oxford University, Oxford, UK

Eva Morris is Professor of Health Data Epidemiology within the Big Data Institute and Oxford Population Health. She works in the field of health data research with a particularly strong interest in national cancer datasets. She has a portfolio of highly applied research based around the use of linked NHS datasets to investigate the management and outcome of common diseases and a particular focus on colorectal cancer.

Fabiana Lorencatto

University College London, London, UK

Dr Fabiana Lorencatto is Professor of Behavioural and Implementation Sciences and Co-Director of the Centre for Behaviour Change at University College London.

A behavioural scientist, her work applies theory-driven methods to understand individual, social, and environmental influences on behaviour and to design effective interventions. Her research focuses on healthcare provider behaviour, quality improvement, and environmental sustainability, with methodological expertise in process evaluation and intervention fidelity.

She also uses behavioural frameworks in systematic reviews to identify key mechanisms of change. Her multidisciplinary research spans areas including antimicrobial resistance, infection control, medication adherence, maternal health, and plastic waste reduction. Fabiana completed her PhD in Health Psychology at UCL in 2013 and has held several academic leadership roles. She teaches across degree programmes, supervises postgraduate researchers, and provides consultancy and training in behavioural science.

Scott W. Lowe

Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center, USA

Scott W. Lowe is the Chair of Cancer Biology & Genetics Program at the Sloan Kettering Institute (SKI); Chair of Geoffrey Beene Cancer Research Center and Investigator at the Howard Hughes Medical Institute. He began his studies in chemical engineering at the University of Wisconsin–Madison in 1982 before switching to biology, later working as a lab technician in a hypercholesterolemia lab. He pursued graduate training at MIT, earning a PhD focused on the role of the tumor suppressor p53 in cancer, and remained there for postdoctoral work. His early research established p53 as essential for cell death in response to DNA damage. In 1995, he launched his own lab at Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, where he helped discover oncogene-induced senescence, a key tumor-suppressive mechanism, and advanced insights into personalized cancer therapy. His work has broadly examined tumor suppressor genes using RNA interference and CRISPR-based models. In 2011, he joined Memorial Sloan Kettering, uncovering links between senescence therapies and immune surveillance. An HHMI Investigator, he has been elected to the National Academy of Sciences and the National Academy of Medicine.

Yasmina Okan

Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona, Spain

Dr. Yasmina Okan is a Ramón y Cajal Senior Research Fellow in the Department of Communication at Pompeu Fabra University (Spain), where she leads the Health Communication research line. She is also a Visiting Senior Research Fellow at the Center for Decision Research, University of Leeds (UK), where she was formerly Associate Professor in Behavioral Decision Making. Dr. Okan is an internationally recognized expert in health risk perception and communication, drawing on the psychology of judgment and decision making to improve how complex medical information is conveyed to patients and the public. She has led and contributed to international projects on personal cancer risk communication and public health messaging for cancer screening, funded by agencies including Cancer Research UK, the Dutch Cancer Society and the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, and has published extensively on evidence-based strategies to supported informed, shared decisions.

Zachariah Foda

Johns Hopkins, Baltimore, Maryland, USA

Zachariah Foda, MD, PhD is an Assistant Professor of Medicine and Oncology and gastroenterologist specializing in cancer prevention. He leads the Johns Hopkins Colon Cancer Risk Assessment Clinic, providing evaluations for individuals with elevated colon cancer risk. His expertise includes familial adenomatous polyposis, Lynch syndrome, juvenile polyposis, Peutz-Jeghers syndrome, and other polyposis syndromes

Dr. Foda obtained his medical and doctoral degrees at Stony Brook University. He completed internal medicine residency at Johns Hopkins and remained for fellowship in gastroenterology and hepatology. He uses advanced screening and genetic testing to identify those who benefit from intensive surveillance or preventive interventions.

Dr. Foda's research focuses on liquid biopsies and cell-free DNA fragmentomes for early cancer detection, aiming to translate these technologies into personalized cancer interception strategies for patients with hereditary cancer syndromes.

Keynotes & Plenary Lectures

ABSTRACTS

01

Investing in Healthcare for those at High Hereditary Risk of Cancer

Nicoline Hoogerbrugge^{1,2} | KEYNOTE SPEAKER

¹ Human Genetics, Radboud university Medical Center, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

² European Reference Network Genetic Tumor Risk Syndromes (ERN GENTURIS)

Investing in care for hereditary cancer is not a luxury, but a necessary choice for a sustainable and future-proof healthcare system. Hereditary forms of cancer affect families for generations and carry not only major medical consequences, but also significant social and economic impacts. Yet the potential of early identification of those at high hereditary risk and prevention of cancer, is still not fully utilized.

When individuals at high hereditary risk of cancer are identified in time, targeted surveillance, preventive treatments, and personalized guidance can be implemented. This saves lives. At the same time, it prevents cancer from being detected only at a late stage, when treatments are more intensive, more expensive, and less effective. Investing in hereditary cancer care is therefore not only an investment in health, but also in affordable healthcare.

It is also a matter of fairness in healthcare. Everyone should have access to genetic diagnostics, counselling, and specialized support, regardless of where they live or their socioeconomic background. Without targeted investment, access to this care will remain unequal, leaving high-risk groups unnecessarily vulnerable.

By investing now in research, genetic testing, expert centres and expert networks of hereditary forms of cancer, we can take a powerful step toward preventive medicine. This aligns with a broader societal shift: moving from treating disease to preventing it as well.

Our choices will determine whether we continue to react to disease, or actively invest in prevention and early detection. Investing in hereditary cancer care means choosing to save lives, control healthcare costs, and offer families hope and security for generations to come.

02

Addressing the cancer burden: challenges and opportunities in prevention and early detection

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Liora Bowers | PLENARY SESSION SPEAKER

Authors: OECD / European Commission | Liora Bowers, Caroline Berchet

The presentation draws on findings from the OECD/ European Commission's collaboration on the European Cancer Inequalities Registry, including the [EU Country Cancer Profiles Synthesis Report 2025](#), the 2026 [Delivering High Value Cancer Care](#) report, and the 2025 [Assessing cancer care quality in OECD countries](#). These findings are adapted to the context of hereditary cancers and summarized below:

Across the European Union, cancer poses an increasingly urgent public health challenge. Five new cancer cases are diagnosed every minute—amounting to 2.7 million annual diagnoses—and incidence has risen by 30% since 2000. Although part of this increase is driven by population aging, age-standardized trends show a genuine rise in cancer diagnoses, including a marked surge increase among women aged 15–49. Increased earlier age cancer onset – including among cancer types such as breast, colorectal and melanoma that can have a heritable component – has profound implications for patients and health systems due to the treatment, monitoring and survivorship needs of younger people.

The societal impact of cancer is substantial. Cancer care cost EU countries an estimated EUR 120 billion in 2023, with percapita spending projected to increase by nearly 60% by 2050 due to aging populations. Productivity losses are equally significant: cancer-related employment losses are projected to reach the equivalent of 178 fulltime workers per 100 000 population through 2050, and hereditary cancers—given their often-earlier onset—may thus account for a disproportionate share of these losses.

Improving outcomes for people with all cancers – but specifically those with hereditary risk – requires strengthened health literacy and greater individual awareness of their cancer risk.

Prevention strategies are central to reducing cancer burden. For certain hereditary cancers, riskreduction may involve interventions such as prophylactic mastectomy or the removal of ovaries and fallopian tubes; however these options must be carefully considered through a process of shared-decision making with patients.

Early diagnosis remains critical to achieving better health outcomes. Populationbased screening programmes for breast and colorectal cancer—two of the most common hereditary cancers—exist in most OECD countries. While these screening programmes have demonstrated clear benefits in improving early detection, gaps persist: approximately onequarter of colorectal cancers are first detected in emergency settings. Beyond agebased criteria, OECD countries are increasingly adopting riskstratified screening approaches to increase the chances of identifying cancer in those at higher risk and to support more cost-effective use of healthcare resources.

FUNDING/ ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Funding was provided by the European Union (EU) as part of the European Cancer Inequalities Registry - a flagship initiative of the Europe's Beating Cancer Plan.

03

Realising the potential of big data in cancer policy and care: challenges and opportunities in the United Kingdom's National Health Service

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Eva JA Morris¹ | PLENARY SESSION SPEAKER

¹ Big Data Institute and Nuffield Department of Population Health, University of Oxford, Oxford, UK

For decades, cancer outcomes in the United Kingdom have lagged behind those attained by many of its economic neighbours. Closing this gap, and improving survival rates across the entire population, has been a Government priority for many years but, as yet, the differences have persisted.

Recently, new strategies have been adopted. These include a bold ambition to transform the National Health Service (NHS) by shifting from 'analogue to digital'. The intention is to harness the hugely rich cancer data within the NHS, analyse it with cutting edge data science techniques and generate evidence that will revolutionise services to create a step-change in diagnosis, care and outcomes. The UK is in a unique position because cancer data collected from NHS patients is widely recognised to represent one of the most comprehensive collections anywhere in the world. The potential is truly enormous. Yet the UK has had these rich data for decades and, despite many previous initiatives to capitalize on them, they have not yet come close to realising all that is promised.

Using the example of colorectal cancer, this presentation will discuss the challenges and opportunities that surround the use of big data to drive improvements in cancer care and outcome and explore what is required to truly realise their full potential both in the UK and beyond.

FUNDING / ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This presentation will include data provided by patients and collected by the NHS as part of their care and support

This presentation includes work funded by Bowel Cancer UK, Cancer Research UK, the National Institute of Health Research Biomedical Research Centre: Oxford & Health Data Research UK

04

Using behaviour change frameworks to understand patient and provider behaviours: A Systems perspective to improving health care and outcomes

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Fabiana Lorencatto | PLENARY SESSION SPEAKER

Centre for Behaviour Change, University College London, London, UK

Implementing new technologies, services and treatments in healthcare, or improving experiences of care and outcomes, will almost always require someone to do something differently. That is, it will require behaviour change, not just of one stakeholder group, but often of multiple actors, at different levels in the healthcare system: from patients and public, through to clinicians, teams, managers and leadership, through to commissioners and policy makers. A behaviour change, systems approach to thinking about improvement in health and healthcare is therefore often needed.

This presentation will explore how behaviour change models can provide a unifying structure for understanding the factors that influence both patient and healthcare professional behaviours. Adopting a systems approach, the talk will highlight how behaviours cannot be understood in isolation but must be viewed within the broader healthcare context, including organisational structures, social dynamics, and resource constraints. This perspective allows for a more holistic understanding of how multiple factors interact to shape health outcomes, moving beyond individual-level explanations toward integrated, multi-level insights.

Healthcare behaviours are often complex and shaped by interacting psychological, social and environmental influences. This talk will specifically discuss how frameworks such as the COM-B model (Capability, Opportunity, Motivation- Behaviour) can offer a practical and theory-informed way to identify and organise these influences, enabling a more systematic understanding of why behaviours occur and how they can be changed. Drawing on prior research with patient populations for chronic health conditions such as diabetes, the presentation

will illustrate how COM-B can be used to identify barriers and facilitators to behaviours such as uptake and delivery of diabetic retinopathy screening, both from the perspective of people with diabetes as well as multidisciplinary clinicians. These examples demonstrate how mapping behavioural determinants onto capability, opportunity, and motivation can inform the subsequent design of targeted, multi-level interventions. The talk will also briefly extend these insights to applications in cancer care, highlighting examples of how behaviour change frameworks such as COM-B have supported understanding and improving cancer care, including communication between patients and healthcare professionals, as well as engagement with screening, treatment, and follow-up care.

Overall, the presentation argues that using a common behavioural science framework such as COM-B, combined with a systems perspective, can enhance our ability to understand and influence health-related behaviours. This approach not only supports more coherent research and intervention design but also contributes to the development of more effective, context-sensitive strategies for improving patient outcomes and healthcare delivery.

05

The p53 Tumor Suppressor Network

Scott W. Lowe | PLENARY SESSION SPEAKER

Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Center, USA

Scott W. Lowe lab has had a long-standing interest in the role and regulation of the p53 tumor suppressor. Mutations in the p53 gene (TP53) are often associated with aggressive tumor behavior and poor patient prognosis, and p53 mutant tumors display rampant genomic instability. Wild-type p53 is often engaged in response to cellular damage, where it acts to regulate genes that promote cell-cycle arrest, apoptosis, senescence, differentiation, and autophagy. In addition to these cell-autonomous activities, p53 can promote the secretion of a variety of factors that influence the tissue microenvironment.

A major unanswered question in the field is what p53 effector functions mediate its tumor suppressor functions and how their disruption gives rise to highly aggressive tumors. Historically our laboratory has emphasized understanding how p53 regulates apoptosis and cellular senescence, though we have also become interested in the ability of p53 to restrict lineage plasticity. Using a murine model of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) in which endogenous p53 can be switched on and off using a tetracycline-inducible shRNA, we showed that restoring p53 in advanced PDAC increased a-ketoglutarate levels and activated a transcriptional program that drove tumor cells into a premalignant state. These observations imply that p53 loss is required to sustain tumor cells in a less-differentiated state and illustrate how mimicking p53 function might have therapeutic benefit.

Current efforts combine a range of multiomic and spatial imaging approaches to understand p53 action and the immediate effects of p53 loss in sporadic cancer progression. p53 inactivation typically arises through a missense mutation in one allele and a “second hit” deletion event that also encompasses adjacent genes. Researchers often regard all p53 mutations as equivalent, though some missense mutants apparently have “gain-of-function” effects. Moreover, the p53 deletions frequently encompass many other genes. Using

chromosome engineering, we also showed that the deletion events target biologically relevant genes whose co-deletion enhances tumorigenesis.

These results challenge the concept of classifying tumors simply as p53 wild-type or mutant. Current efforts in the laboratory are using new CRISPR base-editing methodologies to better understand the functional consequences of allelic variation in p53 mutations. Addressing the role of “genomic instability” in the evolution of p53 mutant tumors, we used a unique model that enables fluorescent tagging of cells that inactivate p53 well before tumors arise to characterize genomic changes from premalignancy to full-blown cancer. The work demonstrated a deterministic pattern of genome evolution involving copy-number alterations that contribute to the malignant potential of p53-mutant cells. Thus, despite the chaotic nature of p53-mutant tumors, their evolution follows rules that may eventually be exploited. Current efforts in the laboratory focus on other aspects of how cells that acquire p53 mutations evolve towards cancer.

06

Towards a Rare Diseases Strategy at Global and EU level: state of play

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Enrique Terol | PLENARY SESSION SPEAKER

Permanent Representation of Spain to the EU Brussels, Belgium;
Ministry of health of Spain, Madrid, Spain

Rare diseases represent a major public health challenge due to their cumulative burden, clinical complexity and persistent inequalities in access to diagnosis, treatment and specialised care. Increasing policy attention at European Union and global levels reflects the need for a more coherent strategic framework.

Recent international developments, notably the 2025 World Health Assembly resolution on rare diseases, mark a turning point in recognising these conditions as a global health priority. Within the EU, this builds on key milestones, including the Commission Communication “Rare Diseases: Europe’s challenges”, the Council Recommendation on rare diseases, and more recent Council Conclusions on the future of the European Health Union.

EU action combines regulatory, policy and funding instruments. Support through EU4Health and its predecessors has enabled joint actions, registries and capacity-building initiatives. In parallel, most Member States have adopted national rare disease strategies over the past decade, contributing to gradual convergence despite differences in implementation.

The European Reference Networks (ERNs), established under Directive 2011/24/EU, represent a central pillar, enhancing cross-border cooperation, expertise sharing and access to specialised care. Patient organisations, particularly EURORDIS through the Rare 2030 Foresight Study, and the European Economic and Social Committee have reinforced calls for a comprehensive EU approach.

Political momentum has increased through recent Council Presidencies (French, Czech, Spanish, Hungarian and Polish), highlighting the need for a European strategy. This is reflected in ongoing work in the European Parliament on an “EU rare disease action plan” (2025/2130(INL)).

Despite progress, gaps remain in governance, coherence and

FUNDING / ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

No specific funding was received for this work. The author acknowledges the contributions of EU institutions, patient organisations and international bodies advancing rare diseases policy.

sustainable funding. Stronger integration into EU instruments, including Horizon Europe and future frameworks, is needed.

Advancing towards a European strategy requires a common framework to prioritise and coordinate actions, supported by robust monitoring and evaluation. This would enable alignment of national strategies with shared EU objectives and improve equity and long-term impact.

07

What works and why? Evidence-based cancer risk communication for shared decisions

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Yasmina Okan | PLENARY SESSION SPEAKER

Department of Communication, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain

In order to make informed decisions about cancer prevention, patients must often navigate complex information, weighing their personal susceptibility against quantitative data on the benefits and harms of different risk-reduction options. A substantial body of research shows that many patients struggle to interpret such information, particularly those with lower health literacy or numeracy skills. Moreover, risk information is not always presented in formats that optimally support comprehension and informed decision-making.

This talk will address the core question of what works and why in cancer risk communication, providing an overview of evidence-based principles designed to support individuals with varying levels of skill.

Recommendations will be grounded on accumulated evidence in the field, including the International Patient Decision Aid Standards (IPDAS) guidelines, as well as recent insights from the Making Numbers Meaningful systematic review, which synthesizes strategies for presenting numerical risk information in ways that improve understanding and usability.

A central focus of the session will be how different communication strategies support shared decision-making by enabling informed and value-concordant and choices, while also considering their potential influence on risk-reducing behavior. Finally, I will discuss the specific challenges inherent in communicating about hereditary cancer, where the interplay of probabilistic information and familial implications adds layers of complexity to the decision-making process. By examining these issues, the talk will highlight emerging directions for more personalized and effective cancer risk communication.

FUNDING / ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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08

Genome-Wide Liquid Biopsy for Personalized Cancer Interception

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Zachariah H. Foda | KEYNOTE SPEAKER

Johns Hopkins School of Medicine, Department of Medicine, Division of Gastroenterology, Baltimore MD, USA

The largest potential strides against cancer mortality lie in early detection. For screening to meaningfully impact outcomes, it must identify early-stage disease, as this offers the greatest opportunity to reduce mortality. Individuals with hereditary cancer syndromes face a lifetime of elevated cancer risk, requiring intensive surveillance and preventive interventions. Traditional screening approaches, while effective, are often invasive, resource-intensive, and imperfect in detecting early-stage disease. Liquid biopsy, including the analysis of cell-free DNA (cfDNA) from a simple blood draw, offers a promising non-invasive alternative.

Our work leverages genome-wide analyses of cfDNA fragmentomes, the characteristic patterns of DNA fragmentation that differ between healthy individuals and those with cancer. The cfDNA fragmentome provides an integrated view of the chromatin, genome, and transcriptome states of normal and cancer cells, offering a multitude of tumor-specific changes beyond mutations alone. Using the DELFI (DNA Evaluation of Fragments for early Interception) approach, we apply machine learning to these genome-wide fragmentome patterns to detect cancer-associated signals before symptoms arise or tumors become visible on imaging.

This approach has demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity across multiple cancer types. In liver cancer, DELFI machine learning models detected hepatocellular carcinoma with high performance across all stages, outperforming traditional biomarkers such as AFP. For ovarian cancer, DELFI demonstrated significantly improved early-stage sensitivity compared to CA-125. The approach has also been validated in clinical trials for lung cancer detection and applied to multi-cancer early detection, where it can distinguish individuals with cancer from healthy individuals while identifying the tissue of origin.

FUNDING /
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported in part by the Dr. Miriam and Sheldon G. Adelson Medical Research Foundation, the Commonwealth Foundation, the Cole Foundation, US National Institutes of Health grants, and Department of Defense grant.

In this talk, I will discuss how genome-wide liquid biopsy approaches can be applied to high-risk populations. I will highlight recent advances in fragmentome analysis and machine learning, explore the challenges of translating these technologies from research to clinical practice, and discuss the potential for personalized cancer interception strategies. The ultimate goal is to intercept cancer at its earliest, most treatable stage transforming how we care for patients at high risk.

Corporate Satellites

01

ILC satellite symposium: New era of cancer biology with Aviti24

Agnieszka Ciesielska | PRESENT AT THE AUDITORIUM
Senior Technical Sales Scientist Element Biosciences

Advances in biological research increasingly require approaches that unify sequencing-based measurements with spatial and phenotypic context at single cell resolution. Here, we present an integrated platform that brings together in situ sequencing and spatially resolved multiomic measurements to enable high-dimensional phenotyping within native biological contexts.

We will describe the technical approach of the platform and discuss its use in drug response pathway analysis, genetic perturbation screening, immune profiling, and dynamic cell-state characterization. By leveraging Avidite Base Chemistry (ABC™) to support direct sequencing of RNA transcripts within cells, the system bypasses conventional library preparation while maintaining accuracy and supporting simultaneous spatial and molecular readouts.

Results from representative examples demonstrate how this approach supports multiomic analyses with reduced experimental complexity. Together, these findings illustrate how spatial co-detection of RNA, protein, and cellular morphology extend beyond traditional genomics to enable high-resolution interrogation of cellular heterogeneity, genotype-phenotype relationships, and dynamic cell-state transitions.

02

Cureety satellite symposium:Early Symptom Detection in Oncology:
Improving Patient Safety and Optimizing
Clinical Workflows Through Telemonitoring**Maria Neto** | PRESENT AT ROOM 1

Cureety

In Portugal, oncology care remains largely reactive, with limited visibility between hospital visits, often leading to late detection of complications and avoidable care escalation. This presentation will explore how continuous patient monitoring can support a shift towards more proactive, data-driven care, improving outcomes while reducing unnecessary emergency episodes, hospitalisations and treatment disruptions.

It will also highlight the impact on clinical teams, showing how structured, real-time patient data enables better prioritization, streamlines workflows, and helps alleviate pressure on already overloaded healthcare professionals, contributing to more efficient and sustainable oncology care delivery.

Oral Communications

ABSTRACTS

ORAL COMMUNICATION'S LIST | DAY 1

OC1**From treatment to proactive prevention in Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes – Evidences from the PREVENTABLE multicentric cohort**

Sara B. Pereira, Ricardo Amorim, Liliana Sousa, Adriana Costal, Katja Verbeek, Patricia Faure, Birte B. Lundhaug, Bárbara Peleteiro, Luzia Garrido, Laura Duran-Lozano, Silvana Lobo, Amalia Nanciu, Irène Stenfors, Alexander Sun Zhang, Marbelia Fernandes, Paula Boaventura, João Fonseca; Daniela Duarte, Diana Ferreira, António Moreira, Nuria Dueñas, Jasper Verkroost, Marion Rolain, Marianne T. Haavind, Mia Quante, Rui Sousa, Lucybell Moreira, Maria I. Carvalho, PREVENTABLE Clinical Team, PREVENTABLE Cost-effectiveness Team, PREVENTABLE Consortium, Paula Soares, Svetlana Bajalica-Lagercrantz, Stefan Aretz, Judith Balmaña, Ana Azevedo, Hildegunn H. Vetti, Jean-Christophe Thery, Claude Houdayer, Janneke Schuurs-hoeijmakers, Joan Brunet, Carla Oliveira

OC2**ETV6::JAK2 fusion promotes central nervous system invasion in a pre-clinical model of B-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia**

Telma Costa, Telmo A. Catarino, Ivette Pacheco-Leyva, Nuno R. dos Santos

OC3**Macrophage-driven mechanisms of radiotherapy resistance in triple-negative breast cancer**

Ana Canha-Borges, Lisa Bouarroudj, Diogo Estêvão, Beatriz M. Sousa, Tânia Cruz, Joana Paredes, Joana Lencart, Carmen Jerónimo, Michele Mondini, Eric Deutsch, Flávia Castro, Maria J Oliveira

OC4

Preventive management of *CDH1* carriers improves survival and reduces healthcare costs: a European multicenter real-world study

Ricardo Amorim, Bárbara Peleteiro, Luzia Garrido, Laura Duran-Lozano, Amalia Nanciu, Adriana Costal, Iréne Stenfors, Diana Ferreira, Janneke Schuurs-Hoeijmakers, João Fonseca, Liliana Sousa, Marbelia Fernandes, Daniela Duarte, António Moreira, Nuria Dueñas, Patricia Faure, Marion Rolain, Birte B. Lundhaug, Marianne T. Haavind, Mia Quante, Jasper Verkroost, Lucybell Moreira, Maria I. Carvalho, PREVENTABLE Clinical Team, PREVENTABLE Cost-effectiveness Team, PREVENTABLE Consortium, Rui Sousa, Céu Mateus, Claude Houdayer, Jean-Christophe Théry, Hildegunn H. Vetti, Katja Verbeek, Svetlana Bajalica-Lagercrantz, Ana Azevedo, Joan Brunet, Stefan Aretz, Judith Balmaña, Sara B. Pereira, Carla Oliveira

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Barriers and enablers influencing clinical teams recommendations of RTRS care pathways: A qualitative study

Susana Mourão, Maiara Moreto, Ana Machado, Isabel Fernandes, Ana Maria Rodrigues, Bárbara Peleteiro, Joan Brunet, Judith Balmaña, Claude Houdayer, Jean-Christophe Thery, Janneke H.M. Schuurs-Hoeijmakers, Stefan Aretz, Amalia Nanciu, Charlotte Pahnke, Leonard Frach, Cathrine Bjorvatn, Liliana Sousa, Sara Pereira, Carla Oliveira, PREVENTABLE Clinical Team, PREVENTABLE Consortium, Marta M. Marques

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Healthcare cost of cancer surveillance vs. treatment in Peutz-Jeghers syndrome: Real-world evidence from the PREVENTABLE project

Amalia Nicole Nanciu, Ricardo Amorim, Mia Quante, Katrin van Beekum, Marion Rolain, Adriana Costal, Birte Blindheim Lundhaug, Laura Duran-Lozano, Janneke H.M. Schuurs-Hoeijmakers, Bárbara Peleteiro, Luzia Garrido, Silvana Lobo, António Moreira, Annette Erle, Liliana Sousa, Marbélia Fernandes, Núria Dueñas, PREVENTABLE Clinical Team, PREVENTABLE Cost-effectiveness Team, PREVENTABLE Consortium, Rui Sousa, Svetlana Bajalica-Lagercrantz, Ana Azevedo, Katja C.J. Verbeek, Judith Balmaña, Hildegunn Høberg Vetti, Claude Houdayer, Jean-Christophe Théry, Joan Brunet, Robert Hüneburg, Sara Pereira, Carla Oliveira, Stefan Aretz

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Marion Rolain, Ricardo Amorim, Patricia Faure, Adriana Costal, Alexander Sun Zhang, Laura Duran-Lozano, Bárbara Peleteiro, Pauline Rochefort, Valérie Bonadona, Isabelle Rochet, Nadège Corradini, Julie Boone, Elisa Piras-Ferencz, Coralie Rubeck, Solveig Menu-Hespel, Amalia Nicole Nanciu, Olivier Caron, Véronica Goldberg, Léa Guerrini-Rousseau, Birte Blindheim Lundhaug, Muriel Belotti, Marion Gauthier-Villars, Janneke H.M. Schuurs-Hoeijmakers, Marbélia Fernandes, Liliana Sousa, António Moreira, Núria Dueñas, Silvana Lobo, Marianne T. Haavind, Maud Branchaud, Nathalie Parodi, Stéphanie Baert-Desurmont, Edwige Kasper, Gaëlle Bougeard, Thomas Vermeulin, PREVENTABLE Clinical Team, PREVENTABLE Cost-Effectiveness Team, PREVENTABLE Consortium, Rui Sousa, Sara Pereira, Katja C.J. Verbeek, Hildegunn Høberg Vetti, Stefan Aretz, Ana Azevedo, Judith Balmaña, Svetlana Bajalica-Lagercrantz, Joan Brunet, Carla Oliveira, Jean-Christophe Thery, Claude Houdayer

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Alexandre Dias, Rita Barbosa-Matos, Rita Quental, Luís F. Maia, Carla Oliveira

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Rita Carvalho, Liliana Santos, Inês Conde, Ricardo Leitão, Célia Gomes, Ana Paula Silva, Fernando Schmitt, Carina Carvalho-Maia, João Lobo, Carmen Jerónimo, Joana Paredes, Ana Sofia Ribeiro

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Katja C.J. Verbeek, Ricardo Amorim, Nicoline Hoogerbrugge, Janet Vos, Birte Lundhaug, Núria Dueñas, Amalia N. Nanciu, Marion Rolain, Laura Duran-Lozano, Bárbara Peleteiro, Silvana Lobo, Marbelia Fernandes, António Moreira, Liliana Sousa, Sara Pereira, PREVENTABLE Clinical Team, PREVENTABLE Cost-effectiveness Team, PREVENTABLE Consortium, Svetlana Bajalica-Lagercrantz, Céu Mateus, Hildegunn Høberg Vetti, Joan Brunet, Stefan Aretz, Claude Houdayer, Jean-Christophe Théry, Judith Balmaña, Ana Azevedo, Rui Sousa, Carla Oliveira, Janneke H.M. Schuurs-Hoeijmakers

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Maiara Moreto, Maiara Moreto, Susana Mourão, Ana Machado, Isabel Fernandes, Ana Maria Rodrigues, Bárbara Peleteiro, Joan Brunet, Judith Balmaña, Claude Houdayer, Jean-Christophe Thery, Janneke H.M. Schuurs-Hoeijmakers, Stefan Aretz, Amalia Nauciu, Charlotte Pahnke, Leonard Frach, Cathrine Bjorvatn, Liliana Sousa, Sara Pereira, Carla Oliveira, PREVENTABLE Clinical Team, PREVENTABLE Consortium, Marta M. Marques

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Andrew Titman, Zillur Shabuz, Carolina Di Fabrizio, Ricardo Amorim, Bárbara Peleteiro, Luzia Garrido, Janneke Schuurs-Hoeijmakers, Liliana Sousa, Marbelia Fernandes, António Moreira, Lucybell Moreira, Maria I. Carvalho, PREVENTABLE Clinical Team, Rui Sousa, Claude Houdayer, Jean-Christophe Théry, Hildegunn H. Vetti, Svetlana Bajalica-Lagercrantz, Joan Brunet, Stefan Aretz, Ana Azevedo, Judith Balmaña, Sara B. Pereira, PREVENTABLE Consortium, Carla Oliveira, Judite Gonçalves, Céu Mateus

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Silvana Lobo, Alexandre Dias, Ana M Pedro, Marta Ferreira, André Pinto-Oliveira, Celina São José, Jennifer Herrera-Mullar, Chrystelle Colas, Robert Hüneburg, Jacob Nattermann, Lise Boussemart, Liselotte P van Hest, Leticia Moreira, Carolyn Horton, Dana Farengo Clark, Sigrid Tinschert, Lisa Golmard, Isabel Spier, Adrià López-Fernández, Daniela Oliveira, Magali Svrcek, Pierre Bourgoïn, Florence Coulet, Helene Delhomelle, Jeremy Davis, Birthe Zäncker, Conxi Lazaro, Joana Guerra, Maria L Almeida, Sergio Carrera, Ana Patiño, Paul Gundlach, Monika Laszkowska, Vivian E Strong, Manuel R Teixeira, Kasmintan A Schrader, Verena Steinke-Lange, Irene Gullo, Sérgio Sousa, Manuela Batista, Stefan Aretz, Judith Balmaña, Melyssa Aronson, Augusto P Antoniazzi, Edenir I Palmero, Paul Mansfield, Lizet E van der Kolk, Annemieke Cats, Jolanda M van Dieren, Sergi Castellvi-Bel, Bryson W Katona, Rachid Karam, Paulo S Pereira, Patrick R Benusiglio, Carla Oliveira

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Adriana Costal, Ricardo Amorim, Sara Isabel Pereira, Liliana Sousa, Núria Dueñas, Roser Lleuger-Pujol, Birte Lundhaug, Laura Duran-Lozano, Amalia Nanciu, Irene Stenfors, Bárbara Peleteiro, Katja C.J. Verbeek, Marion Rolain, Alex Teulé, Adrià López-Fernández, Paula Boaventura, Patricia Faure, Jean Christophe Thery, Marbélia Fernandes, António Moreira, PREVENTABLE Clinical team, PREVENTABLE Cost-effectiveness team, PREVENTABLE Consortium, Céu Mateus, Andrew Titman, Rui Sousa, Claude Houdayer, Janneke Schuurs-Hoeijmakers, Ana Azevedo, Svetlana Bajalica-Lagercrantz, Stefan Aretz, Judith Balmaña, Hildegunn H.Vetti, Carla Oliveira, Joan Brunet

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Luísa Pereira, Ricardo J. Pinto, Carla dos Santos, Ana C. Magalhães, Verónica Fernandes, António Pombinho, Dylan Ferreira, Lurdes Torres, Paulo Salamanca, Fernando Miguel, Pamela Borges, Carla Barbosa, Vitor Costa, Carlos Lopes, Margarida André, Adelaide Sousa, Pedro Sequeira, Cláudia Pereira, Paulo M. Costa, Lúcio Lara Santos

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OC1

From treatment to proactive prevention in Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes – Evidences from the PREVENTABLE multicentric cohort

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Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes (RTRS) are diseases with a prevalence of ≤ 5 per 10.000 people caused by heritable genetic variants increasing lifetime risk of developing multiple, early-onset and, in some conditions, very aggressive cancers (1, 2). Identification of actionable germline variants in RTRS patients at risk provides an opportunity for cancer prevention or early detection. This is accomplished by intensive surveillance programs and/or prophylactic surgeries according to consensus clinical guidelines. Although apparently obvious, the cost-benefit of proactive prevention in RTRS is currently missing and is the mission of the PREVENTABLE project (<https://preventable.eu/>) (3).

We developed an IT tool interface (PREVENT-IT) that systematically collects real-world clinical data and indexes country-specific healthcare costs/prices to clinical procedures/sub-procedures/DRGs. It considers risk of multiple cancers within and across each RTRS identified in ERN GENTURIS reference centers.

RTRS-specific matrices were built to map individual patient trajectories with associated clinical procedures in their care pathways for Birt-Hogg-Dubé (BHDS - FLCN), Familial Melanoma (FM - CDKN2A, CDK4), Hereditary Gastrointestinal Stromal Tumours (HGIST - SDHx and KIT), Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (HDGC - CDH1, CTNNA1), Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Carcinoma (HLRCC - FH), Li-Fraumeni (LFS - TP53), PTEN Hamartoma Tumour (PHTS - PTEN), and Peutz-Jeghers (PJS - STK11) syndromes. Data was collected from a total of 2596 patients, from which 1556 (59%) were RTRS carriers. The most frequent (33%) RTRS in the cohort was LFS with data collected from 505 carriers, followed by HDGC (16%) and PHTS (15%), with data collected from 246 and 234 carriers, respectively. The rarest RTRS in the cohort were HGIST (1%) and PJS (5.0%).

Across RTRS, 64 of carriers were identified before cancer development and entered active prevention pathways, ranging from 98% in HLRCC to 38% in LFS, reflecting widespread implementation of guideline-based care. In LFS, a disproportional fraction of carriers presented cancer at genetic diagnosis or initial risk assessment (62%). So far, survival was significantly improved for HDGC, LFS and HLRCC patients

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in prevention pathways compared with treatment. Across all RTRS, clinical outcomes improved when early cancer was detected during surveillance. From a financial perspective, although cumulative prevention costs were higher for HDGC and BHDS, treatment pathways across all RTRS consistently incurred substantially greater costs per patient, driven largely by a small number of high-cost interventions. On a per-case basis, prevention pathways had lower, more evenly distributed costs over time across all RTRS, despite syndrome-specific differences in preventive strategies. Overall, these findings support a shift from reactive treatment to proactive prevention in the management of RTRS.

- (1) Vos et al. *Fam Cancer* 2019, 18
- (2) Garutti et al. *Genes-Basel* 2023, 14
- (3) Pereira et al. 2025, doi:10.5281/zenodo.14893718

OC2

ETV6::JAK2 fusion promotes central nervous system invasion in a pre-clinical model of B-cell acute lymphoblastic leukemia

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Acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) is the most frequent pediatric malignancy and remains an important cause of mortality and morbidity in all ages. A subgroup of B-cell precursor ALL (BCP-ALL) patients with dismal prognosis carries specific genetic alterations, including *JAK2* fusions and *CDKN2A* deletions. Disease relapse in these patients is often associated with central nervous system (CNS) invasion.

Here, we hypothesized that *JAK2* fusions are a risk factor for the development of aggressive CNS-infiltrating BCP-ALL. To study the impact of constitutively active *JAK2* kinase signaling in CNS involvement by B-ALL, we generated mice expressing an ETV6::*JAK2* fusion in the lymphoid lineage, in a leukemia-prone genetic background (*Rag2* and *Cdkn2a* deficiency).

Indeed, although *Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} mice developed B-ALL with full penetrance, ETV6::*JAK2*;*Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} littermates developed B-ALL with earlier onset and with more frequent CNS invasion, as determined by occurrence of paraparesis/paraplegia of hind limbs. Immunohistochemical analyses of diseased ETV6::*JAK2*;*Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} and *Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} mice revealed leptomenigeal invasion by leukemic cells expressing the B220 and PAX5 B-cell markers and phosphorylated STAT5, a *JAK* kinase substrate. *In vitro* treatment of primary leukemic cells with AZD1480 (*JAK2* kinase inhibitor) significantly impaired the survival of ETV6::*JAK2*;*Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} but not *Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} leukemic cells. Moreover, treatment of wild-type mice transplanted with ETV6::*JAK2*;*Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} B-ALL with FDA-approved *JAK1*/*JAK2* inhibitor Ruxolitinib (100 mg/kg/daily) resulted in a significant reduction of circulating

B-ALL cells and decreased tumor burden in the spleen, in comparison to vehicle group. In parallel, to grasp the dynamics of CNS invasion by B-ALL, we infused CD45.2-expressing ETV6::JAK2;*Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} and *Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} cells in *Rag2*^{-/-};CD45.1⁺ recipients and quantified via flow cytometry analysis the presence of leukemic cells in the cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) at different timepoints. Mice injected with ETV6::JAK2-driven B-ALL presented earlier and significantly higher invasion of CSF by CD45.2⁺B220⁺ cells compared to those transplanted with *Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} leukemia, but similar tumor burden in the bone marrow. Moreover, transcriptomic analysis of leukemic cells from ETV6::JAK2;*Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} mice revealed upregulation of genes (*Selp/g* and *Ccr5*) and signaling pathways (unfolded protein response and cholesterol synthesis) related to CNS invasion in B-ALL, compared to *Rag2*^{-/-};*Cdkn2a*^{-/-} leukemia.

In conclusion, the ETV6::JAK2 fusion promotes leukemia survival, accelerates disease development, and confers increased neurotropism to leukemic cells.

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OC3

Macrophage-driven mechanisms of radiotherapy resistance in triple-negative breast cancer

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Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC), the most aggressive subtype, is associated with higher risk of relapse following radiotherapy (RT). To overcome this clinical challenge, focus must be paid to immune cells, in particular macrophages, highly recruited upon RT, and associated with tumor progression and recurrence.

Herein, we established and characterized 3D spheroids gathering TNBC cells (tumor spheroids, TS) or TNBC cells with human macrophages (tumor-immune spheroids, TiS). These were then submitted to five cumulative fractions of 2.67Gy or 5.2Gy, mimicking one week of TNBC patients treatment. Multiomic and in vivo studies were further performed to unveil the mechanisms underlying macrophage-mediated TNBC radioresistance.

Collected data indicates that RT selectively kills cancer cells while does not affect macrophage and cancer cells viability in TiS. Specifically, macrophages protected cancer cells from RT-induced cell death throughout time, promoting their proliferation and increasing CD47 and CD40 expression, which may favor immune escape. Notably, RT seems to potentiate different macrophage polarization signatures over time, ranging from an anti-tumor pro-inflammatory towards a more pro-tumor anti-inflammatory phenotype. RNASeq analysis identified CXCR2 as significantly increased in irradiated macrophages. Concordantly, Multiplex ELISA revealed increased secretion of IL8 (CXCR2 ligand), which may favor radioresistance, and that we demonstrated to correlate with worst prognosis on a TNBC

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patients cohort. Furthermore, in absence of macrophages, irradiated cancer cells upregulated pathways related to cell cycle arrest and DNA damage and exhibited an increase on lipid droplets and mitochondria deregulation. Contrarily, the most altered pathways on irradiated TiS were on sterol and cholesterol metabolic processes. These results highlight a novel radioresistance mechanism through which macrophages subvert and nourish the tumor microenvironment, modifying cancer cells lipid metabolism to escape RT-mediated cell death. In vivo experiments, using an orthotopic TNBC mouse model evidence that the intratumor administration of clodronate, a macrophage inhibitor, significantly repressed primary tumors growth. Moreover, the combination of clodronate and RT significantly improved the overall survival of the animals, further suggesting the pro-tumoral role of tumor-associated macrophages in TNBC.

These data confirm that macrophages potentiate TNBC radioresistance through different and novel mechanisms. Our current *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments aim at targeting lipid metabolism that will hopefully revert macrophage-mediated radioresistance, and sensitize cancer cells to death, improving RT response and patient prognosis.

OC4

Preventive management of *CDH1* carriers improves survival and reduces healthcare costs: a European multicenter real-world study

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Hereditary diffuse gastric cancer (HDGC) is a rare, but life-threatening condition, linked mainly to pathogenic variants in *CDH1* and increasing lifetime risk of diffuse gastric cancer (DGC) and lobular breast cancer (LBC). Clinical guidelines recommend prophylactic surgeries and/or intensive surveillance to decrease cancer risk. Real-world data on HDGC-related care pathways and healthcare costs across European Reference Centres are missing. We conducted a multinational retrospective cohort study including families carrying *CDH1* pathogenic variants, followed between 1998 and 2023 across eight expert centers within the European Reference Network on Genetic Tumour Risk Syndromes - ERN GENTURIS. Clinical events were harmonized through a centralized IT platform. Outcomes included timing of interventions, tumor stage, survival, healthcare utilization, and cumulative healthcare costs.

A total of 426 individuals were enrolled, including 246 *CDH1* carriers (median age 39.5 years; 59% female) with a median follow-up of 39 months. Sixty-one carriers (25%) developed cancer, corresponding to 64 tumor phenotypes (41 DGC and 23 LBC). While 32% of DGC and 9% of LBC were advanced (stage IV) cancers, 44% and 30%, respectively, were diagnosed at an early stage (stage I). Cancer-specific mortality occurred in 18 carriers, mainly from advanced DGC (89%). Prophylactic surgery was performed in 47% of carriers, comprising gastrectomy in 83% and mastectomy in 17% of these procedures. Two main clinical trajectories were identified after first risk-assessment: 161 carriers (65%) were cancer free and enrolled in preventive pathways, while 53 presented with cancer, 28% of which detected in stage IV. Proactive prevention eliminated the occurrence of advanced cancer, with only 5% of patients presenting with early-stage (I/II) DGC and/or LBC. In the treatment group, 44% of DGC were advanced (stage III-IV). Median time from risk assessment to surveillance was 3-5 months; to prophylactic gastrectomy was 7-8 months; and to risk-reducing mastectomy was 42 months. Median survival was 17 months for advanced DGC vs 245 months for advanced LBC.

Treatment arm was consistently more expensive than prevention: median cumulative costs, per patient, within 24 months were €13 107 [10 451-17 125] vs €1 275 [279- 3 888],

remaining higher at 24–60 months (€14 966 [9 153–24 126] vs €4 441 [1 870– 5 917]) and beyond 60 months (€19 759 [13 836–24 508] vs €6 198 [4 305–11 624]), respectively. Higher treatment cost was driven by hospitalizations, systemic therapy, and palliative care, with systemic treatments accounting for ~95% of the costs. Despite involving fewer patients, treatment showed a six-fold higher median per-patient cost.

These findings demonstrate that proactive prevention in *CDH1* carriers is associated with earlier detection, substantially improved survival, and markedly lower healthcare costs compared with therapeutic care after cancer onset.

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OC5

Barriers and enablers influencing clinical teams recommendations of RTRS care pathways: A qualitative study

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Background: Cancer prevention strategies exist for individuals with rare tumour risk syndromes (RTRS), but healthcare systems often prioritise treatment over prevention. PREVENTABLE, an EU-Horizon-funded project, aims to assess the clinical, social, and economic impact of preventive care pathways for families with RTRS. This study explored barriers and enablers to implementing and referring these pathways, as perceived by clinical teams.

Methods: Six focus groups were conducted with clinical teams experienced in managing different RTRS across Portugal, Spain, France, Germany, Netherlands, and Norway. Discussion topics were informed by literature, expert input, and quantitative survey findings. Semi-structured topic guides were based on the COM-B model that categorizes behavioural determinants into: i) physical and psychological Capability (energy, knowledge); ii) physical and social Opportunity (access to care, social support); iii) reflective and automatic Motivation (goals, emotions). Focus groups were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and analysed using MAXQDA. A two-stage thematic analysis was conducted. First, transcripts were deductively coded into Theoretical Domains Framework (TDF) and corresponding COM-B components. Second, inductive analysis was conducted to identify emergent themes and subthemes within each domain. Codes were classified as barriers (hindering the behaviour), enablers (supporting it), or mixed (exhibiting both barrier and enabler).

Results: A total of 781 references (segments of text that were coded) were identified. Behavioural factors were identified across five COM-B components and twelve TDF domains, with some domains more influential based on quote frequency. Among 35 clinical team members (77% female), psychological capability (n=338, 43.3%) and physical opportunity (n=209, 26.8%) were most frequently discussed, followed by reflective motivation (n=114, 14.6%), social opportunity (n=90, 11.5%), and automatic motivation (n=30, 3.8%). Main perceived barriers included lack of knowledge (n=15), communication challenges (n=15), and economic/financial costs to services (n=16). Care organisation was reported both as a barrier (n=16) and having mixed influence (n=18). Patient context (n=17) and tailoring explanations to patient preferences (n=16)

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often function as both barriers and enablers. Key perceived enablers included interprofessional relationships (n=23), patient-clinician relationships (n=23), and implementation intentions (n=14).

Conclusion: These findings provide novel insights into behavioural factors influencing the implementation of preventive care pathways for RTRS and highlight the need to strengthen clinical knowledge and communication skills, as well as organisational structures and professional relationships, to support preventive care. Critical analysis of these findings is essential to produce communication guidelines towards improvement of RTRS patients' management.

OC6

Healthcare cost of cancer surveillance vs. treatment in Peutz–Jeghers syndrome: Real-world evidence from the PREVENTABLE project

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Peutz–Jeghers syndrome (PJS) is a rare autosomal dominant tumour risk syndrome, caused by pathogenic germline variants in *STK11* and associated with a high lifetime risk of a broad spectrum of early-onset malignancies including breast, pancreas, bowel, and gastric cancer. Current guidelines recommend intensive lifelong surveillance, yet the costs of preventive care vs. symptomatic cancer management remain unexplored. Within the PREVENTABLE project, we have mapped the cumulative costs of prevention-based and symptom-driven care trajectories in PJS based on real-world data.

In collaboration with nine ERN GENTURIS centers across Europe, a multinational retrospective cohort study was conducted. Syndrome-specific care pathways across six modules (genetic diagnosis, risk assessment, surveillance, treatment of malignancies, follow-up) were mapped and validated by retrospective data. Costs for medical procedures were estimated using German diagnosis-related groups and public reimbursement rates. The prevention pathway was allocated to patients without a malignancy at genetic diagnosis, and the treatment pathway to patients with cancer at admission or at first risk assessment after genetic diagnosis.

In total, 127 individuals were registered including 82 *STK11* variant carriers (55 index patients, 27 via predictive testing) and 45 non-carriers. On average, 1.3 relatives per index case underwent predictive testing. Among *STK11* carriers, 70 individuals (85%) entered the prevention pathway and 12 individuals (15%) the treatment pathway. Median follow-up time was 180 months (IQR 89-283; range 6-667) in the prevention group and 136 months (IQR 65-208; range 18-446) in the treatment group.

Across the cohort, 12 malignancies were detected prior to or at time of genetic testing and three during surveillance: breast cancer (n=6), pancreatic cancer (n=2), small bowel cancer (n=2), one metachronous small bowel and gastric cancer, and four additional PJS-associated malignancies.

Testing of non-carriers allowed discharge from surveillance and generated total healthcare costs of €29,174 (€600 per individual). Among *STK11* variant carriers, cumulative healthcare costs amounted to €1,281,618 in the prevention pathway (median €15k per patient; IQR €8k–€26k) and

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€298,033 in the treatment pathway (median €23k per patient; IQR €13k-€31k). Mean per-patient cost breakdown by category showed that the majority of expenses in the prevention pathway were attributable to surveillance procedures (44%) and intussusception treatment (35%) while treatment pathway costs were primarily driven by oncological treatments (55%).

When normalized for follow-up duration, median healthcare costs per patient per month were €101 (IQR €59-€181) in the prevention and €183 (IQR €142-€314) in the treatment pathway, indicating that treatment was approximately 81% more expensive per month. The data show that timely genetic cascade testing followed by preventive measures result in substantial cost savings.

OC7

Clinical Outcomes and Cost-effectiveness of Preventive Surveillance versus Treatment in Li-Fraumeni Syndrome: Results from the European PREVENTABLE Project

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Li-Fraumeni syndrome (LFS), caused by TP53 pathogenic variants, is one of the most severe hereditary cancer predisposition syndromes, characterized by very early cancer onset, broad tumor spectrum, and a high lifetime risk of multiple cancers. At the European level, no large-scale health economics study has compared LFS proactive cancer preventive management including intensive multiorgan surveillance and early cancer detection, with treatment approaches initiated after the first tumor occurs in individuals at high cancer risk. To address this gap, and within the European PREVENTABLE project, we evaluated healthcare pathways and cumulative costs of proactive prevention versus treatment in LFS European families.

We retrospectively collected clinical data from 866 individuals from seven European countries, from nine ERN GENTURIS centers (including four centers in the French LFS network), including 505 TP53 gene carriers (27% of whom were children) and 361 non-carrier family members. Based on multidisciplinary expertise, we developed a structured LFS care matrix, mapping patient clinical trajectories and clinical procedures across diagnosis, risk reduction strategies, surveillance, treatments, and follow-up. Costs were estimated using standardized French hospital tariffs, and data were collected via a GDPR-compliant digital tool interface developed by the PREVENTABLE consortium.

From 866 individuals, 155 were TP53 carriers without a prior cancer diagnosis at the time of genetic testing were included in the preventive arm. During follow-up (median 75 months; range 6-267), 20 individuals developed one or more cancers. The mean prevention cost per patient was €6,046.8 (range €451-€71,854.76). Among the 273 patients with a history of cancer prior to genetic testing, 109 had early-stage disease and 164 had advanced-stage disease (median follow-up 83 months; range 2-468). The mean treatment cost per patient was €53,906 (range €385.50-€440,760.93). Overall cumulative costs were €937,258 for prevention and €15,103,188 for treatment, including €5,245,915 for early-stage cancers and €9,857,273 for advanced-stage cancers. Preventive mastectomy was performed in 24% of women in either prevention or treatment groups.

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This first European cumulative cost analysis demonstrates that treatment costs for LFS far exceed prevention costs, providing strong economic evidence in favor of early genetic diagnosis and preventive surveillance. These findings support public health decision-making and the harmonization of care pathways within the framework of precision medicine in Europe.

OC8

IARC dataset curation reveals new genotype-phenotype associations in Heritable TP53-Related Cancers

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Background: Heritable *TP53*-related cancer (h*TP53rc*) syndrome is an autosomal dominant syndrome caused by *TP53* germline variants that significantly increase the lifetime-risk of developing various cancers, as early as infancy. Currently, clinical guidelines disregard specific *TP53* genotype-phenotype associations to prioritize organs for surveillance. This study aims to provide the most comprehensive genotype-phenotype analysis to date, integrating clinical, demographic and molecular features to improve surveillance guidelines for *TP53*-carriers.

Patients and methods: We curated and analyzed the germline variant dataset of the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) *TP53* database R20 focusing on four aspects: quality control, manual variant classification/reclassification, manual classification/reclassification of predicted impact at protein level, dominant-negative effect (DNE) and Loss-of-Function (LOF), and standardization of phenotypes. Analyses were carried out considering occurrence of multiple cancers or the first cancer only, in *TP53* carriers or relatives with unknown carrier status and developing cancer <50 years. Associations were evaluated using non-parametric tests, χ^2 /Fisher tests, correlation analyses with multiple-testing correction, and age and sex adjusted logistic regression models.

Results: The curated dataset comprised 2736 phenotypes occurring in 2072 individuals from 913 families carrying 202 pathogenic/likely pathogenic *TP53* variants, 65% females. Phenotypes were standardized into 24 cancers in 19 organs.

From 2072 patients, 34% developed their first cancer between 0–17 years, while 14.5% were diagnosed after 50 years. From 202 TP53 variants, 55.4% were classified as DNE_LOF, 13.7% notDNE_LOF, and 30.9% otherDNE_LOF. We found that breast cancer was associated with variants in codon-133 (OR=3.5, $p=0.0008$), and CNS cancers, leukemias, and soft-tissue sarcomas with variants c.742C>T (OR=2.1, $p=0.003$), c.916C>T (OR=4.6, $p=0.0016$), and c.824G>A (OR=10, $p<0.0001$), respectively. Additionally, c.455C>T and c.1010G>A variants were associated with the development of a first cancer in adrenal gland at pediatric age, and c.824G>A variant with first cancers in soft-tissues during adulthood. Finally, variants in exon-8 were associated with sarcoma development (OR=1.9, $p<0.0001$), variants c.1010G>A, c.455C>T, c.659A>G, c.743G>A, and c.844C>T were associated with particularly early onset (≤ 18 years), and DNE_LOF variants were associated to the developing of multiple cancers (OR=1.5, $p=0.0190$).

Conclusion: Our study extends and reveals novel genotype-phenotype associations within hTP53rc patients, widening the spectrum of non-core cancers (leukemias) in TP53 carriers and may help prioritize, adrenal-gland, breast, soft-tissues and CNS for intensive surveillance in at-risk individuals carrying specific TP53 variants.

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OC9

Deciphering the impact of cancer cell's secretome and its derived peptide VGF on breast cancer brain metastasis

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Brain metastases represent one of the most serious clinical challenges in breast cancer progression due to their association with reduced survival and limited effective therapies. In this study, we investigated the impact of the secretome from brain organotropic breast cancer cells on the establishment of the brain pre-metastatic niche. Our findings revealed that the secretome of these cells induces blood-brain barrier disruption and microglial activation in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models.

Proteomic analysis of the secretome identified six dysregulated peptides, including the nerve growth factor-inducible protein VGF. Notably, we demonstrated that VGF compromises BBB integrity and alters microglial function

in vitro and *in vivo*, and that it also promotes cancer cell colonization within the brain microenvironment.

We further evaluated VGF expression in a cohort of human breast tumors and observed its presence in both cancer cells and adjacent stromal tissue. Importantly, VGF-positive tumors were significantly associated with HER2 overexpression, triple-negative molecular subtype, and poorer prognosis. Additional validation in an independent cohort of primary tumors from metastatic breast cancer cases, including paired metastases, revealed a significant association between VGF expression and propensity for brain metastasis, with a marked impact on patient prognosis.

In conclusion, our study highlights the role of the secretome of brain organotropic breast cancer cells in promoting the formation of the brain pre-metastatic niche. We identified a distinct secretome signature, pinpointing VGF as a critical mediator of early brain microenvironment remodeling and metastatic colonization. Moreover, VGF expression emerges as a prognostic marker for brain metastasis in breast cancer patients, supporting its potential as a therapeutic target to control brain metastatic disease progression.

OC10

Costs of cancer prevention versus cancer treatment in PTEN Hamartoma Tumor Syndrome: EU PREVENTABLE project

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PTEN Hamartoma Tumor Syndrome (PHTS), caused by germline pathogenic variants in PTEN, entails a very high hereditary lifetime risk of up to 76% for breast cancer, and up to 22% for endometrial and thyroid cancer. While genetic testing and cancer prevention by surveillance for these cancers are recommended by EU guidelines, the cumulative healthcare costs remain unexplored. This study evaluated the clinical outcomes and healthcare costs of prevention versus treatment in European PHTS patients.

Within the framework of the Horizon Europe PREVENTABLE project, a matrix of clinical patient trajectories was constructed across six modules: genetic diagnosis, risk-assessment, surveillance, treatment of early- and advanced stage cancer, and follow-up. Costs for each clinical procedure were estimated using diagnosis-related groups and public reimbursement rates. An IT tool was developed for systematic registration of patient data from seven European centers. The prevention group included patients without cancer prior to genetic testing, and the treatment group included patients with cancer prior to genetic testing or detected at first risk-assessment.

Among 234 PHTS patients, 140 (60%) were female. Fourteen female patients received a risk-reducing mastectomy. Ten (4%) PHTS patients died at a median age of 46 years (IQR: 34-53). Overall survival analyses showed no significant difference between the prevention and treatment group. Nineteen patients had insufficient clinical data for stratification.

The prevention group consisted of 152 patients who were cancer-free prior to genetic testing and received surveillance. During surveillance, ten patients were diagnosed with early stage cancer and one patient with early stage and advanced stage cancer. In this prevention group, the median costs were in total €10,510 (IQR: €5,420-€20,606) per patient and €118 (IQR: €57-€296) per patient per month. The majority of the costs were related to medical consultations (47%) and exams and tests (20%).

Among 63 patients with cancer prior to genetic testing, 56 patients received surveillance. In this treatment group, the median costs were in total €56,604 (IQR: €33,773-€97,830) per patient and €386 (IQR: €280-€890) per patient per month. The treatment group had comprehensive cancer

treatment and hospitalizations, reflected in the majority of the costs that were related to treatments (43%) and hospitalizations (30%).

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Median follow-up time was longer in the treatment group (131 months) than in the prevention group (102 months). The median costs per patient per month were 70% lower in the prevention group (€118 (IQR: €57-€296)) as compared to the treatment group (€386 (IQR: €280-€890)). This study shows the clinical outcomes and median costs per month per patient in the prevention and treatment group in a European PHTS patient cohort. These data are essential for optimal allocation of healthcare resources and ensuring sustainable care delivery.

OC11

Liquid Biopsy-Based MSI Detection in Lynch Syndrome: Platform Comparison and Diagnostic Performance

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Background: Lynch syndrome (LS) is an inherited cancer predisposition characterized by microsatellite instability (MSI) in (pre)cancerous lesions, particularly in colorectal cancer (CRC). Endoscopic surveillance reduces CRC incidence but may miss interval cancers and is burdensome for patients. We developed a multiplex digital PCR (dPCR) assay capable of detecting mutant allele frequencies (MAF) as low as 0.01% in liquid biopsies, enabling minimally invasive MSI detection.

Methods: The prospective BioLynch study enrolled asymptomatic LS carriers for baseline colonoscopy, followed by two annual rounds, and quarterly blood draws. If deemed necessary, gastroscopy was also offered. Plasma MSI was assessed using five microsatellites (BAT26, BAT25, NR24, NR21, Mono27), combining their MAF into a blood MSI (bMSI) score. We compared two dPCR platforms: QuantStudio 3D (QS3D) and Absolute Q (AbsQ). Study endpoints included (i) concordance between platforms for bMSI measurement, and (ii) diagnostic performance of each platform for detecting endoscopically confirmed (pre)cancerous lesions.

Results: At baseline, 109 participants were enrolled, 21% had mutations in *MLH1*, 47% in *MSH2* and 32% in *MSH6/PMS2*. Lesions were detected in 14 patients (13 by colonoscopy and 1 by gastroscopy): mostly female (57% vs. 43%, $p=0.15$)

with a median age of 53 (range: 20-81 years). Colorectal lesions included 9 low-grade, 3 high-grade dysplasia, and 1 adenocarcinoma. Analysis were restricted to the 105 participants with no assay failures in both platforms. AbsQ yielded higher MAF values than QS3D across all markers, with a mean bMSI difference of 0.002 favoring AbsQ. Concordance correlation coefficient between platforms was 0.50 (95%CI: 0.36-0.62) for bMSI, ranging from 0.24 (BAT25) to 0.46 (NR24) for single assays. Despite Bland-Altman analysis showed an over estimate tendency of AbsQ with respect to QS3D for bMSI, Mono27 and NR24, the majority of the samples fall within the Limits of Agreement. In logistic models predicting colonoscopy outcome (lesion vs. no lesion), bMSI showed an AUC of 0.78 (95%CI: 0.63-0.94) for QS3D and 0.81 (95%CI: 0.67-0.95) for AbsQ.

Conclusions: Liquid biopsy-based MSI detection reliably identifies (pre)cancerous lesions in LS patients. Both QS3D and AbsQ platforms showed comparable diagnostic performance, with AbsQ offering slightly higher performance. These findings support further development of bMSI testing to implement colonoscopic surveillance in LS.

OC12

Barriers and enablers influencing patients uptake of RTRS care pathways: A qualitative study

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Background: Rare Tumor Risk Syndromes (RTRS) are genetic diseases with up to a 100% cancer risk. Surveillance and risk-reduction strategies can improve survival rates, but most healthcare systems focus on treating clinically manifested cancers. PREVENTABLE, an EU-Horizon-funded project, evaluates the clinical, social, and economic impact of implementing preventive care pathways for families affected by RTRS (including Birt-Hogg-Dubé, Familial Malignant Melanoma, Gastrointestinal Stromal Tumors, Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer, Hereditary Leiomyomatosis, Li-Fraumeni, Peutz-Jeghers, PTEN Hamartoma Tumor, and Renal Cell Carcinomas). This study aimed to identify barriers and enablers influencing patients' uptake of RTRS care pathways.

Methods: Six focus groups were conducted with RTRS patients in six countries (Portugal, Spain, France, Germany, the Netherlands, and Norway). Semi-structured topic guides were informed by prior survey results and based on the Capability-Opportunity-Motivation-Behaviour (COM-B) model. This model categorizes behavioural factors into physical and psychological capability (energy, knowledge), physical and social opportunity (access to care, social support), and reflective and automatic motivation (goals, emotions). Focus groups were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and analysed in MAXQDA using a two-stage thematic analysis guided by COM-B and the Theoretical Domains Framework (TDF). First, transcripts were deductively coded into TDF domains and corresponding COM-B components. Second, inductive analysis was conducted to identify emergent themes and subthemes within each domain. Codes were categorised as barriers, enablers, or mixed.

Results: Thirty-six patients participated (50% female). The most frequently coded domain was psychological capability (n=310; 36.5%), followed by reflective motivation (n=188; 22.1%), physical opportunity (n=171; 20.1%), social opportunity (n=102; 12%), and automatic motivation (n=79; 9.3%). Key barriers included challenges attending appointments (n=20), long waiting times (n=20), and care organisation (n=20). Enablers included a good relationship with clinical teams (n=20) and strong social support (n=18). Decision-making about care (n=16) and fear and initial shock (n=14) had mixed

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influence. Psychological capability was the most cited domain in all countries except France, where reflective motivation predominated. Automatic motivation was least cited overall, except in France and Spain, where social opportunity was least reported. Physical opportunity emerged as the second most cited domain in four countries, except in Portugal and Spain.

Conclusions. Uptake of preventive care pathways for RTRS is shaped by interacting capability, opportunity, and motivation factors. Improving knowledge, communication, care organisation, and clinical relationships supports patient-centred prevention. Country differences highlight the need for context-sensitive policies.

OC13

Real-world data to evaluate care pathways and costs in hereditary leiomyomatosis and renal cell cancer syndrome: PREVENTABLE study

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Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and renal cell cancer (HLRCC) is a rare tumor-risk syndrome caused by heterozygous germline pathogenic variants in *FH* gene, which encodes fumarate hydratase, a Krebs cycle enzyme. Pathogenic variants in this gene predispose for aggressive papillary type 2 renal cancer, as well as cutaneous and uterine leiomyomas. Our aim is to describe real-world clinical care pathways, survival outcomes, and calculate the healthcare costs of clinical management of *FH* carriers.

Eight clinical trajectories were defined, three related to prevention and five related to treatment. Clinical trajectories

include genetic testing, risk-reduction, surveillance, therapeutic protocol and follow-up. All procedures across these pathways were listed and assigned a cost using data from hospital databases, diagnosis-related group (DRG), and Catalan Health Institute (ICS) fees. An interface of the PREVENT-IT tool was developed to register clinical data and costs for each patient.

Data from 231 individuals from FH HLRCC families were collected across five ERN-GENTURIS centers. Of these, 122 (53%) carried a FH pathogenic variant and 109 (47%) did not. Of the 231 individuals, 51 were probands tested through multigene panel analysis based on clinical eligibility criteria, and 180 were relatives who underwent variant predictive testing, of whom 71 (39%) were positive. On average, 3.5 relatives per proband were tested.

Among 114 carriers eligible for surveillance, 58 were lost to follow-up after the first risk assessment and 54 underwent surveillance protocols (median follow-up 19 months, IQR 3-44). Two patients were diagnosed with asymptomatic early-stage renal cancer at first risk assessment, and one individual (1%) was diagnosed with early-stage renal cancer 34 months after genetic testing. Among patients diagnosed with cancer before genetic testing (n=8), five presented with advanced-stage cancer.

Average cost for the five treatment pathways of care was 43312€ and for the three prevention pathways was 972€. Non-carriers' average cost was 416€ per person.

Advanced-stage renal cancer is more frequent in carriers diagnosed before genetic testing. Genetic and cascade testing enables early-stage diagnosis of renal cancer and identification of non-carriers who can be spared of unnecessary imaging, resulting in substantial cost savings.

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OC14

Pancreatic enhancer deletion drives acinar cell plasticity and neoplastic transformation through chromatin remodeling

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Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) is among the deadliest human cancers. Although hereditary predisposition is estimated in approximately 10% of cases, most lack an identified germline cause. *PTF1A* is a master regulator of pancreatic identity and functions as a tumor suppressor. Downregulation of *PTF1A* in acinar cells lowers the barrier to lineage reprogramming and oncogenic transformation. While coding mutations are rare, regulatory variants in *PTF1A* enhancers represent an underexplored hereditary risk factor. In this work, we use zebrafish to model how germline enhancer loss at the *ptf1a* locus destabilizes lineage programs, resulting in a cancer-permissive state.

We identified z3'-DpE, a distal enhancer of *ptf1a*, active in multipotent pancreatic progenitors (MPCs) and differentiated acinar cells. Deletion of z3'-DpE reduces *ptf1a* expression in MPCs, leading to depletion of the progenitor pool, altered morphogenesis, and premature exocrine differentiation. Transcriptomic analysis revealed broad repression of proliferation- and morphogenesis-related genes, including Notch pathway components essential for progenitor maintenance. After differentiation, z3'-DpE loss produces a graded reduction of acinar tissue with expansion of ductal and endocrine compartments and disrupted organ architecture.

In adults, micro-CT imaging revealed fragmented pancreatic architecture dominated by duct-like structures, while flow cytometry confirmed a 0.32-fold reduction in acinar cells alongside a 3.98-fold increase in β -cells. Chromatin accessibility profiling (ATAC-seq) of purified acinar cells revealed widespread remodeling, with reduced accessibility at loci linked to acinar and developmental programs and increased accessibility at sites associated with inflammation, epithelial-mesenchymal transition, and enrichment for oncogenic transcription factor motifs, such as AP-1, ETS1, and FLI1. Cross-species comparison revealed a significant overlap between genes with increased accessibility in z3'-DpE-/- acinar cells and upregulated genes in Nr5a2+/- mouse pancreas, a mouse PDAC-predisposition model. Histopathology of adult mutants confirmed loss of compact acinar tissue, expansion of disorganized duct-like structures, mucin-producing lesions resembling early neoplasia, and duct-like outgrowths extending into adjacent liver parenchyma.

Thus, z3'-DpE safeguards acinar identity by sustaining a chromatin landscape that restricts fate instability and oncogenic plasticity. Together, these data identify z3'-DpE as a dual-phase safeguard that couples progenitor expansion to long-term acinar lineage stabilization, limiting pathological plasticity and early neoplastic traits. Although not strictly conserved in mammals at the sequence level, we propose that late-acting *PTF1A* regulatory elements in humans may represent underexplored hereditary pancreatic cancer susceptibility loci.

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OC15

Cost-effectiveness modelling in rare tumour risk syndromes (RTRS) - results and challenges

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Introduction: Hereditary cancer syndromes account for approximately 10% of all cancers. Many of these conditions, classified as rare tumour risk syndromes (RTRS), lack comprehensive data on their natural history, lifetime cancer risk, and the long-term impact of surveillance strategies. Cost-effectiveness analyses are crucial but present many challenges considering the current evidence on RTRS to inform disease progression models and support future economic evaluations.

Objective: The primary objective of the work is to present the preliminary results of the cost-effectiveness models of

preventative treatments for the management of patients identified as carriers of disease-causing genetic variants with hereditary diffuse gastric cancer syndrome (HDGC), Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Carcinoma (HLRCC), and Birt-Hogg-Dubé Syndrome (BHDS).

Methods: Through the EU-funded PREVENTABLE project (www.preventable.eu), we retrospectively analysed data for HDGC (246 CDH1 carriers), HLRCC (122 carriers) and BHD (274 carriers) across Portugal, Spain, France, Norway, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany (between years 2000 and 2023) to populate the models with parameters regarding resource use and respective costs, when possible.

A series of general functions have been developed in R to allow models from this general class of models to build with arbitrary flexibility. All transition intensities between states can be time dependent with respect to either age or time since entry into the state, or both. Models were run for suitable strategies in each RTRS and for men and women strategies when deemed necessary, under the base-case parameter estimates. Subsequently, each set of parameters was set to the upper and lower values of their plausible range to provide one-way sensitivity analyses. Finally, a full set of parameters was repeatedly drawn from the approximate estimated posterior distribution, to perform probabilistic sensitivity analysis (PSA).

Results: Estimated incremental QALYs are highly sensitive to the assumed utility weights for preventative strategies and relative risk of having cancer. The impact of changes to other parameter values is less marked. In HLRCC, surveillance has an incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) between €14,340/QALY for men and €38,129/QALY for women. For HDGC and BHD, ICERs implied much higher willingness to pay.

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OC16

Familial Melanoma: an Evaluation of clinical outcome and healthcare costs in the EU PREVENTABLE project

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Familial melanoma (FM) is caused by germline pathogenic variants in *CDKN2A* or *CDK4*. In addition to a high lifetime risk of cutaneous melanoma, individuals carrying these variants have increased risk of pancreatic cancer. FM care pathways include genetic counselling and testing, life-long skin surveillance including excision of suspicious lesions, research-based pancreas surveillance and treatment of melanoma and pancreatic cancer at different stages. Within the frame of the Horizon Europe Preventable project, we aimed to investigate the clinical outcome and healthcare costs for individuals with FM.

In this retrospective study, individuals belonging to families with an identified *CDKN2A/CDK4* pathogenic variant from six ERN GENTURIS reference centers were included. Their clinical trajectories were mapped in detail and registered in a specialized IT tool, developed for the PREVENTABLE project, where the costs of all clinical procedures had been standardized by using Norwegian diagnosis-related groups (DRGs) and public reimbursement rates.

A total of 286 individuals were identified, 171 carriers of pathogenic *CDKN2A* (n=144) or *CDK4* (n=27) variants and 115 non-carriers. Among the carriers, 92 were cancer-free at genetic diagnosis (prevention arm), while 79 were affected by melanoma or pancreatic cancer at the time of genetic diagnosis (treatment arm). Median duration of follow-up was 53 months (range: 1-232 months) in the prevention arm, and 130 months (range: 2-586 months) in the treatment arm.

Fifty-nine carriers in the prevention arm entered regular skin surveillance, of whom 14 developed early-stage melanoma, and one developed advanced melanoma. One carrier was diagnosed with resectable pancreatic cancer. Among patients with cancer prior to genetic testing (treatment arm), 59 had early melanoma at the time of genetic diagnosis, five had advanced melanoma, three had pancreatic cancer, and one had both melanoma and pancreatic cancer. Within this group, three patients developed advanced melanoma and one developed pancreatic cancer during the follow-up period.

Across all carriers in the cohort (n=171), a total of 154 cases of early melanoma (stage 0-IIA) and 12 cases of advanced melanoma (stage >IIA) were recorded. Forty-two individuals developed multiple melanomas, ranging from 2 to 10 melanomas.

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Median total cost of skin-related care per patient was €1 509 in the prevention arm (IQR: €447-4 494) compared to €6 615 per patient in the treatment arm (IQR: €3 792-10 590) ($p < 0.001$). For pancreas, the median total cost per patient was €931 in the prevention arm (IQR: €286-3 211) and €1 441 in the treatment arm (IQR: €780-3 921) ($p = 0.073$).

Our study shows that skin surveillance of individuals with FM leads to detection of melanomas at an early stage and initial analyses indicate that identifying these individuals before they manifest with cancer costs less than delaying treatment until the cancer manifests clinically.

OC17

Atypical Cases of POT1 Tumor Predisposition Syndrome - Multicentric Report

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Background: *POT1* Tumor Predisposition Syndrome (POT1-TPD) is an autosomal dominant condition associated with an increased risk for various malignancies, including cutaneous melanoma, sarcomas, chronic lymphocytic leukemia, and gliomas. Despite its clinical relevance, reported cases remain limited, and the syndrome displays considerable phenotypic variability across affected families.

Methods: Retrospective review of clinical and genetic data from families with POT1-TPD followed at two medical centers in northern Portugal.

Results: We report two families with a pathogenic *POT1* variant, both identified as incidental findings. Family 1: The index case was diagnosed with breast cancer and a pathogenic nonsense *POT1* variant was an incidental finding during genetic investigation. Family history included two deceased ancestors with melanoma. A cascade screening identified ten relatives with the variant; only one of these has developed a known POT1-associated malignancy (melanoma). Family 2: The index case

was a child investigated for congenital malformations, during which a chromosome 7 deletion (including *POT1* gene) was identified. The mother was also confirmed to carry the variant and started on surveillance; there was no personal or family history of melanoma or other *POT1*-associated tumors. Family testing is ongoing.

Conclusions: These two families illustrate atypical presentations of POT1-TPD, reinforcing the need for broader clinical awareness of this disease. Given its rarity and variability, further studies are needed to better characterize the full range of associated tumors, as well as the syndrome's penetrance, prevalence, natural history and optimal surveillance strategies. Considering the long-term risks and the implications for patient monitoring, the authors question the appropriateness of including the *POT1* gene in the list of reportable incidental findings, warranting further discussion on its relevance in clinical practice.

OC18

Thymopoiesis and thymic structural alterations after T-cell lymphoblastic lymphoma regression

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T-cell lymphoblastic lymphoma (T-LBL) is an aggressive immature T-cell malignancy that predominantly arises in the thymus, forming large thymic lymphomas with limited bone marrow involvement. Nonetheless, malignant cells can also infiltrate other organs, such as the spleen and lymph nodes. Despite advances in therapy and improved survival, particularly in pediatric patients, long-term immune dysfunction in disease survivors remains a matter of significant concern. The thymus, essential for T-cell maturation, may suffer lasting damage from the expansion of malignant T cells or chemotherapy, compromising immune recovery and the establishment of a self-tolerant T-cell repertoire. Previous studies from our group demonstrated that leukemic T-cell expansion disrupts thymic structure, cellular composition, and function. We hypothesized that T-LBL malignant cells durably damage the thymus, leading to sustained immune dysregulation. With this project, we aim to examine the impact of malignant T cells on thymopoiesis, including thymocyte numbers, subset distribution, and overall T-cell development. Moreover, we also seek to assess how T-LBL regression influences the thymic microenvironment, focusing on structural integrity.

Using ETV6::JAK2 fusion transgenic mice, which spontaneously develop fatal thymic lymphoblastic lymphomas with full penetrance, we conditionally expressed the diphtheria toxin (DT) receptor in leukemic T cells, enabling selective ablation upon DT administration. DTR-expressing ETV6::JAK2 mice presenting spontaneous signs of disease (dyspnea), and with confirmed thymic lymphoma by magnetic resonance

imaging (MRI), were treated with DT. Treated mice regained a healthy physical condition, which persisted for at least 14 days after treatment cessation. Through flow cytometry detection of typical T-cell development surface marker proteins (e.g. CD4, CD8, CD25, CD44 and TCR β), we found that two weeks after treatment cessation, the minimum time for thymic repopulation, the thymus did not fully regain its normal thymocyte cell numbers and population subsets. Furthermore, immunofluorescence and stromal profiling will examine the restoration of thymic architecture and key microenvironmental populations, including thymic epithelial cells (TECs), fibroblasts, dendritic cells, and macrophages. To identify deeper molecular alterations, enriched stromal subsets will be analyzed by single-cell RNA sequencing.

Our data indicates that 14 days post-remission, thymopoiesis remains disrupted, suggesting impaired T-cell production. These findings support our hypothesis that T-LBL-induced thymic remodeling leads to durable disruptions in thymopoiesis, potentially contributing to long-term immune defects observed in survivors. Together, our findings will define how leukemic infiltration disrupts the thymus and whether these changes affect immune reconstitution.

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OC19

Cost-effectiveness model care pathways of Rare Tumour Risk Syndrome - the case of Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer

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Introduction: Hereditary cancer syndromes account for approximately 10% of all cancers. Many of these conditions, classified as rare tumour risk syndromes (RTRS), lack comprehensive data on their natural history, lifetime cancer risk, and the long-term impact of surveillance strategies. Cost-effectiveness analyses are crucial but present many challenges considering the current evidence on RTRS to inform disease

progression models and support future economic evaluations.

Objective: The primary objective of the work is to assess the cost-effectiveness of preventative treatments for the management of patients with hereditary diffuse gastric cancer syndrome (HDGC), identified as carriers of disease-causing genetic variants in the CDH1 gene.

Methods: Through the EU-funded PREVENTABLE project (www.preventable.eu), we retrospectively analysed data from 246 CDH1 carriers (101 men, 145 women) across Portugal, Spain, France, Norway, Sweden, the Netherlands, and Germany (between 2000 and 2023) to populate the model with parameters regarding resource use and respective costs, when possible.

A series of general functions have been developed in R to allow models from this general class of models to build with arbitrary flexibility. All transition intensities between states can be time dependent with respect to either age or time since entry into the state, or both. The model was run for each of the four strategies for men and each of the twelve strategies for women (i.e. combinations of either prophylactic total gastrectomy (PTG), pT1a surveillance, pT1b surveillance or nothing for gastric cancer and either mastectomy, surveillance or nothing for breast cancer), under the base-case parameter estimates. Subsequently, each set of parameters was set to the upper and lower values of their plausible range to provide one-way sensitivity analyses. Finally, a full set of parameters was repeatedly drawn from the approximate estimated posterior distribution, to perform probabilistic sensitivity analysis (PSA).

Results: Genetic diagnosis costs were estimated at €354.9 (95% CI: 308, 407) amongst confirmed carriers (n=246). For endoscopic surveillance, the average cost per visit (including the associated consultation) was €515.6 (95% CI: 438, 603), and this was assumed to be the resulting annual cost (under an assumption of annual surveillance). For breast cancer surveillance, the mean annual cost was estimated as €219.3 (95% CI: 182, 262). The estimated incremental QALY is highly sensitive to the assumed utility weight corresponding to PTG, which itself is highly uncertain. The impact of changes to other parameter values is less marked. There is uncertainty over cost-effectiveness for breast cancer surveillance even for very high levels of willingness-to-pay. From our results it is deemed very unlikely PTG is cost-effective.

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OC20

Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer onset: a matter of extrusion imbalances driven by E-cadherin and Filamin A interactions

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E-cadherin germline variants are causative of Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (HDGC), a highly invasive cancer syndrome characterized by the occurrence of diffuse gastric cancer and lobular breast cancer. Patients frequently present with advanced disease at the time of diagnosis, reflecting the silent and aggressive nature of this disorder. Interestingly, pagetoid spread of signet-ring cells beneath an intact gastric epithelium has been identified as a distinctive precursor lesion of invasive gastric cancer. It has been proposed that this feature results from a switch from apical to basal extrusion of E-cadherin dysfunctional cells. Nonetheless, the molecular mechanisms that allow E-cadherin mutant cells to be retained and invade the underlying tissue, rather than being eliminated, remain poorly understood.

To explore the fate of E-cadherin mutant cells in the epithelium, AGS gastric cells were transfected with both wild-type E-cadherin and variants affecting different protein domains. A monolayer system, encompassing labelled mutant cells surrounded by non-labelled wild-type counterparts, was established and monitored to determine extrusion phenotypes. Structural organization, protrusion formation, and cell spreading were further evaluated using a 3D culture system. In addition, distribution analyses, as well as inhibition assays of cytoskeletal components were implemented to assess their contribution to cell delamination.

Herein, we demonstrated that cells expressing variants disrupting the juxtamembrane and intracellular regions exhibit increased basal extrusion rates and achieve greater invasion distances, when compared to those expressing extracellular variants. Notably, the juxtamembrane R749W and intracellular V832M variants were associated with reduced Filamin A activity and actin remodeling. The role of Filamin A in cell extrusion was validated by its depletion in wild-type cells, which promoted significant changes in cytoskeletal architecture, basal nuclear positioning, and integrin upregulation, ultimately leading to an increased capacity of cells to migrate deeply into the extracellular matrix.

Overall, this work reveals a functional interplay between E-cadherin and Filamin A, highlighting their involvement in a shared pathway that regulates epithelial cell extrusion. Moreover, these findings provide new insights into early events of gastric cancer progression and suggest potential therapeutic avenues for intervention in E-cadherin-mediated carcinogenesis.

OC21

CTNNA1 germline alterations are positively associated with hereditary diffuse gastric cancer development

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Introduction: *CTNNA1* germline variants were associated with hereditary diffuse gastric cancer (HDGC) in 2020, despite scarce supporting research. Despite joint efforts to improve knowledge on *CTNNA1*-associated disease and cancer lifetime risks, *CTNNA1*-related disease spectrum, variant-type causality and clinical criteria driving genetic testing remain understudied. This knowledge gap hampers clinical management of carrier families and definition of variant classification criteria.

Aim: Explore genotype-phenotype associations in *CTNNA1* germline variants carriers to improve genetic testing criteria, surveillance and risk reduction recommendation for at-risk individuals.

Methods: Using molecular, clinical and population data from 351 *CTNNA1* variant carrier families worldwide, we analysed genotype-phenotype associations with multivariable logistic regression, and compared results to *CDH1* variant carriers. We knockout *CTNNA1* using CRISPR/Cas9 in gastric cancer (GC) cells, developed *CTNNA1* humanized *Drosophila* models and analysed diffuse GC (DGC) tumour samples from carriers, to assess *CTNNA1*-associated loss-of-function mechanisms. We redefined current HDGC criteria to improve *CTNNA1* genetic testing yield.

Results: We discovered that *CTNNA1* truncated transcripts are degraded by the Nonsense Mediated mRNA Decay (NMD) pathway, and that DGCs from *CTNNA1* truncating carriers completely lose α E-catenin expression. Moreover, our humanized *Drosophila* model demonstrated that only truncating transcripts are non-functional, leading to severe fly lethality and impaired organ development. From the clinical standpoint, we showed that the likelihood of DGC development is 8-fold higher in truncating carriers, compared to non-truncating carriers, and that this risks still holds true compared to wild-type individuals. Nevertheless, *CTNNA1* truncating carriers present a 5-fold lower risk of GC development when compared to *CDH1* carriers. Lobular breast cancer, the 2nd HDGC-associated phenotype, is recurrent among *CTNNA1* truncating carrier families. We adapted and simplified the current clinical guidelines for genetic testing of HDGC families, which increased *CTNNA1*-carrier families' pick-up rate by 9%, without decreasing criteria performance.

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Discussion/Conclusion: We provide, for the first time, compelling evidence supporting *CTNNA1* truncating variants as positively associated with DGC development, being NMD the pathophysiological mechanism leading to *CTNNA1* downregulation in HDGC. We demonstrate that, compared to *CDH1*, *CTNNA1* is a moderate penetrance HDGC gene, and that simplifying current clinical HDGC guidelines can identify more *CTNNA1* variant carrier families, without losing HDGC-associated specificity. This knowledge is new and essential to define surveillance and/or prophylactic measures for *CTNNA1* carrier individuals/families.

OC22

Clinical Impact and Healthcare Expenditure of Prevention versus Treatment in Birt-Hogg-Dubé Syndrome: Findings from the EU PREVENTABLE Project

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Birt-Hogg-Dubé syndrome (BHD) is a rare autosomal dominant disorder caused by germline pathogenic *FLCN* variants, characterized by cutaneous fibrofolliculomas, pulmonary cysts, spontaneous pneumothorax, and increased risk of renal cell carcinoma (RCC). Given the indolent growth of many BHD-associated renal tumours and recommendations to defer intervention until ≥ 3 cm, early genetic diagnosis and structured surveillance are key, focusing on renal preservation rather than survival.

Within the Horizon Europe PREVENTABLE project, we evaluated real-world clinical pathways, outcomes, and healthcare costs associated with prevention versus treatment strategies in BHD individuals from seven ERN-GENTURIS centres. Data were collected using a dedicated IT tool. The prevention pathway included *FLCN* carrier individuals without renal tumours at baseline, as well as those with untreated renal tumours < 3 cm in size; the treatment pathway comprised individuals treated for prior RCC or RCC detected at first risk assessment.

A total of 274 individuals were recorded, including 173 pathogenic *FLCN* variant carriers and 101 non-carriers. Among carriers with sufficient follow-up data, RCC was detected during surveillance in five patients, and at first risk assessment in three. Renal interventions in the prevention pathway included partial nephrectomy ($n = 2$), combined partial and total nephrectomy ($n = 1$), and radiofrequency ablation ($n = 1$). Eleven patients were classified in the treatment pathway, submitted to interventions comprising partial nephrectomy ($n = 5$), total nephrectomy ($n = 3$), or combined partial and total nephrectomy ($n = 2$).

Surveillance was generally in line with current GENTURIS guidelines. MRI was used in over 50% of cases at a mean interval of 22 months, and ultrasound (US) every 18 months. Although CT scans are no longer recommended, they were performed in a subset of patients, possibly reflecting historical practices or limited availability of MRI/US. Survival analyses showed no significant differences across presentations or

pathways, consistent with the focus on reducing morbidity and preserving renal function rather than improving overall survival.

Total costs were €326 723 for prevention and €264 303 for treatment. Despite higher overall prevention costs, due to a larger patient cohort under surveillance, median per-patient costs were lower (€1 580 [IQR: €1 010–2 207]) than treatment (€16 761 [IQR: €14 725–23 427]). Consultations and imaging dominated preventive costs, whereas hospitalizations for nephrectomies were the main cost drivers in treatment pathways.

These findings indicate that, in BHD, prevention provides clinical value through early detection, morbidity reduction and organ-sparing interventions, and is substantially more cost-effective per patient than treatment. Syndrome-specific endpoints should be considered when evaluating prevention strategies in BHD and other rare tumour risk syndromes with high overall survival.

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OC23

Contributing to cancer equity: omics characterization and establishment of patient-derived cancer models from sub-Saharan African patients

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The dramatic increase in cancer incidence in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) calls for urgent cancer research in this region. This includes an effort in cataloguing cancer genomic diversity in SSA samples, and also the establishment of SSA patient-derived cancer cell lines (CCLs) for functional testing and translation of findings for a meaningful impact on SSA cancer patient wellbeing. Here we will report how we have established an informal research network (<https://palopomics.i3s.up.pt/>) with the community of Portuguese-speaking African countries (PALOP, to use the Portuguese abbreviation), including Angola, Cape Verde and Mozambique. We will also present the first results we are obtaining under this cooperation, for the two types of cancer that are more frequent in SSA patients than in other ancestries, triple negative breast cancer (TNBC) and prostate cancer (PC).

For TNBC, we performed whole-exome sequencing (WES+UTRs) on 30 samples from Angola and Cape Verde (African cohort), and compared data with African- and European-American cohorts from The Cancer Genome Atlas. The WES profiling revealed a high somatic mutation burden of the African cohort, with 86% of variants unreported in the COSMIC database, 17% variants estimated as having functional coding impact and 20% overlapped with cis-regulatory elements. Driver hits were mapped in 25 of 30 patients, involving impactful mutations and CNVs (mainly gains in 1q, 8q, 6, and 10p) in known BC driver genes, which are integral components of response to radiation and related DNA repair pathways. Evidence indicates *TTN*, *CEACAM7*, *DEFB132*, *COPZ2* and *GAST* as putative novel driver genes in the TNBC SSA context.

For PC, we collected five fresh samples from SSA patients who had surgery or biopsies at a Lisbon hospital (ULS Almada-Seixal), and were able to establish three SSA-PC cell lines using conditional reprogramming (CR), a method that maintains genotypic and phenotypic features of the original cells. This SSA-PC cell line panel was authenticated by STR and ~1 million SNP profiling, and extensively characterized for proliferation, migration, karyotyping and epithelial and prostate tumor lineage markers. We also performed a high-throughput screen of 1,280 compounds, followed by further validations for hits. A new finding was the reduced sensitivity of SSA-derived models (compared to commercial European PC cell lines) to camptothecin, a TOP1 inhibitor, while being equally sensitive to epirubicin hydrochloride, a TOP2 inhibitor. The cardiac glycoside digoxin, anthelmintic pyriminium pamoate and antirheumatic agent auranofin were also efficient drugs in the in vitro testing.

The global results highlight the added value of conducting omics analyses and establishing patient-derived CCL on SSA ancestry. It is notorious the importance of specific DNA damage repair pathways in TNBC and PC SSA background, with indications on potential therapeutics to be explored.

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OC24

Outcomes of distress assessment in carriers of a pathogenic variant related to Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer: a retrospective study

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Introduction: Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer (HBOC) predisposition syndromes account for approximately 5-10% of breast cancer and 20% of ovarian cancer. In our Familial Cancer Risk Clinic (FCRC), a multidisciplinary team plays a fundamental role in identifying high-risk individuals, providing assistance, assessing expectations, perceived risk of developing cancer, and emotional well-being.

A positive genetic HBOC-related diagnosis in cancer patients', survivors, and healthy individuals can have a significant psychological impact.

To assess the psychological impact on the these population, a prospective, cross-sectional study, published in 2019, developed and validated a telephone questionnaire, to assess psychological distress (anxiety, depression, loss of emotional control), awareness about the disease and the proposed surveillance programs in BRCA1/2 families. A nursing teleconsultation was implemented, in which the distress thermometer is applied simultaneously with the validated questionnaire, one week and one month after the transmission of the positive result. Since then, distress assessment was offered to every identified individual with a HBOC pathogenic variant.

Methods: We performed a retrospective review of all individuals offered distress assessment after a positive genetic HBOC-related diagnosis, between 2020 and 2025.

All individuals were 18 years or older, capable of providing informed consent, regardless previous cancer history.

Results: 837 individuals with a HBOC pathogenic variant were referred to distress assessment. Of the total sample, 90% (752/837) were considered eligible, while 10% (85/837) were excluded due to the following reasons: unavailable or disconnected phone number (59), lack of signed informed consent (12), logistical reasons (8), progressive symptomatic disease precluding participation (5), and death (1). The majority of enrolled individuals were female 78% (588/752).

After assessment, 4% (33/752) were identified as experiencing clinical distress and were referred for further care: 30 to psychology and 3 to psychiatry. In 9% of cases (70/752), a prior psychological and/or psychiatric follow-up was reported. 40% of these individuals (28/70) experienced clinical distress and were encourage to continue care. Almost all individuals with clinical distress were female (60/61).

Conclusions: Advantages of genetic testing include identifying high-risk individuals, estimation of cancer risk and counselling on risk management (healthy lifestyles, increase surveillance, and risk-reducing surgeries). Our results highlight how a nursing teleconsultation program included in test counselling is a useful resource to manage clinical distress.

PREVENTABLE
Learning Hub

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Preventable's RTRS Learning Hub is an online resource dedicated to eight rare tumour risk syndromes (RTRS), with the goal of providing accessible and reliable knowledge, helping patients, carriers, family members, healthcare professionals and health managers to better understand these syndromes and make informed decisions.

For this Hub, different series of videos were created, which will be on continuous display in the 'Learning Hub Room' during the Porto Cancer Meeting (check timetable on-site).

RARE BUT NOT ALONE

Documentaries exploring the challenges and successes of patients, their families, and health providers.

Rare but not alone:
living with Birt-Hogg-Dubé syndrome (00:24:47)

Rare but not alone:
living with Familiar Malignant Melanoma (00:24:00)

Rare but not alone:
living with Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (under production)

Rare but not alone:
living with Hereditary GIST (under production)

Rare but not alone: living with Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Cancer (under production)

Rare but not alone: living with PTEN Hamartoma Tumour Syndrome (00:24:32)

Rare but not alone: living with Peutz-Jeghers Syndrome (00:29:03)

SIMPLY RARE

Infographic animation about each syndrome, in a simple, comprehensive, and engaging way.

it's Simply Rare:
Birt-Hogg-Dubé Syndrome (00:04:34)

it's Simply Rare:
Familial Malignant Melanoma Syndrome (00:04:02)

it's Simply Rare:
Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer Syndrome (00:04:33)

it's Simply Rare:
Hereditary GIST (under production)

it's Simply Rare:
Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Cancer (under production)

it's Simply Rare:
Li-Fraumeni syndrome (00:03:54)

it's Simply Rare:
PTEN Hamartoma Tumour Syndrome (00:03:30)

it's Simply Rare:
Peutz-Jeghers Syndrome (00:04:02)

CLINICAL STORY

Patient testimonials on their journey towards a diagnosis and treatment.

Birt-Hogg-Dubé Syndrome

a Clinical Story:
Núria and Birt-Hogg-Dubé Syndrome (00:05:30) Birt-Hogg-Dubé Syndrome (00:04:34)

a Clinical Story:
Josefina and Birt-Hogg-Dubé Syndrome (00:06:41)

Familiar Malignant Melanoma

a Clinical Story:
Elisabeth and Familial Malignant Melanoma syndrome
(00:06:53)

a Clinical Story:
Emma and Familial Malignant Melanoma syndrome (00:06:15)

Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer

a Clinical Story:
Deolinda and Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (00:04:36)

a Clinical Story:
Henrique and Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (00:04:44)

Hereditary GIST

a Clinical Story:
Henrique and Hereditary GIST (under production)

a Clinical Story:
Maria do Carmo and Hereditary GIST (under production)

Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Cancer

a Clinical Story:
Laura and Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Cancer
(00:08:38)

a Clinical Story:
María and Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Cancer
(00:08:22)

a Clinical Story:
Cristina and Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell
Cancer (under production)

Li-Fraumeni Syndrome

a Clinical Story:
Clementine and Li-Fraumeni Syndrome (00:06:54)

a Clinical Story:
Elodie and Li-Fraumeni Syndrome (00:08:12)

a Clinical Story:
Justine and Li-Fraumeni Syndrome (00:05:36)

PTEN Hamartoma Tumour Syndrome

a Clinical Story:
"Joan" and PTEN Hamartoma Tumour Syndrome (00:07:21)

a Clinical Story:
Mariska and PTEN Hamartoma Tumour Syndrome (00:06:08)

a Clinical Story:
Cindy and PTEN Hamartoma Tumour Syndrome (00:06:13)

Peutz-Jeghers Syndrome

a Clinical Story:
Kira and Peutz-Jeghers Syndrome (00:08:13)

a Clinical Story:
Sabine and Peutz-Jeghers Syndrome (00:09:20)

a Clinical Story:
Samantha and Peutz-Jeghers Syndrome (00:07:07)

RISKY TALKLS

A videocast series featuring leading experts on RTRS.

Birt-Hogg-Dubé Syndrome

Joan Brunet (Oncologist)
on Using genetics to tailor care (00:07:01)

Vicky Garriga (Radiologist) on The key role of
radiosurveillance (00:07:20)

Dolors Sitjas (Dermatologist) on Dermatology at the heart
of early diagnosis (00:05:37)

Roger Boix (Urologist) on Kidney surveillance and
treatment: a fine balance (00:06:56)

Familial Malignant Melanoma

Hildegunn Vetti (Clinical geneticist) on Genetic testing: the
first step for prevention in FMM (00:05:03)

Ingeborg Bachmann (Dermatologist) on Skin monitoring: an
effective prevention tool (00:05:14)

Oddbjørn Straume (Oncologist) on The ongoing success
story of melanoma treatment (00:04:08) Familial Malignant

Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer

Carla Oliveira (Researcher) on Research at the heart of
clinical care (00:05:57)

Sérgio Castedo (Geneticist) on Breaking the chain:
preimplantation genetic diagnosis (00:03:28)

Elsa Madureira (Nutritionist), on Living without a stomach
(00:06:40)

Hereditary GIST

Paula Soares (Researcher) on Hereditary GIST (under production)

António Gouveia (Surgeon) on Hereditary GIST (under production)

Daniela Almeida (Oncologist) on Hereditary GIST (under production)

Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Cancer

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P1

Unraveling Cancer Stem Cell Biomarkers Driving Breast Cancer Metastatic Organotropism to the Brain and Bone

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Breast cancer (BC) remains a leading cause of cancer-related mortality, largely due to metastatic dissemination. Brain and bone metastases represent clinically challenging secondary sites, associated with poor prognosis and limited therapeutic options. Increasing evidence supports the involvement of cancer stem cells (CSCs) in metastatic initiation and their interaction with organ-specific microenvironments, contributing to metastatic organotropism and therapy resistance. Thus, identifying CSC-associated biomarkers and understanding their functional relevance within distinct metastatic niches is essential to improve patient stratification and therapeutic targeting. Using the metastatic MDA-MB-231 BC model and its brain- and bone-tropic variants, we applied a membrane-focused proteomic approach to identify CSC-associated biomarkers involved in metastatic organotropism.

In brain-tropic cells, PGRMC1 emerged as an overexpressed candidate CSC biomarker. PGRMC1 chemical inhibition using AG-205 significantly reduced mammosphere formation, indicating impaired stem-like properties *in vitro*. Importantly, *in vivo* limiting dilution assays, using the chick chorioallantoic membrane, revealed a consistent trend towards decreased stem cell frequency in AG-205-treated brain-tropic cells compared to control. Functional *in vitro* validation of CSC

properties using CRISPR-Cas9-edited PGRMC1 cells is currently ongoing. Clinically, high PGRMC1 expression in primary breast tumours was associated with aggressive clinicopathological features, a CSC profile, and reduced 5-year overall survival. These findings were further validated in an independent cohort of primary tumours from patients who developed brain metastases.

In a parallel approach, proteomic profiling of bone-tropic cells identified NGFR as an overexpressed candidate. Currently, NGFR's role in CSC properties of bone-tropic BC cells is being explored in a silenced model established using CRISPR-Cas9 knockout and single-cell cloning. Analysis of primary breast tumours demonstrated that NGFR expression correlates with adverse clinicopathological features, relevant molecular biomarkers, and a CSC profile. Although NGFR expression alone was not directly associated with patient prognosis, its incorporation into a CSC signature improved patient survival stratification.

Overall, our work identified PGRMC1 and NGFR as putative CSC-associated membrane biomarkers potentially involved in driving BC metastasis to the brain and bone, respectively. Importantly, the identification of CSC-based membrane biomarkers tailored to individual metastatic sites may improve patient stratification and support more precise clinical approaches, reinforcing their potential as prognostic tools and therapeutic targets, with direct implications for the development of site-specific intervention strategies in metastatic BC.

P2

ADARB1 dictates nuclear plasticity and invasive phenotypes associated with Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer

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Hereditary diffuse gastric cancer (HDGC) is an autosomal dominant cancer syndrome caused by germline variants in the *CDH1* gene, which encodes E-cadherin. E-cadherin dysfunction is strongly associated with the ability of cancer cells to diffusely invade the gastric wall and disseminate into the peritoneal cavity and adjacent organs, however the molecular mechanisms driving this invasive behaviour remain poorly understood. Herein, we propose that the impairment of E-cadherin activates a mechanotransduction program that leads to nuclear remodelling, ultimately promoting a pro-invasive cellular signature.

To address this hypothesis, we established an *in vitro* model of transfected cell lines expressing either wild-type E-cadherin or the Y755C mutant form identified in an HDGC family. Comparative analysis of the nuclear proteome from wild-type and mutant cells was performed using high-resolution mass features by implementing width-controlled microchannel devices designed to recapitulate the narrow geometry of the extracellular matrix. We verified that ADARB1 silencing in wild-type E-cadherin cells resulted an enhanced migratory capacity, characterized by persistent and directed movement with reduced interaction with channel walls. Additionally, we detected a decrease in nuclear solidity accompanied

by increased structural irregularities, typically associated with a more deformable nucleus and closely resembling the mutant cell phenotype. In contrast, wild-type cells transfected with non-targeting siRNA displayed frequent pauses when migrating within spatially restricted environments.

Overall, these findings demonstrate that loss of E-cadherin function induces changes in the abundance of specific nuclear proteins that modulate nuclear plasticity during cell migration and propagation throughout the extracellular matrix. Furthermore, our study provides evidence that ADARB1 acts as a critical effector downstream of E-cadherin dysfunction and highlights nuclear mechanotransduction pathways as potential therapeutic targets to limit tumour dissemination.

P3

P-cadherin - a putative biomarker of a hybrid EMT and immune evasive phenotype

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Epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT) is a dynamic and plastic process in cancer that enables tumor cells to acquire enhanced adaptability, invasiveness, stemness, and immune evasive capabilities. Along this continuum, hybrid epithelial (E) / mesenchymal (M) phenotypes are increasingly recognized as critical mediators of metastasis, therapy resistance, and immune modulation. P-cadherin, encoded by the *CDH3* gene, is a calcium-dependent cell-cell adhesion glycoprotein whose overexpression is associated with aggressive basal-like and triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) and poor prognosis. While its roles in cell motility and invasion are well documented, its contribution to hybrid E/M phenotypes and tumor immune regulation remains incompletely understood.

In this study, we investigated the role of P-cadherin in modulating hybrid EMT and immune evasion in breast cancer through integrated bioinformatic and experimental approaches. Large-scale transcriptomic analyses of CCLE, TCGA-BRCA, and PanCancer Atlas datasets revealed that *CDH3* expression is significantly enriched in basal-like tumors and Basal A breast cancer cell lines. Elevated *CDH3* levels were predominantly driven by copy number gains rather than promoter methylation and were associated with poorer overall survival. Notably, *CDH3* expression peaked in tumors with intermediate EMT scores and correlated with E and M gene programs, supporting its association with hybrid E/M phenotypes and EMT plasticity.

Functional validation in breast cancer cell lines confirmed that P-cadherin promotes EMT and induces PD-L1 expression. In an EMT-inducible MCF10A-ER-Src model, tamoxifen treatment triggered a M transition accompanied by upregulation of P-cadherin and PD-L1. Similar effects were observed following genetic manipulation of *CDH3* using CRISPR/Cas9-mediated knockout and retroviral overexpression. Importantly, CAM assays revealed enhanced tumorigenesis and reduced immune cell recruitment, demonstrating functional immune exclusion and immune evasion.

Together, these findings identify P-cadherin as a central regulator linking EMT plasticity with immune modulation in breast cancer. By sustaining hybrid E/M states and promoting PD-L1-associated immune escape, P-cadherin emerges as a promising biomarker and therapeutic target in aggressive breast carcinomas.

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P4

Genome-wide CRISPR screen identifies new targets for gastric cancer treatment

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Gastric cancer (GC) represents a global health challenge, being the fifth most common cancer worldwide. Due to the absence of early symptoms and the lack of screening programs, it is often diagnosed at an advanced stage, where treatment options are scarce.

About 20% GC overexpress HER2 and can be treated with inhibitors such as trastuzumab. However, due to tumour heterogeneity, only ~47% of patients respond, and even those who do, eventually develop resistance to it. Therefore, there is an urgent need to identify additional molecular vulnerabilities and modifiers of therapy response to extend the benefit of HER2 inhibition and to develop new strategies for the majority of GC patients who are HER2-negative.

This project aims to uncover the biology behind the lack of efficacy of anti-HER2 therapies in HER2-positive GC. We hypothesize that there might be genes whose loss may enhance (or hinder) the efficacy of anti-HER2 therapy.

To test this, we performed a pilot genome-wide CRISPR screen, in a HER2-positive GC cell line, to identify genes which lead to increase in sensitivity or resistance to HER2 small molecule inhibitor, lapatinib, and it was identified over 20 hits. Validation was performed with target knock-out (KO) of the top hits in multiple GC cell lines using CRISPR/Cas9 followed by drug-response assays with HER2 inhibitors to assess KO effects.

KO of the top hit, RAB14, sensitized multiple GC cell lines to different HER2 inhibitors. Unexpectedly, we found that loss of

RAB14 was synergistic with HER2 inhibition, not only in HER2-positive, but also in HER2-negative cell lines. RAB14 was found overexpressed in GC. Preliminary data further suggest that RIC8A may have a similar effect to RAB14 in HER2-positive cells.

Additionally, validation of the genes of interest was performed in a pilot *Mus musculus* study, in which both genes demonstrated promising results in reducing cell proliferation and improving therapeutic response.

In summary, we identified two modifiers of response to HER2 inhibition, RAB14 (overexpressed in GC) and RIC8A, each synergizing with lapatinib to reduce cell viability. The notable synergistic effect of RAB14 depletion and lapatinib in HER2-negative cells, likely reflects lapatinib pleiotropy, providing an opportunity to treat HER2-negative (80% of GC cases) or HER2 heterogeneous GC, which currently lacks or poorly respond to targeted treatment strategies.

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P5

Development of an Organoid-based Multi-organ-on-a-chip to study Gastric Cancer Metastasis

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Gastric cancer (GC) remains a leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide, mostly because of late diagnosis. According to the Laurén classification, GC is divided into intestinal, diffuse, and mixed subtypes, each with distinct growth patterns and dissemination routes. Intestinal-type GC forms solid tumors that metastasize to distant organs such as the liver, lung, and bone. In contrast, diffuse-type GC comprises poorly cohesive cells that spread rapidly through the peritoneum and lymphatic system, often causing early mortality due to peritoneal carcinomatosis. Despite these differences, the mechanisms driving organ-specific metastatic tropism and dissemination speed remain poorly understood, partly due to limitations of animal models and the impossibility of observing the full natural history of metastasis in patients with diffuse-type GC.

To address these challenges, we propose a human-relevant multi-organ-on-a-chip (MoC) platform integrating gastric cancer organoids and/or spheroids with organ-specific target tissues. This system combines the biological fidelity of 3D tumor models with the experimental control of microfluidic technologies.

We hypothesize that this MoC will recapitulate subtype-specific and organ-preferential metastatic behaviors observed in vivo, advancing our understanding of GC metastasis, establishing a predictive human cancer avatar, and providing a versatile platform for personalized medicine.

The proposed device consists of four interconnected chambers: one representing the gastric tumor and three representing common metastatic sites. For intestinal-type GC, these include liver, lung, and bone, while for diffuse-type GC, the bone compartment is replaced by a peritoneal model. A perfusable, fibronectin-coated channel lined with human umbilical vein endothelial cells functions as an artificial vasculature, enabling dynamic tumor cell dissemination. Initial validation uses immortalized GC and organ-specific cell lines, followed by patient-derived organoids.

The platform is engineered using multilayered PDMS microfabrication and plasma bonding, with each compartment filled with hydrogel to support long-term 3D culture. The MoC platform has been validated, showing robust hydrogel confinement and stable separation between the channel and tissue matrices. Controlled fluid exchange into the hydrogel occurs within 2 hours under 3 mbar pressure, confirming transport across the compartment interface. GC spheroids are being fabricated using agarose microwell molds for future integration into the chip. Fluorescent cell tracing demonstrates longitudinal tracking of cells for up to 16 days, supporting future studies of tumor dissemination within the system.

Overall, this multi-organ-on-a-chip platform provides a human-relevant system to study subtype-specific gastric cancer metastasis, enabling real-time analysis of tumor dissemination and supporting future translational and personalized approaches.

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P6

PDX-Derived Organoids: A Translational Platform to Investigate PDAC Biology and Microenvironment Interactions

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Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma (PDAC) remains one of the deadliest cancers, with a 5-year survival rate of 8%. Tumor progression and metastization are influenced by complex interactions between cancer cells, the immune system and the surrounding stromal cells, contributing to its highly desmoplastic stroma.

Although considered a cold tumor, the immune system plays a critical role in metastization process.

To overcome the lack of an adaptive immune system in PDX models, Patient-Derived Xenograft Organoids (PDXOs) were established to maintain a close relation with human tumor biology. After PDXO validation and characterization, advanced techniques such as live imaging, mass spectrometry and secretome were performed in co-cultures between organoids and NK cells to investigate their ability to eliminate cancer cells and revealing the effectiveness of the immune response in metastization process. Additionally, co-cultures between PDXOs and CAFs (Cancer-associated Fibroblasts) were established in order to deeply understand the interactions between the cancer cells and the main protagonists in PDAC desmoplasia.

In this study, organoids have proven to be an efficient platform for validating our findings in mouse models, constituting a promising strategy that replicates human tumors, and opening new doors to explore interactions between cancer cells and tumor microenvironment.

P7

Genetic characterization of RET fusion genes in papillary and poorly differentiated thyroid cancer

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Background: RET is a receptor tyrosine kinase that has been found altered in multiple thyroid cancer (TC) subtypes. Whilst mutations are the most common alteration in medullary thyroid cancer, *RET* fusions are long known to be involved in PTC. Such fusions, however, are yet to be fully characterized. Here, we investigated the role of fusion genes as a RET activating mechanism in PTCs and poorly differentiated thyroid cancers (PDTCs).

Methods: To identify and characterize *RET* fusions, we interrogated 315 PTCs and 132 PDTCs, previously subjected to targeted sequencing, from the cBioportal database, and 531 PTCs previously subjected to whole-exome (TCGA) and whole-genome sequencing (PCAWG). The frame status and fusion driver probability were evaluated using Oncofuse. Breakpoint locations in the gene sequence and protein domain were also assessed. The TCGA RNA sequencing data taken from PTC cases harboring *RET* fusions was examined to measure the expression levels of RET.

Results: *RET* fusion genes were identified in 44 primary and 17 metastatic PTCs (61/846, 7,2%), and in 1 primary and 6 metastatic PDTCs (7/132, 5,3%). Of the 68 *RET* fusions identified, 64 were in-frame (94%), and 4 were out-of-frame (6%). In PTCs, 52% of *RET* fusions had a driver probability of 99%, while in PDTCs, all *RET* fusions displayed a driver probability lower than 50%. All of the 68 fusion genes were found to affect the transmembrane domain of the *RET* gene,

with 91% affecting the exon 12 (n=62), and 9% affecting the exon 11 (n=6) of *RET*. Recurrent fusion genes included those affecting *CCDC6* (n=43, 63%), *NCOA4* (n=9, 13%), and *ERC1* (n=4) genes. RNA sequencing data showed that PTCs harboring *RET* fusions had a significantly higher expression of the *RET* gene than those not harboring any *RET* genetic alteration (median z-score 2.2 vs -0.4, $p < 0.0001$).

Conclusion: Fusion genes affecting *RET* were found in primary tumors and metastases from both PTCs and PDTCs, thus suggesting the presence of an activating mechanism of RET at different stages of the disease. These findings thus broaden the spectrum of molecular mechanisms of RET activation in thyroid cancer, with diagnostic and potentially therapeutic relevance.

P8

An organ-on-a-chip model to explore a molecular signature of Diffuse Gastric Cancer initiation

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Introduction: Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer (HDGC) is linked to mutations in the tumor-suppressing gene *CDH1*. The multifocal and often asymptomatic nature of this disease prevents early diagnosis. Many early-stage lesions remain undetectable through standard gastroscopic surveillance, which can result in the progression to late-stage cancer. Thus, the most effective measure against DGC in these patients is prophylactic total gastrectomy (PTG); however, this procedure is associated with significant long-term consequences. Currently, it is challenging to predict whether a patient with HDGC will develop invasive disease. With this in mind, we believe that identifying potential biomarkers linked to locally invasive and treatable disease could enhance risk stratification and lead to more informed clinical decision-making. However, since most patients with HDGC undergo PTG, studying the initiation of cancer presents a challenge, highlighting a secondary unmet need. To address this issue, we aim to develop a biomimetic tool that closely mimics the physiology of the gastric environment, enabling the identification of secreted biomarkers that could be predictive of disease onset.

Methods: Our team developed a biomimetic tool that effectively replicates the physiological environment of the

stomach. The DGC-on-a-chip is designed by soft lithography and xurography, mimicking the epithelium, basement membrane, and lamina propria of the gastric mucosa. The MKN74 cell line was utilized as a model for cohesive gastric epithelium, while KATOIII cells represented DGC. We evaluated the chip's performance under long-term cell culture conditions by assessing its resistance to delamination, as well as its suitability as a cell culture vessel. For biomarker profiling, we will analyze secretomes from patient-derived normal gastric organoids and KATOIII cell cultures (both 2D, ongoing 3D, and on-chip) using liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry and smallRNAseq.

Results: Our results show that the designed DGC-on-chip exhibits resistance to delamination. A co-culture was employed to replicate DGC foci. A viable co-culture of KATOIII and MKN74 cells was achieved, with KATOIII foci distinguishable for up to 16 days with FarRed tracer labelling. Proteomic analysis of Kato III cells compared to normal gastric organoids yielded a final dataset of 2 396 relevant proteins. Among these, 1 708 (71.3%) proteins were uniquely secreted by KATOIII, while only 28 proteins (1.17%) were exclusively identified in the organoids' secretome. 660 proteins (27.5%) were shared between organoids and KATOIII. Our analysis identified 17 proteins significantly altered in DGC that are potential biomarkers of invasive disease.

Conclusion: These results highlight the potential for discovering biomarkers associated with early DGC. Further validation in a 3D environment, on a chip, and in clinical settings could improve risk stratification and lead to more informed clinical decision-making.

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P9

Metabolic and Structural Divergence Between Diffuse and Intestinal Gastric Cancer Cell Lines

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Gastric cancer comprises distinct subtypes with divergent biological features and metastatic patterns. Diffuse gastric cancer (DGC) is highly aggressive and preferentially disseminates within the peritoneal cavity, whereas the intestinal subtype forms glandular structures and metastasizes mainly via hematogenous routes. Subtype-specific metabolic features may influence gastric cancer behavior and interactions with the microenvironment [1,2,3], yet their relationship with the distinct metastatic dissemination patterns of diffuse and intestinal subtypes remains unclear. To address this, we compared mitochondrial organization, redox balance, antioxidant defenses, and cellular organization in diffuse and intestinal gastric cancer cell lines.

Diffuse (MKN45, Kato III) and Intestinal (MKN74) gastric cancer cell lines were analyzed in vitro to assess subtype-specific metabolic and structural features. Mitochondrial organization, metabolic activity, redox homeostasis, antioxidant defense, and cellular organization were evaluated using Tetramethylrhodamine methyl ester and resazurin assays, ROS and H₂O₂ challenge assays, Western blot analysis, and qualitative assessment of cell-cell adhesion markers, including E-cadherin.

Microscopic analysis showed that MKN74 cells have higher TMRM signal (~3x) and larger mitochondrial structures than MKN45 and Kato III cells; however, MKN74 cells also exhibited larger cell area. Although basal ROS levels were markedly higher in MKN74 (~11x), all three gastric cancer cell lines

exhibited similar responses to H₂O₂ dose-response assays, suggesting distinct antioxidant defense profiles. In fact, MKN45 exhibited higher catalase (34%; 1.40 vs 1.04 U.A.) and SOD1 (62%; 0.93 vs 0.58 U.A.) expression compared with MKN74, consistent with enhanced antioxidant capacity. Within diffuse-type models, MKN45 also showed higher catalase (26%; 1.40 vs 1.11 U.A.) and SOD1 (37%; 0.93 vs 0.68 U.A.) levels than Kato III, whereas thioredoxin expression was highest in Kato III (0.92 U.A.) relative to MKN45 (105%; 0.45 U.A.) and MKN74 (89%; 0.48 U.A.), indicating distinct redox regulatory strategies. Structural organization and cell-cell interactions differed markedly between models. MKN74 displayed elevated smooth muscle actin expression relative to MKN45 (44%; 0.78 vs 0.54 U.A.) and Kato III (130%; 0.78 U.A. vs 0.34 U.A.), consistent with greater cytoskeletal organization. This was mirrored by cell-cell adhesion patterns, with E-cadherin expression highest in MKN74, reduced in MKN45, and minimal to nearly absent in Kato III, reflecting progressive loss of cellular cohesion, and coherent with loss of epithelial phenotype.

Gastric cancer cell lines exhibit subtype-specific differences in mitochondrial features, redox balance, antioxidant defenses, and cellular organization. These distinct phenotypes may contribute to the divergent biological behavior of diffuse and intestinal gastric cancer subtypes, potentially influencing metastatic patterns.

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P10

Metabolic Crosstalk in Gastric Cancer: Adipose Tissue-Derived Lipids Drive Lipid Droplet Accumulation in Gastric Cancer Cells

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Diffuse gastric cancer (DGC) represents one of the most lethal and therapeutically refractory gastrointestinal malignancies. Unlike the intestinal subtype of gastric cancer (GC), which often forms cohesive glandular masses, DGC is characterized by non-cohesive, invasive cells that frequently harbor CDH1 genetic inactivation. The high lethality of DGC is "paradoxical": DGC cells are fragile to survive in circulation, but exhibit the capacity to form peritoneal metastases. Peritoneal adipose tissue (AT) has emerged as an active metabolic component of the metastatic niche, yet the metabolic strategies supporting DGC survival in adipose-rich environments remain unclear. Lipid droplets (LDs) are key regulators of cellular metabolism and dysregulated LD expansion is a feature of multiple metabolic diseases. LD homeostasis has been identified as a possible tumor-intrinsic survival mechanism in DGC but the source of fatty acids during peritoneal dissemination remains unexplored.

To investigate the metabolic crosstalk between GC and the peritoneal niche, we assessed the tumor secretome's influence on the adipogenic niche by exposing SGBS preadipocytes to conditioned medium from diffuse (MKN45, Kat0III) and intestinal (MKN74) GC cell lines during differentiation process. The tumor secretome had no visible impact on preadipocyte differentiation. Then, to model physiological paracrine

interactions, we performed *ex vivo* co-cultures of GC cells with AT explants from different body regions (omental and perigastric) from bariatric and cancer patients (ULSSJ). By quantifying LD accumulation through BODIPY staining, we assessed subtype-specific capacity of GC cells to use lipids from distinct adipose depots.

Our primary results showed a higher baseline LD content in KATOIII cells by approximately 4 and 10 times when compared with MKN74 and MKN45, respectively. Co-culturing with AT significantly increased LD accumulation in all three cancer cell lines. In MKN74 cells, LD levels increased in response to AT from both bariatric and cancer patients, with a markedly stronger effect observed with cancer-derived adipose tissue. MKN45 cells also showed increased lipid droplet accumulation, with a more pronounced increase in the presence of cancer-derived AT. KATOIII cells exhibited similar levels in lipid droplet accumulation when exposed to AT from both bariatric and cancer patients. In both diffuse and intestinal-type cell lines, results consistently showed higher LD accumulation in the presence of omental compared to perigastric AT, with omental AT inducing a more pronounced increase in LD content.

These findings suggest anatomical specificity of AT in tumor-adipocyte interactions and LD accumulation supports the metabolic reprogramming in DGC cells, with lipid metabolism potentially serving as an alternative energy source to glycolysis in DGC cells, providing the opportunity to identify metabolic vulnerabilities that may be exploited for future therapeutic intervention.

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P11

Spatial Heterogeneity of TLR9-Positive Immune Cells in Glioma Tissue Assessed by Digital Pathology

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Toll-like receptor 9 (TLR9) plays a key role in innate immune signaling and has been implicated in tumor-immune interactions across multiple cancer types. However, its spatial distribution across immune cell populations within tumor tissue remains insufficiently characterized, particularly in relation to tumor molecular subtypes.

In this study, we investigated the density and spatial heterogeneity of TLR9-positive immune and nonimmune cells in glioma tissue using digital pathology analysis of samples immunohistochemically stained with a multimarker panel. Diffuse astrocytoma tumors spotted on tissue microarrays were analyzed to quantify TLR9-positive and TLR9-negative cells across multiple myeloid immune cell types, including macrophages, dendritic cells, and granulocytes. Other immune cells and nonimmune cells were analyzed as separate groups. Cell-level detections were aggregated at the tissue region level, enabling computation of cell-type-specific TLR9 positivity fractions and densities.

Comparative analyses were performed between isocitrate dehydrogenase (IDH) wild-type (wt) and mutant (mut) glioma samples. Non-parametric statistical testing revealed marked differences in TLR9-positive fractions for selected immune cell populations, with granulocyte derived compartments showing

clearly the highest fraction of TLR9 positivity. Tissue resident microglia showed significantly higher TLR9-positivity in more aggressive IDHwt than IDHmut tumors, aligning with higher density of TLR9+ cells in general.

These findings highlight substantial spatial and cellular heterogeneity in TLR9 expression within the diffuse glioma immune microenvironment. The study demonstrates how quantitative digital pathology can support more nuanced immune profiling by moving beyond single-biomarker histopathological assessment. Such approaches may facilitate improved hypothesis generation for immunological mechanisms and support the development of spatially informed biomarkers in cancer research.

P12

Investigating the role of MRP8+ Cells in Orchestrating Pro-Tumour Inflammation in PDAC

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Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) remains one of the deadliest cancers, and overcoming its clinical challenges requires a deeper understanding of the inflammatory processes shaping its tumour microenvironment (TME). Myeloid-related protein 8 (MRP8; S100A8) is a key mediator of inflammation in several diseases, yet its role in cancer is poorly defined.

Our recent findings reveal that high infiltration of MRP8+ cells in PDAC correlates with reduced overall survival in patients. Using genetically engineered mouse models (GEMMs), we observed that increased MRP8+ cell infiltration triggers an inflammation-driven cascade that reprograms the immune milieu toward a tumour-promoting state. We hypothesize that MRP8+ cells facilitate PDAC progression by shaping a protumorigenic immune microenvironment.

To test this, we will perform adoptive transfer experiments by introducing isolated MRP8+ cells into PDAC mouse models, with or without endogenous MRP8 expression. Tumour growth and metastasis will be monitored by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and immune profiling will assess changes in infiltrating cell populations. Together, these studies will define the functional role of MRP8+ cells in PDAC and evaluate their potential as therapeutic targets.

P13

Defining and Enhancing NK Cell Control of Metastasis in PDAC

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Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) is an aggressive malignancy by early metastasis and a profoundly immunosuppressive tumor microenvironment (TME) that limits immunotherapy efficacy. Natural killer (NK) cells, key cytotoxic effectors of innate immunity, may restrain metastasis, yet their roles in PDAC remain unclear.

Our data show that NK cells act as critical barriers to metastatic spread. NK-cell depletion in murine PDAC models increased liver and lung metastases and circulating tumor cells, while adoptive NK transfer reduced dissemination and improved survival. These findings were confirmed in patient-derived xenografts. NK loss triggered epithelial-mesenchymal transition, inflammatory signaling, and TME remodeling with expansion of suppressive myeloid and stromal populations.

We will investigate how NK cells control tumor invasion, survival in circulation, and metastatic seeding, and how they shape epithelial plasticity, stromal activation, and immune balance within the TME. These studies aim to define how NK-tumor interactions govern disease progression and establish NK cells as actionable therapeutic targets to improve outcomes in PDAC.

P14

Optimizing Prevention and Care in Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes: Prevalence and Care Burden from the PREVENTABLE European Consortium

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Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes (RTRS) are a heterogeneous group of rare genetic conditions, each affecting fewer than 5 per 10,000 individuals, but collectively associated with substantial clinical complexity and long-term healthcare burden. Management requires specialized diagnosis, structured surveillance, preventive interventions, and lifelong multidisciplinary care. European Reference Networks (ERNs), particularly the ERN GENTURIS, aim to centralize expertise, harmonize care pathways for individuals with TRS, and develop European guidelines for RTRS. The present work evaluates the prevalence and medical burden of RTRS carrier families receiving care within ERN GENTURIS reference centres across Europe that are part of the PREVENTABLE consortium.

Data from families with a genetically confirmed diagnosis of eight RTRS (Hereditary Diffuse Gastric Cancer, Hereditary Gastrointestinal Stromal Tumour, Birt-Hogg-Dubé, Hereditary Leiomyomatosis and Renal Cell Carcinoma, Li-Fraumeni, PTEN Hamartoma Tumour, Familial Malignant Melanoma, and Peutz-Jeghers syndromes) were retrospectively collected between 2000 and 2023 from nine ERN GENTURIS reference centres in seven European countries. A combined catchment population of 16.6 million individuals served by the participating centres was used to calculate the prevalence of each RTRS.

A total of 1,018 RTRS families were identified with Li-Fraumeni syndrome (31%), PTEN hamartoma tumour syndrome (29%), and HDGC syndrome (10%) accounting for 70% of families. Overall, 2,596 people were offered genetic testing compatible with their RTRS risk. From these, 1,080 non-carriers (41%) were discharged from follow-up, reducing unnecessary surveillance, psychological burden, and healthcare resource use. Structured multidisciplinary surveillance, preventive interventions, and/or oncological treatment within reference centres was offered to 1,516 carriers. The prevalence of RTRS carriers managed within ERN GENTURIS reference centres participating in the PREVENTABLE consortium was estimated at approximately 1 per 10,000. However, several studies indicate that a substantial proportion of RTRS carriers remain undiagnosed, with estimates suggesting that more than 50%, and in some settings up to 90%, of affected individuals are not yet identified. Therefore, the true population prevalence of RTRS is likely to be considerably higher.

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Although RTRS remain individually rare, this analysis demonstrates their substantial collective clinical and organizational burden within European centres of excellence. These findings highlight both the importance of reference centres in centralizing specialized care, optimizing resource allocation, and informing harmonized European care pathways and health policy planning, and the critical need to close existing diagnostic gaps to enable equitable access to preventive care for rare cancer predisposition syndromes.

P15

Monoallelic BRCA1/2 variants in pediatric, adolescent and young adult patients with central nervous system tumors

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Primary tumors of the central nervous system (CNS) are the second most common cancer in children, after leukemia, and the leading cause of cancer mortality among children, adolescents, and young adults (AYAs). Despite advances in both histopathological and molecular classification, these tumors remain highly variable in biological and clinical terms. In recent years, thanks to next-generation sequencing (NGS), it has been observed that a considerable number of pediatric patients with cancer have germline variants in genes associated with cancer predisposition.

Some cancer predisposition syndromes (CPSs), such as Li-Fraumeni syndrome (LFS) or neurofibromatosis type 1 (NF1), are well established in the context of CNS tumors. However, the role of genes typically implicated in adult neoplasms is less clear. The *BRCA1* DNA Repair Associated (*BRCA1*) and *BRCA2* DNA Repair Associated (*BRCA2*) genes, known to encode proteins essential for DNA damage repair through homologous

recombination, are traditionally associated with hereditary breast and ovarian cancer (HBOC) syndromes. Germline variants in the *BRCA* genes have also been associated with isolated solid tumors, affecting prostate and pancreas among other organs. However, *BRCA* genes role in CNS tumor susceptibility in younger patients is still debated. We analyzed 367 pediatric and adolescent and young adult (AYA) patients with primary CNS tumors. Tumors were classified according to the WHO Classification of Tumors of the CNS, 5th edition. All patients underwent clinical exome sequencing, including *BRCA1* and *BRCA2*. Germline *BRCA1/2* variants were identified in 17/367 patients (4.6%). Pathogenic or likely pathogenic variants (PV/LPV) were detected in 5 patients (1.4% of the cohort). The remaining patients carried variants of uncertain significance (VUSs). Our findings support emerging evidence that monoallelic pathogenic variants in *BRCA1/2* may act as low-penetrance susceptibility factors in pediatric and AYA CNS tumors rather than as primary oncogenic drivers. Interpretation is limited by cohort heterogeneity, lack of a non-cancer control group, and absence of systematic somatic analyses to assess biallelic inactivation or homologous recombination deficiency.

Nevertheless, these data support the inclusion of *BRCA* genes in germline testing panels for pediatric and AYA CNS tumors, with relevant implications for genetic counseling and long-term surveillance.

P16

A rare case of pediatric high grade glioma in the context of combined Li-Fraumeni and Lynch Syndrome

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Pediatric-type diffuse high-grade gliomas (pHGG) are rare and aggressive tumors of the central nervous system. Increasing evidence supports the relevance of integrated molecular profiling and germline testing, particularly in early onset patients, to identify cancer predisposition syndromes (CPSs) with diagnostic, therapeutic, and familial implications. We describe a 8-year-old patient presented with a focal epileptic seizure characterized by impaired awareness, bilateral clonic movements, drooling, and chewing automatisms.

Brain MRI revealed a frontal lobe lesion, which was surgically completely resected. Histopathological examination and DNA methylation profiling confirmed a diagnosis of pHGG, H3/IDH wildtype. Immunophenotypic analysis revealed loss of PMS2 expression, suggesting that the possibility of a Lynch syndrome-associated glioma should be investigated. Molecular analysis revealed mismatch repair deficiency due to a *MutL Homolog 1 (MLH1)* variant [NM_000249.4]: c.2059C>T (p.Arg687Trp), with an allele frequency (AF) of approximately 71%, along with a *Tumor Protein P53 (TP53)* variant [NM_000546.6]: c.535C>A (p.His179Asn), with an AF of approximately 72%. The patient had a suggestive family history of multiple cancers on

the paternal side. In particular, the paternal grandfather was affected by colorectal and prostate cancer, and the patient's father was undergoing surveillance colonoscopies for a tubular adenoma. Both variants were confirmed at the germline level. The MLH1 variant, classified as pathogenic according to ACMG criteria, was inherited from the father and was consistent with Lynch syndrome (LS). In contrast, the TP53 variant, classified as likely pathogenic, occurred *de novo* and was consistent with Li-Fraumeni syndrome (LFS). This case therefore represents a rare coexistence of two distinct hereditary tumor predisposition syndromes in the same patient.

While high-grade gliomas are a well-recognized manifestation of LFS, Lynch syndrome has also been associated with glioma development, suggesting a potential additive role of mismatch repair deficiency in tumorigenesis. Identification of the germline MLH1 variant enabled cascade genetic testing within the family. The patient subsequently received a personalized treatment strategy, including immunotherapy combined with proton therapy. This case underscores the critical importance of comprehensive molecular and germline characterization in pediatric high-grade gliomas. The coexistence of Li-Fraumeni and Lynch syndromes highlights the complexity of cancer predisposition and supports routine consideration of germline testing. Moreover, identification of mismatch repair deficiency may have therapeutic implications—particularly for the use of immunotherapy—as well as significant consequences for familial surveillance.

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P17

Genetic studies beyond index cases: cascade genetic testing relevance for hereditary cancer care

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Background: Genetic testing is integral to the diagnosis, management, and prevention of hereditary cancers as 5–10% of malignancies occur in the context of an increased risk associated with inherited germline alterations. Identifying pathogenic variants in cancer susceptibility genes enables personalized risk management, informed surgical decisions, targeted treatments, tailored screening, and reproductive options for carriers and their families. We aimed to evaluate the impact of cascade testing by measuring the number of individuals tested per index case, assessing the benefits for carriers and non-carriers and determine the frequency of five pathogenic variants in our cohort (NM_007294.4(*BRCA1*): c.3331_3334del and c.2037delinsCC; NM_000059.4(*BRCA2*): c.156_157insAlu; NM_000251.3(*MSH2*): c.388_389del; and NM_004360.5(*CDH1*): c.1901C>T), recognized as Portuguese founder variants.

Material and Methods: We conducted a retrospective analysis of clinical germline genetic testing data from individuals with a documented personal or family history of cancer, suggestive of a hereditary syndrome. The study cohort included 9922 patients who underwent testing between 2015 and 2025. Data were retrieved from internal databases, covering a broad spectrum of cancer syndromes (e.g., breast, ovarian,

pancreatic, etc.). The genes analyzed were selected based on known associations with increased cancer risk related to the patient's clinical presentation, personal history, and/or family history of cancer. Genetic variant classification was performed according to the American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics (ACMG)/Association for Molecular Pathology (AMP) and the ClinGen expert panels specifications guidelines.

Results: Among 9922 index cases, 919 (9.3%) harbored a pathogenic (P) or likely pathogenic (LP) variant. The remaining cases presented variants of unknown significance (VUS), likely benign (LB) or benign (B), and were excluded from downstream analyses. The 919 index cases with P/LP variants prompted cascade genetic testing in our laboratory for 1256 at-risk relatives (from 508 presumed different families), of whom 559 (44.5%) were identified as carriers of the familial P/LP variant, while 676 (53.8%) were non-carriers. Non-carrier family members were managed according to general population screening guidelines, while carriers benefited from intensified surveillance and/or risk-reducing interventions. The analyzed founder pathogenic variants accounted for 6.5% of all identified P/LP carriers, with NM_007294.4(BRCA1): c.3331_3334del being the most prevalent.

Conclusion: Our findings demonstrate the clinical and translational value of cascade testing in hereditary cancer, supporting its role in extending the benefits of genetic testing to families and optimizing resources. The significant contribution of founder pathogenic variants underscores the importance of population-specific data to design testing strategies and policy development in hereditary cancer care.

P18

Hereditary Tumor Registry for Precision Prevention in Lynch Syndrome

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Precision prevention in hereditary cancer syndromes requires comprehensive data integration to enable personalized risk assessment and surveillance strategies.

We analyzed data of Lynch Syndrome patients enrolled in our Hereditary Digestive Tumors Registry. All data were prospectively collected from patients who provided written informed consent (#INT12/18). We evaluated patient demographics, genetic profiles, surveillance outcomes, and family history data systematically collected in the registry.

The registry included 1,326 patients with genetically confirmed Lynch Syndrome enrolled from 1995 to 2025. Among these, 373 patients were excluded from the analyses as they had incomplete clinical data, so the final study group included 953 patients: 523 females (54.8%), mean age 54.4 years (± 16.8). Genetic distribution comprised MLH1 (N=279, 29.3%), MSH2 or EPCAM (N=370, 38.8%), MSH6 (N=198, 20.8%), and PMS2 (N=106, 11.1%) mutations. In total, 370 patients (38.8%) had a history of colorectal cancers, with 73 (7.6%) having metachronous colorectal cancers, 375 patients (39.3%) had a history of extracolonic neoplasms, and 146 patients (15.3%) had multiple extracolonic neoplasms. Additionally, 390 patients (40.9%) had no neoplasia history, at the time of last follow-up, requiring family history-guided surveillance protocols from dedicated physicians. Risk-reducing interventions included 146 (27.9%) prophylactic hysterectomies. Patients were under surveillance for a mean of 162 months (± 120). To date, 702 patients (73.6%) remain in active follow-up at our institution, while 130 patients (13.6%) are deceased.

Hereditary tumor registries are pivotal for precision prevention, providing systematic data collection necessary for personalized cancer risk management. Family history documentation within registry frameworks enables gene-specific surveillance timing and intensity optimization. In the last 30 years the registry-based precision prevention has facilitated early detection, appropriate risk-reducing interventions, and long-term follow-up, improving outcomes through individualized care strategies tailored to hereditary risk profiles and family history patterns.

P19

Decoding Familial Non-Medullary Thyroid Cancer: A Systematic Review of Its Demographic, Histological, and Genetic Dimensions

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Background: Non-syndromic familial non-medullary thyroid cancer (NSFNMTTC) presents significant challenges for both clinicians and researchers due to its enigmatic clinical and genetic profile. Unlike sporadic thyroid cancer, NSFNMTTC lacks a well-defined female-to-male incidence ratio, and pediatric cases are rarely reported. Currently, there are no histological markers that distinguish familial from sporadic cases. Moreover, the underlying genetic mechanisms of NSFNMTTC remain rather heterogenous and poorly understood.

Aims: This work aims to enhance the understanding of NSFNMTTC by synthesizing research conducted over the past 30 years, covering its epidemiological, clinical, and molecular features.

Methods: Our team conducted a systematic review on four databases (PubMed, Scopus, Embase, and Web of Science), encompassing studies published between January 1994 and December 2024. Included studies comprehended case reports, case series, case-control, and cross-sectional studies that provided demographic, pathological, and/or genetic data on affected kindreds or family members.

Results: Our search returned 3923 studies. After duplicate removal and application of exclusion criteria, 71 studies were included for data extraction, comprising 374 families. Mean age at diagnosis was 41.6 ± 9.4 years, approximately six years earlier

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than sporadic cases. PTC accounted for 88% of diagnoses. Overall female-to-male ratio was comparable to sporadic cases (2.9:1), however, the ratio decreased to 1.8:1 in pediatric cases. In this subgroup, a higher prevalence of malignant tumors was observed in females, whereas benign conditions were more commonly diagnosed in males. Incidence of these lesions was increased after puberty. Genetic alterations were reported in 67.6% of all studies, though methodologies varied substantially. Overall, over the past 30 years, 32 studies presented 133 novel germline mutations, and 8 presented 9 novel susceptibility loci for NSFNMTTC. Most studies presented with missing demographics and histological data.

Conclusions: Our study provides novel insights into key aspects of the disease that had not been clearly defined previously. Despite the large number of families, substantial variability among studies and methodologies was observed. Incomplete and inconsistent data also remain major obstacles to drawing robust conclusions. A more comprehensive characterization of the families, detailed histopathological descriptions of the tumors, and integrated genetic analyses will be essential for advancing our understanding of this disease.

P20

Smarter Delivery of Genetic Information in Hereditary Cancer Through Digital Tools

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Medical genetics and genetic testing play an increasingly central role in the diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up of cancer patients. This has resulted in a growing demand for genetic counselling and necessitates efficient, safe, and patient-centered approaches. To meet this demand, we have developed two digital genetic information tools to serve as valuable supplements to traditional genetic counselling.

1. ROSA – an AI based app, chatbot, providing genetic information to individuals undergoing testing for hereditary breast and ovarian cancer.

2. A digital education and self-management learning tool for patients with pathogenic variants in the BRCA genes. Both tools were developed using a participatory design approach, including iterative development and user testing.

The Rosa chatbot was evaluated through qualitative interviews among individuals at increased genetic risk, newly diagnosed patients with breast or ovarian cancer, and healthcare professionals.

The chatbot was perceived as accessible, useful, and trustworthy. However, both patients and healthcare professionals expressed concerns about missing important information. The chatbot has the potential to increase efficiency in genetic counselling but should be used as a supplement to, not a replacement for, healthcare professionals.

The digital education and self-management tool contain eight distinct modules. Each module includes video segments,

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animations, and written materials featuring information provided by gynaecologists, breast surgeons, a psychologist, and a sexologist. In addition, an introductory module is available, offering an overview of inheritance patterns and the associated risks of relevant cancer types.

AI based chatbots and digital learning tools may enhance patient support during genetic testing and follow-up and has the potential to increase efficiency in genetic counselling but should be used as a supplement to, not a replacement for, healthcare professionals.

P21

MicroRNAs as Potential Biomarkers for Endometrial Cancer Risk in Endometriosis

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Endometriosis is a chronic inflammatory disease affecting around 10% of women at reproductive age, defined by the presence of endometrial tissue outside the uterine cavity. Endometriotic cells display reminiscent hallmarks of malignancy, including deregulated proliferation, resistance to apoptosis, chronic inflammation, and invasive potential. In line with this, epidemiological evidence has shown an increased incidence of estrogen-dependent endometrial and ovarian cancers in patients with endometriosis. In addition, endometrial cancer stems from malignant transformation of endometrium cells and is the fourth most common cancer in women and the leading gynaecological malignancy in developed countries, with more than 380,000 new cases/year. MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are emerging as key post-transcriptional regulators of disease progression, acting as tumor suppressors or, conversely, oncogenic miRNAs (oncomiRs).

Characterizing miRNA dysregulation in endometriotic tissue may provide insights into early molecular alterations associated with malignant potential and identify biomarkers for cancer risk stratification. Human eutopic (EU) endometrium from patients (n=9) and ectopic (EC) endometriotic lesions (n=8) were assessed from patients submitted to laparoscopic procedures at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of the Unidade Local de Saúde de São João (ULSSJ) - Porto. Control eutopic endometrium (n=6) was harvested from patients submitted to myoma excision surgeries. Through

formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded tissue samples, a panel of candidate miRNAs (miR-1, miR-9, miR-16, miR-21, miR-30a, miR-125b, miR-139, miR-320a) was profiled by RT-PCR. EC tissue showed significantly higher expression of miR-125b ($p=0.060$; $p=0.008$) and miR-139 ($p=0.008$; $p=0.002$), compared with control and EU, respectively, with miR-320a showing a similar trend.

These findings suggest the suppression of apoptotic pathways and enhanced migratory capacity. Conversely, the tumor suppressor miR-30a was consistently downregulated in endometriotic tissue (EU: $p=0.027$; EC: $p=0.030$), and miR-16 showed a tendency for reduced expression in EC, consistent with increased proliferation, angiogenesis, and inflammation. Interestingly, miR-1, a tumour suppressor, was instead elevated in EC, possibly reflecting a compensatory response. Classical oncomiRs miR-9 and miR-21 showed no significant changes.

Overall, our results reveal a miRNA signature in endometriosis, particularly in EC, that mirrors neoplastic features and supports the notion of malignant potential in this tissue, highlighting the need to extend analysis to endometrial cancer samples.

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P22

Signaling pathways mediating lymphoma cell apoptosis triggered by PSGL-1 antibody binding

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Lymphomas are a heterogeneous group of diseases that originate from T, B or natural killer cells. Lymphoma treatment is based on chemotherapy, radiotherapy and monoclonal antibodies (mAb) or other immunotherapies. The P-selectin glycoprotein ligand-1 (PSGL-1) is a transmembrane protein on immune cells that acts as a docking site for selectins on blood vessel walls, initiating the rolling and adhesion of white blood cells to inflamed tissues acting as a target in cancer and autoimmune research.

This protein is also expressed at the surface of hematological malignant cells and has been shown to have a pro-oncogenic role in multiple myeloma and lymphoma. Our group found that PSGL-1 was expressed in both T and B cell-derived lymphoma cell lines. For most lymphoma cell lines, in vitro targeting with a PL-1 mAb that recognizes the PSGL-1 N-terminal extracellular region and blocks functional interactions with selectins, resulted in reduced cell viability due apoptosis. The PL-1 mAb pro-apoptotic activity was shown to be dose-dependent and linked to increased ERK kinase phosphorylation and to be dependent on the MAP kinase signaling pathway.

To understand how PSGL-1 antibody ligation induces apoptosis, we aim to determine the signaling pathways required for this activity. For this, we will use specific inhibitors inhibitors MAPK, PI3K and SYK kinase pathways and detect the phosphorylated

proteins by western blotting. Further we will determine if Venetoclax and Ibrutinib, specific Bcl2 and BTK inhibitors, are involved in cell line apoptosis. Altogether, we will uncover the specific apoptosis signaling pathways triggered by PSGL-1 in lymphoma cells.

P23

The power of glycans in disseminated tumor cell biology: impact in cancer dormancy and metastasis

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Metastasis is the leading cause of cancer-related mortality. Once seeded in distant organs, metastatic cancer cells can persist as dormant disseminated tumour cells (DTCs) for months to years, even after the eradication of the primary tumor. Glycosylation – a ubiquitous post-translational modification – promotes several facets of cancer progression, including immune evasion (Pinho & Reis, 2015, Nat Rev Cancer). However, it remains unclear how glycosylation shapes immune surveillance during indolent phases of metastasis, particularly during the induction, maintenance and exit from dormancy.

To address this gap, we sought to identify metastasis-associated glycotranscriptomic signatures by analysing single-cell RNA sequencing data from human liver metastases originating from distinct primary tumours (breast and pancreatic cancer). In parallel, immunocompetent animal models of metastatic dormancy are being leveraged to validate candidate glycosylation programmes. Using models that recapitulate breast cancer DTC dormancy in the liver (Correia et al., 2021, Nature), we will test whether glycosylation influences dormant DTC survival and metastatic outgrowth. We will also determine whether engagement of glycan-binding proteins (GBPs) expressed by resident immune populations (including Kupffer and natural killer cells) modulates their ability to restrain the dormancy-to-proliferation transition.

Preliminary data indicate that metastatic cancer cells upregulate sialyltransferase expression relative to their tumor of origin. Moreover, GBP-high macrophages accumulate in liver metastases and display pro-tumoural transcriptional

programmes, suggesting that GBP expression may stratify macrophage functionality in human metastasis. Ongoing work is dedicated to validating these findings in an independent cohort and probing a putative glycan-GBP axis in dormant metastasis.

Overall, we aim to determine how glycans enable metastatic cancer cells to persist and, later on, to form macrometastases. By uncovering a novel layer of immune escape, we seek to leverage glycosylation to potentiate immune surveillance and prevent metastatic relapse.

P24

Tumor organoid-based 3D models to uncover predictive biomarkers for breast cancer progression

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Breast cancer (BC) is the most common cancer in women and, despite continuous research, its relatively high mortality due to metastasis and disease progression remains a huge concern. Prognosis varies by subtype: Luminal A and B, HER2-overexpression and Triple-Negative (TN), which includes Basal-like and Claudin-low subtypes. HER2+ and TN subtypes present the worst outcomes. Recent advances in research highlight the importance in identifying predictive biomarkers of metastasis as a crucial point in order to improve BC prognosis.

While traditional 2D models fail to replicate the complexity of the tumor microenvironment, 3D tumor-derived organoid cultures mimic better the *in vivo* conditions. Therefore, in this work, we aimed to develop and optimize a protocol for generating BC organoids from xenograft tumors representing different BC subtypes and then adapt the method for patient samples. To establish BC organoids, we conducted a pre-clinical study in which BC cell lines representative of each subtype (MCF-7/Az and T47D for Luminal A; BT474 for Luminal B; SKBR3 and MDA-IBC-3 for HER2-overexpressed; BT20 and MDA-MB-468 for Basal-like; and MDA-MB-231 and SUM149PT for Claudin-low) were cultured and injected into immunosuppressed female N: NIH(S)II-nu/nu mice. Upon tumor growth, they were excised and processed to establish tumor-derived organoid cultures. A non-tumorigenic human cell line (MCF10A) was used as a control for healthy tissue, as well as samples from mice's normal breast. After its successful

optimization, we applied this protocol to primary breast tumor samples obtained by IPO-Porto to generate patient-derived organoids (PDOs). Both cell line-derived and patient-derived tumor organoid cultures exhibited success rates consistent with the literature (~70% for cell line-derived and ~55% for patient-derived), although there remains room for further improvement and optimization. In addition, these organoids retained the same histological profile as their original tumors, reinforcing their value as a model to study metastatic predictive biomarkers.

While further downstream analyses are ongoing, this study lays the groundwork for future research. Organoid cultures provide a more biologically relevant model for studying tumor biology, compared to traditional 2D models. Their successful establishment in this study opens new opportunities to explore BC progression and improve metastatic research. This advancement may ultimately lead to improved early detection and treatment of metastasis, contributing to a better prognosis for breast cancer patients.

P25

Beyond European Genomes: Deciphering Colorectal Cancer Susceptibility in a Highly Admixed Brazilian Cohort

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Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the most common cancers and the second leading cause of cancer-related death worldwide. Despite advances in prevention and treatment strategies, the CRC burden continues to rise, driven mainly by population aging and the adoption of Westernized lifestyles. In recent years, genome-wide association studies (GWAS) have revolutionized the genetic landscape of CRC, in its diverse forms, uncovering multiple common susceptibility variants. However, most of these GWASs were conducted in European-ancestry populations, leaving admixed populations, such as those in Brazil, significantly underrepresented. Given the potential differences in genetic architecture between Europeans and admixed populations, this study aims to conduct a GWAS on risk of sporadic CRC in a Brazilian cohort.

A total of 1458 CRC patients (mean age: 55 years) and 2555 cancer-free controls (mean age: 54 years) were included. Participants represent all five regions of Brazil, with the Southeast predominating (53%), due to Barretos Cancer Hospital location. DNA genotyping was performed using the

850K Axiom™ Precision Medicine Diversity Array, covering 855,943 pan-ethnic variants. The genotyped data underwent array-level quality control (QC) using the Applied Biosystems™ Axiom™ Analysis Suite, followed by single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) and sample-level QC in PLINK. Population structure was assessed via Multidimensional Scaling (MDS) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) against a merged reference panel comprising the 1000 Genomes Project and Human Genome Diversity Project (HGDP) datasets. Ancestry estimation was conducted using ADMIXTURE. Association testing was performed using logistic regression adjusted for population stratification, applying a genome-wide significance threshold of $P < 5 \times 10^{-8}$.

After all the standard QC procedures, the final dataset comprised 519,155 SNPs and 3596 individuals (1357 cases and 2239 controls). Population structure analysis confirmed a highly genetically admixed cohort with predominant European ancestry, followed by African, Native American, and lastly, East Asian components. The association analysis identified 10 genome-wide significant variants ($P < 5 \times 10^{-8}$), located on chromosomes 1, 2, 6, 11, 15, and 20. Notably, two missense variants were identified: rs41330148 in the *MUC2* (11:1099990; OR=3.763; $P=1.21e-8$) and rs115737063 in the *RGL2* (6:33296167; OR=3.270; $P=2.75e-8$) genes, suggesting a direct functional impact on CRC susceptibility.

In conclusion, this is the largest GWAS assessing sporadic CRC risk in the Brazilian population to date. It suggests 10 potential risk *loci*, including likely functional missense variants in *MUC2* and *RGL2*. Future work will focus on refining these signals through genotype imputation and comprehensive post-GWAS functional analyses to validate their role in CRC susceptibility.

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P26

Genomic Characterization of Sporadic Colorectal Cancer in the Minho Region: A Pilot Genome-Wide Association Study

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Colorectal cancer (CRC) represents a major public health challenge in Portugal, where it stands as the second most common cancer and the second leading cause of cancer-related mortality. Sporadic CRC accounts for 70-80% of all cases and is a multifactorial disease driven by the interplay between genetic architecture and environmental exposures. Crucially, the rising incidence in Portugal is increasingly linked to lifestyle shifts, particularly the transition to more westernized dietary habits. Despite the exponential growth of genome-wide association studies (GWAS) for CRC, these have primarily aggregated broad European populations, often leaving specific Southern European cohorts, such as the Portuguese, underrepresented. Therefore, this study aims to conduct a preliminary GWAS of sporadic CRC in the Portuguese population to characterize its genetic profile and evaluate the feasibility of genomic risk assessment in this specific population.

A total of 149 participants (114 sporadic CRC cases and 35 cancer-free controls, 64 females and 85 males) were recruited at ULSAM and ULSAAVE. Eligibility criteria required a confirmed diagnosis of CRC, excluding familial CRC syndromes

and other malignancies. Genotyping was performed using the 850K Axiom™ Precision Medicine Diversity Array, which covers 855,943 pan-ethnic variants. Data underwent standard quality control (QC) procedures, namely array-level QC using the Applied Biosystems™ Axiom™ Analysis Suite, followed by single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) and sample-level QC in PLINK. Population structure was evaluated via multidimensional scaling (MDS) against a reference panel based on the 1000 Genomes Project Dataset, and ancestry analysis was conducted using ADMIXTURE. Association testing was performed using logistic regression, applying a study-specific significance threshold of $P < 1.6 \times 10^{-7}$.

Post-QC, the final dataset included 108 sporadic CRC cases, 34 controls, and 309,984 variants. MDS analysis confirmed that our Portuguese cohort is genetically homogenous and aligned with European populations. ADMIXTURE results revealed that European ancestry is the predominant component, followed by a consistent minor African ancestry signal, reflecting the region's specific demographic history. Due to sample size limitations and case-control imbalance, no variant reached genome-wide significance. However, three suggestive variants ($P < 10^{-5}$) were identified: rs799459 (OR=0.1974; $P=4.75e^{-7}$) and rs712316 (OR=0.1634; $P=9.90e^{-7}$) at the *SRP54/SRP54-AS1* locus on chromosome 14, and rs3107034 (OR=4.5560; $P=2.11e^{-6}$) in *CFAP418-AS1* on chromosome 8.

In conclusion, this pilot study demonstrates the feasibility of conducting genomic risk assessment of sporadic CRC in the Portuguese population of the Minho region. As recruitment is ongoing, future analyses will be conducted in a larger, more balanced cohort to fully validate these signals and refine the genetic risk profile of CRC in Portugal.

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THOR Methylation signatures in liquid biopsies for early breast cancer detection

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Breast Cancer (BC) is the leading cause of cancer-related death among women worldwide. The incidence of BC in young women (<40 years old) is rising, revealing the need to develop and implement new strategies for BC diagnosis beyond current imaging-based approaches. Telomerase reactivation through upregulation of human Telomerase Reverse Transcriptase (*hTERT*) gene occurs in most BC cases, leading the cancer cells achieve self-renewal capacity and supporting tumor progression. One mechanism responsible for *hTERT* upregulation is the hypermethylation of a specific region within the *hTERT* promoter, called TERT Hypermethylated Oncological Region (THOR). Our group showed that THOR is significantly hypermethylated in malignant breast tissue when compared to benign tissue (40.23% vs. 12.81%). Liquid biopsy is a minimally invasive approach that provides real-time information about tumor status, particularly through circulating cell-free DNA analysis. We aim to identify BC-specific THOR methylation signatures for prospective use as liquid biopsy-based biomarkers to detect BC through a blood sample.

To achieve our goal, we established a discovery cohort comprising 59 BC tissue samples, 60 healthy breast tissue

samples, and 47 blood samples from healthy individuals. Genomic DNA underwent bisulfite treatment, PCR amplification and Illumina MiSeq sequencing. Raw methylation data was processed through a bioinformatic pipeline including quality control, alignment, incomplete bisulfite conversion filtering, methylation extraction, and complete reads selection. To identify the BC-specific THOR methylation signatures, we developed a three-step algorithm: read count normalization, Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney statistical testing ($p < 0.05$), and selection of THOR methylation signatures detected in at least 50% of BC samples but absent in at least 80% of healthy samples.

From the discovery cohort analysis, we found that THOR is hypermethylated in BC tissue in comparison with the healthy breast tissue and healthy blood (Kruskal-Wallis $p < 0.0001$). Moreover, we have identified 3 panels of 12, 6, and 10 THOR methylation patterns with high prevalence in BC tissue samples, but rare in the negative controls (specificity > 0.85 , sensitivity > 0.80).

Our findings underscore the potential of THOR methylation signatures to be used as sensitive and specific biomarkers for breast cancer detection.

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Antibody blockade of the PSGL-1 glycoprotein impairs non-Hodgkin B-cell lymphoma progression and enhances T-cell responses

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Non-Hodgkin B-cell lymphomas are a heterogeneous group of hematologic neoplasms resulting from the clonal proliferation of B cells. Despite advances in immunotherapy and CAR-T therapy, most non-Hodgkin lymphomas remain unresponsive to immune checkpoint inhibitors. In this context, there is a need to develop innovative immunomodulatory approaches to improve the management of patients with lymphoma. The P-selectin glycoprotein ligand-1 (PSGL-1) is a transmembrane glycoprotein recently described as a potential immune checkpoint that negatively regulates T-cell function and promotes T-cell exhaustion in murine cancer models. In this study, we investigated the therapeutic potential of PSGL-1 antibody targeting in B-cell lymphoma.

Our results demonstrated that PSGL-1 blockade in immunocompetent mouse models with B-cell lymphoma results in decreased tumor progression as well as the recruitment and activation of T cells (1). Next, we aimed to decipher the mechanism of action of anti-PSGL-1 treatment and explore its effect on the tumor microenvironment in B-cell lymphomas. Preliminary results showed that PSGL-1 is expressed in several immune populations of the lymphoma microenvironment, not only in the mouse model but also in diffuse large B-cell lymphoma (DLBCL) patients. Simultaneously, bioinformatic analysis of scRNA-seq data from four DLBCL patients revealed a strong correlation between *SELPLG* (gene which encodes PSGL-1) and *VISTA* (V-domain Ig suppressor of T-cell activation). VISTA, encoded by the

VSIR gene, has recently been identified as a ligand of PSGL-1 in the acidic tumor microenvironment. Moreover, we found that SELPLG expression is predominant in the T-cell lineage, whereas VSIR is mainly expressed in macrophages. We hypothesize that the interaction between PSGL-1 and VISTA in these immune populations may contribute to the mechanisms of immunosuppression.

Since PSGL-1 was highly expressed in lymphoma-infiltrating T cells, we assessed whether PSGL-1 antibody blockade could hinder lymphoma progression in their absence. In fact, PSGL-1 targeting of lymphoma-bearing T cell-deficient mice did not hinder tumor progression. These findings indicate that T cells are the key mediators of the anti-PSGL-1 therapeutic effect and reinforce the notion that PSGL-1 plays a crucial role in modulating the immune response in B-cell lymphomas, highlighting it as a promising therapeutic target. Further studies will provide new insights for the development of more effective immunotherapeutic strategies against lymphoma.

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P29

Unveiling and characterizing mechanisms of intercellular communication mediating drug resistance in non-small cell lung cancer

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Targeted cancer therapies have significantly improved the treatment of EGFR-driven non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) [1, 2]. However, the development of resistance that inevitability occurs remains a major clinical challenge and a leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide [3]. Despite being the triggering event, our group observed that therapy-resistant mutations are present only in a subset of relapsing tumor cells. These findings challenge the classical model of resistance based exclusively on cell division and selection of mutated cells and supports a more dynamic model involving intercellular communication.

We used the human H1975 EGFR^{p.L858R}/EGFR^{p.T790M} Erlotinib-resistant and HCC827 EGFR^{p.delE746-A750} Erlotinib-sensitive lung cancer cell lines both *in vitro* and in a co-inoculation immunodeficient C57BL/6^[-/-]; Il2rg^[-/-] mouse model to study the transcriptomic, proteomic and epigenetic profile of therapy sensitive cells before and after development of resistance [4]. This approach allowed us to assess how signals emitted by resistant cells modulate the emergence and persistence of a stable resistant phenotype in initially sensitive cells. To further characterize the nature of the intercellular communication established between therapy-resistant and therapy-sensitive

cells that lead to the acquisition of mutation-independent resistance to EGFR-TKIs, EVs from these cell lines will be extracted and characterized [5].

Our results demonstrate that exposure to conditioned medium from resistant cells, as well as co-inoculation of both therapy-sensitive and therapy-resistant cells *in vivo* leads to a faster and more stable resistance phenotype. The acquisition of resistance is accompanied by extensive transcriptomic reprogramming, including enrichment of the endocytosis pathway, specifically through Caveolin-1 overexpression, which was further validated in human samples. The analysis of the downstream pathway identified PI3K/AKT signaling as a key mediator of resistance, whose pharmacological inhibition can restore sensitivity to therapy. Additionally, immunohistochemical staining of human samples validated pAKT overexpression in therapy-resistant tumors. Furthermore, epigenetic profiling revealed that the resistance phenotype is associated with a shift towards a more hypomethylated profile characterized by the overexpression of epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT), PI3K/AKT and MAPK related genes.

Collectively, our findings support a model in which resistance to targeted therapy can arise from the reprogramming of therapy-sensitive cells through paracrine signaling, highlighting the importance of tumor cell interactions in the spread of the resistance phenotype. Targeting intercellular communication networks may therefore represent a promising strategy to overcome therapeutic resistance in NSCLC.

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P30

Prognostic and Clinicopathological Significance of miR-125a, miR-155, and miR-579 Expression in Cutaneous Melanoma

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Introduction: Cutaneous melanoma (CM) is a highly aggressive and heterogeneous malignancy, characterized by significant recurrence and metastasis rates. It harbors high mutation rates and significant heterogeneity, that leads to frequent treatment resistance and poor prognosis in advanced stages. While mutations in *BRAF*, *NRAS*, and the *TERT* promoter (*TERTp*) are well-established drivers, microRNAs (miRNAs) have emerged as essential regulators of cancer hallmarks and potential biomarkers. This study aimed to evaluate the expression levels of three miRNAs, miR-125a, miR-155, and miR-579, in CM patients and determine their correlation with patients clinicopathological data and the mutational status of key oncogenes.

Materials and Methods: RNA and DNA were extracted from 55 formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue samples. Quantitative PCR (qPCR) was performed to assess miRNA expression levels, using miR-16 as an endogenous control for normalization. Also, mutational status of *BRAF*, *NRAS*, and *TERTp* was determined by PCR and Sanger sequencing. Statistical analyses were performed to correlate miRNA expression with patient clinicopathological features, therapy response, outcomes and the mutational status of the tumors. Results: miR-125a was significantly upregulated in melanoma samples compared to adjacent tissue. Patients with high miR-125a expression exhibited a trend toward lower overall survival

(OS), and appeared to have shorter progression-free survival (PFS). Conversely, high levels of miR-155 were significantly associated with prolonged OS, reinforcing its role as a favorable prognostic indicator in this cohort. miR-579 showed a significant association with Clark level, where higher levels were found in more advanced invasion stages. Furthermore, high miR-579 expression was significantly linked to improved PFS, and a trend toward a lower risk of disease progression. Regarding correlations between the three miRNAs, a tendency for a positive connection was observed between miR-125a and miR-155. Importantly, no statistically significant correlations were found between the expression levels of these three miRNAs and therapy response, and also with the mutational status of *BRAF*, *NRAS*, and *TERT*_p in this series.

Conclusion: The findings suggest that miR-155 and miR-579 may function as positive prognostic biomarkers, as their high expression is associated with increased survival. In contrast, miR-125a seems to behave as a potential oncogenic factor linked to tumor progression and higher mortality risk. These results highlight the potential of miRNA expression profiling to complement standard molecular characterization, thereby enhancing prognostic prediction and clinical management in cutaneous melanoma patients.

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The added value of CNVs detection in multigene panel testing: A GENTURIS Case Report

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Introduction: Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer (HBOC) syndrome is one of the most prevalent genetic tumour-risk syndromes (GENTURIS), accounting for approximately 5-10% of all breast cancer cases. It is classically associated with pathogenic and likely pathogenic germline variants (PVs/LPVs) in *BRCA1* and *BRCA2*. However, the increasing implementation of multigene panel testing, enabling the simultaneous analysis of additional HBOC-associated susceptibility genes (e.g. *PALB2*, *ATM* and *CHEK2*), together with the detection of both single nucleotide variants (SNVs) and copy number variants (CNVs), has substantially improved diagnostic yield and boosted the resolution of previously unsolved hereditary cancer cases in a cost-effective manner.

Herein, we report a clinical case of HBOC identified through multigene panel sequencing, highlighting the diagnostic workflow and emphasizing the clinical utility and implications of multigene testing approaches capable of detecting both SNVs and CNVs concurrently.

Methodology: A woman in her 40s with breast cancer and a strong family history suggestive of HBOC underwent germline multigene panel testing. DNA from peripheral blood leukocytes was analyzed using the Hereditary Plus OncoKitDx panel (Health in Code S.L.), targeting 101 hereditary cancer-predisposition genes. Interpretation prioritized the HBOC-specific subpanel of 25 genes. Variants filtering, visualization and classification, according to ACMG guidelines, were performed using Health in Code's bioinformatics platform, Data Genomics.

Results: Two PVs were identified in the patient: one heterozygous small deletion and one heterozygous CNV.

The small deletion, NM_000051.3:c.8251_8254del, is a frameshift variant located in exon 56 of the *ATM* gene, predicted to result in a premature stop codon (NP_000042.3:p.Thr2751Serfs*54). This variant was classified as pathogenic based on the ACMG criteria PVS1 (predicted loss of function), PM2_Supporting (low population frequency in gnomAD), PM3 (detected in trans with another PV in the same gene) and PP5 (reported as pathogenic in ClinVar, HGMD and LOVD).

Additionally, a heterozygous CNV loss of function deletion of exons 7 to 11 of *PALB2* was detected (NM_024675.3:c.(2586+1_2587-1)_(3201+1_3202-1)del). This variant fulfilled the ACMG criteria PM4_Strong (in-frame deletion affecting >10% of the protein), PM2_Supporting, PS1 (supporting evidence from shorter in-frame PVs) and PP5, and was therefore also classified as pathogenic.

Conclusion: This case highlights the clinical value of multigene panel testing approaches capable of detecting both SNVs and CNVs to achieve an accurate molecular diagnosis and guide appropriate clinical management. Furthermore, the identification of concurrent PVs in moderate- to high-penetrance susceptibility genes may indicate that secondary variants could act as genetic modifiers, potentially increasing cancer penetrance and age of onset in GENTURIS.

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Hybrid Extracellular Vesicle-Lipoplex Platforms for patient-centred therapies

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Glioblastoma (GBM) is one of the most aggressive types of brain tumors. The standard therapy of surgical resection, followed by radiotherapy and chemotherapy with temozolomide, is inefficient, and the overall survival rarely passes 15 months. Developing targeted therapies for GBM faces challenges, including the invasive growth of the tumor, which does not allow for complete surgical resection, the blood-brain barrier (BBB), and resistance to radio- and chemotherapy. According to several clinical studies, patient survival is often related to the molecular and genetic properties of the tumor, which are of interest to the general medical community. No robust panel of genes has yet been established to reliably predict therapeutic response.

In this context, transcription factors such as Forkhead box (FOX) M1 and FOXO3a have been widely studied for their roles in regulating cellular processes involved in tumor progression. Their involvement in pathways associated with therapy resistance has been reported in preclinical models, making them suitable targets for gene silencing approaches aimed at modulating resistance-related mechanisms rather than disease-specific mutations.

Silencing by small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) has demonstrated extensive good results in treating several diseases. However, these molecules are prone to degradation, requiring an efficient delivery vector. Cationic liposomes were initially developed as nonviral vectors but proved cytotoxic, thus leading to the development of anionic lipoplexes with cofactors (e.g., Ca²⁺). Along with that, extracellular vehicles (EVs) have emerged as nanocarriers for targeted therapies

due to their ability to cross the BBB, good biocompatibility, low toxicity, and intrinsic cell-targeting capabilities. However, one of the main limitations is their restricted cargo capacity. Here, we propose a hybrid nanosystem combining tumor cell-derived EVs with siRNA-loaded anionic lipoplexes targeting FOXM1 and FOXO3a. This strategy aims to retain the targeting ability of EVs while benefiting from the higher cargo capacity and reduced toxicity of anionic lipoplexes, ultimately enhancing the chemosensitivity of tumor cells. EVs were isolated from U87 cell line by differential ultracentrifugation, and siRNA-loaded lipoplexes were produced using microfluidics. Hybrids were generated through freeze-thaw cycles followed by extrusion and characterized in terms of size, particle concentration, surface charge, morphology, and encapsulation efficiency. Cell viability assays were performed to assess the ability of the hybrids to enhance TMZ sensitivity in tumor cell lines.

Overall, the results demonstrate enhanced chemosensitivity, supporting hybrids targeting FOXM1 and FOXO3a as a promising strategy to improve therapeutic response. Importantly, the use of EVs that can be derived from the patient introduces a patient-centered dimension, enabling the potential for targeted siRNA delivery.

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Development and Validation of Genetic Tools to Monitor Endosomal Recycling Dynamics in Invasive Triple-Negative Breast Cancer

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Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) is a highly aggressive subtype with limited targeted therapies and high metastatic potential. Increasing evidence highlights the tumor microenvironment as a critical driver of progression, particularly the role of extracellular matrix (ECM) stiffness. High mammographic density, a clinical correlate of increased ECM stiffness, is strongly associated with TNBC risk and promotes cancer cell invasion. Mechanistically, these mechanical cues are integrated into the cell via mechanosensitive regulators, which may modulate intracellular trafficking to enable cells to adapt to their environment.

In particular, the endosomal sorting and recycling (ESR) pathway governs the trafficking of adhesion molecules and growth factor receptors, a process essential for cell migration and invasion. Previous research from our laboratory has demonstrated that the Feline sarcoma-related (FER) kinase, expressed at high levels in one-third of TNBC patients, is a key regulator of this process. We have shown that FER depletion leads to the collapse of Rab4-positive fast-recycling tubules and the concomitant accumulation of abnormal Rab11-positive slow-recycling vesicles, suggesting that FER maintains the ESR efficiency required for invasion.

Here, we hypothesize that TNBC invasiveness is sustained by a stiffness-dependent ESR shift favoring Rab4-dependent fast recycling over Rab11-dependent slow recycling. As the initial phase of a broader investigation, this project aims to

generate and validate fluorescent genetic tools to monitor ESR dynamics in real time within TNBC models. Lentiviral constructs encoding Rab4-mCherry and Rab11-GFP were designed as markers for fast and slow recycling routes, respectively. These tools are being introduced into parental MDA-MB-231 (MM231) cells, MM231-FER iKD cells (bearing doxycycline-inducible FER knockdown), and Patient-Derived Xenograft Organoids. The MM231-FER iKD model will confirm the accuracy of the fluorescent tags by reporting the expected structural shifts upon FER depletion.

Stable cell populations were sorted by FACS. Ongoing validation efforts include protein-expression assessment by Western blot and cell-viability evaluation through flow cytometry (Propidium Iodide). Furthermore, immunofluorescence microscopy will be performed to validate that the tagged proteins maintain the same subcellular localization and spatial-distribution patterns as their endogenous counterparts. High-resolution live-cell confocal imaging will be performed to track the localization and movement of recycling vesicles.

The development of these models will enable investigation into how mechanical cues from the ECM reshape ESR activity to promote TNBC progression. Ultimately, this work will provide robust organotypic models to identify new biomarkers and therapeutic targets linked to ECM-induced metastasis.

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Inflammatory microRNA Profiles in Osteosarcoma–Osteoclast Crosstalk

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Osteosarcoma (OS) is the most common primary malignant bone tumor, accounting for approximately 20-40% of all diagnosed bone cancers, with a predominant incidence in children and adolescents. While most cases arise sporadically, several cancer-predisposing syndromes have been associated with OS, and pathogenic or probably pathogenic germline mutations have been identified in 18% to 28% of patients. Complete surgical resection and chemotherapy remain the cornerstone of OS treatment. However, its effectiveness is markedly reduced in metastatic or recurrent cases, where survival rates decrease to 20%.

A major challenge in OS treatment is its complex and dynamic microenvironment, characterized by bidirectional communication between tumor cells and surrounding bone components, including osteoclasts (OCs; bone-resorbing specialized cells), which promote tumor progression through paracrine signaling and direct matrix-cell interactions. Our group has previously demonstrated that microRNAs (miRNAs) could modulate OCs differentiation and activity and could also change cellular inflammatory profiles. Building on these findings, this study aims to investigate the OS-OCs communication and explore the potential role of TNF- α . To this end, we characterized the expression of panels of inflammatory miRNAs during OCs differentiation and across OS cell lines (SAOS-2, 143-B, MG-63, U2OS), compared with a non-malignant osteoblast cell line (hFOB1.19), and optimized an OS-OCs co-culture system. Expression of key genes (TNF- α , RANKL, DLEU1, DLEU2) and ELISA assays for RANKL and TNF- α were performed. Based on evidence

implicating TNF- α in osteoclastogenesis, two experimental approaches were designed to evaluate its role using standard and sub-optimal concentrations of RANKL. Our results showed minimal involvement of TNF- α in regulating the selected miRNAs (miRNA-21, miRNA-29c, miRNA-125a, miRNA-146a, miRNA-155, miRNA-200c, miRNA-223, and miRNA-342), except for miR-155, which was upregulated. ELISA assays revealed no detectable expression of either RANKL or TNF- α in any OS cell line, consistent with the gene expression data. MiRNAs expression levels did not display a consistent pattern across OS cell lines. Specifically, miRNA-146a, miRNA-125a, and miRNA-29c were upregulated in MG-63, SAOS-2, and U2OS, respectively, whereas miRNA-155 was downregulated in SAOS-2 and U2OS, compared with hFOB1.19 osteoblasts. Notably, OCs differentiation was associated with increased expression of miR-21, miR-146a, and miR-155, together with reduced expression of miR-16 (SAOS-2, U2OS, 143-B, MG-63), miR-15a (SAOS-2, U2OS, 143-B), and DLEU1/2 in OS cell lines. Similar expression patterns were also observed during OCs differentiation. Future studies will focus on modulating these targets in an OS-OCs co-culture model to assess their functional relevance.

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High-grade glioma in a pediatric patient with NF1: limits of histology and relevance of molecular classification and MRI surveillance

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Neurofibromatosis type 1 (NF1) is associated with an increased risk of central nervous system (CNS) tumors, predominantly low-grade gliomas (LGGs). Malignant transformation is rare, particularly in pediatric patients, and may be underestimated when relying on histology alone. Integrated molecular diagnostics and systematic radiological surveillance are therefore essential for accurate tumor classification and clinical management. We report the case of a 14-year-old girl with NF1 carrying a germline heterozygous Neurofibromin 1 (NF1) pathogenic variant c.7843C>T (p.Gln2615Ter), with a negative family history for cancer and delayed neurodevelopment. Brain MRI, performed for chronic headache, revealed a left nucleocapsular lesion involving the caudate nucleus, lentiform nucleus, and internal capsule, with caudal extension to the diencephalon and involvement of the retrochiasmatic optic tract, associated with midline shift. Stereotactic biopsy showed histological features consistent with an LGG within the spectrum of NF1-associated tumors, without classical

characteristics of pilocytic astrocytoma. However, DNA methylation profiling subsequently classified the lesion within the high-grade glioma (HGG) cluster, subgroup B.

Molecular analysis of the tumor revealed two NF1 mutations: p.Gln2636*, corresponding to the germline pathogenic variant, and p.Arg385Leufs*2, representing the somatic second hit, both classified as Tier IB, with allele frequencies of 50% and 31%, respectively. No CDKN2A deletion was detected, and tumor mutational burden was 7. Surgical debulking was proposed but declined. Follow-up MRI at seven months demonstrated a mild increase in tumor thickness, predominantly at the level of the caudate head. Based on the molecular classification and the underlying genetic condition, a targeted therapeutic approach with combined MEK and PARP inhibitors was initiated. This case highlights the limitations of relying on histology alone in NF1-associated gliomas and underscores the critical role of molecular profiling in identifying high-grade biology. Furthermore, it reinforces the importance of systematic brain MRI surveillance in NF1 patients, as undiagnosed LGGs may harbor or evolve toward aggressive molecular phenotypes, with significant implications for therapy.

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Gastrointestinal stromal tumours in carriers of rare germline variants in *KIT*/*PDGFRA*: an update in prevalence and clinical manifestations

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Heritable gastrointestinal stromal tumors (GISTs) are rare (<5% of all GIST cases) and often underdiagnosed. Current data hints towards germline variants in *KIT* and *PDGFA* as likely predisposing factors in this condition, but the literature is scarce. *KIT* germline variant carriers either develop small, multifocal GISTs at a young age or remain lifelong asymptomatic. Multifocal GISTs increase the risk of complications like bleeding or perforation, increasing morbidity. Occasionally, *KIT* germline variant carriers present with cutaneous hyperpigmentation and/or mast cell abnormalities, highlighting these benign conditions as a proxy of genetic susceptibility.

We aimed at systematically review the literature to identify genotype-phenotype correlations in *KIT* and *PDGFR* carrier individuals and families. For that, we conducted a

literature search in PubMed and Google Scholar with the terms "germline mutation" or "germline variant" and "GIST," to identify publications related to KIT and PDGFRA germline predisposition, published until March 2025. We developed a GIST interface for the IT tool used in the Preventable project, to collect data from sporadic GIST before age 50, to infer the pathway of care of heritable GIST, and from cases from KIT carrier families to calculate healthcare costs with treatment and proactive cancer prevention.

We identified 53 publications reporting GISTs in 9 individuals without family history and 47 families carrying rare KIT germline variants, encompassing a total of 260 individuals. From these, 62.7% (163/260) individuals were diagnosed with GIST, with the youngest case diagnosed at 15 years (age range: 15-82 years). GISTs were particularly frequent (80.2%; 93/116) in the small intestine, and in 45.7% (53/116) of the patients GISTs occurred in multiple locations, namely in the stomach and small bowel. This contrasts with sporadic GISTs, which are typically solitary and primarily located in the stomach. Germline KIT variants in exons 13 and 17 were significantly more frequent in familial cases (19.6% and 12.5%, respectively), when compared to sporadic cases (1% for both). Notably, exon 17 germline variants reported an association with Imatinib resistance.

PDGFRA germline variants were reported in 7 publications, involving 2 individuals without a family history and 5 families, carrying 7 different rare germline variants, and encompassing in total 35 individuals. From these, 13 (37.0%) were diagnosed with GIST. Despite the small numbers, *PDGFRA* associated GISTs were most frequently found in the stomach (5/7, 71.4%), and the youngest case reported was 39 years old (age range: 39-67).

Across 3 ERN GENTURIS reference centres, we identified 28 individuals from KIT variant carrier families from Portugal, Spain and the Netherlands and 38 sporadic GISTs from Portugal. The integration of knowledge derived from the literature review and real patient data collection will now be used to define clinical trajectories and pathways of care in heritable GIST.

The collection of real-world sporadic GIST data and associated healthcare cost will allow costing the treatment with GIST patients, while the literature search on heritable

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GIST families will be essential to understand and predict the cost with active prevention of organs at risk in KIT and PDGFR germline carriers.

The identification of families with heritable GIST is expected to improve clinical management and help defining guidelines for clinical management.

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An in-house strategy to retrieve high-quality clinical data to manage patients with rare tumour risk syndromes

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Retrieval of high-quality data from electronic medical records is a key component of research and health care systems management. Rare Tumour Risk Syndrome (RTRS) patients are followed by multiple specialties and there are specific legal requirements for confidentiality of genetic information, increasing the complexity of information management. Our aim was to show our rationale in the development of a solution to identify all RTRS patients in the hospital and retrieve data relevant both to PREVENTABLE project and for monitoring as a GENTURIS healthcare provider, as well as the inclusion of patients within the GENTURIS registry.

Based on the care pathways characterized in the scope of WP1 of PREVENTABLE - establishment and validation of parallel and condition-specific care pathway *per* RTRS, we screened the administrative database and the electronic health record (EHR) where data are registered at our hospital for RTRS patients, starting by patients undergoing oncogenetics consultation, high-risk appointments for surveillance, specific tests and procedures. For all possible cases, we retrieved patients' information including the PREVENTABLE minimum dataset, generating a list of GENTURIS patients who become tagged as such.

From a total of 9505 patients identified through first consultations (n=3141), specific tests (n=4725) and procedures

(n=1639) during January 2023-September 2025 searching, it was possible to retrieve data from 3553 patients, 2124 women and 1429 men), in the age range from 0 to 94 years (mean age 44 years). The distribution of new cases according to ERN GENTURIS thematic group was the following: 101 patients in thematic group 1 (schwannomatosis and neurofibromatosis), 156 patients in thematic group 2 (Lynch syndrome and polyposis), 299 patients in thematic group 3 (Hereditary Breast and Ovarian Cancer Syndrome) and 152 patients in thematic group 4 (Other rare - predominantly malignant - genturis).

This retrospective review and classification will prospectively converge with improvement in the clinical records of new cases. This monitoring system will enable the identification of new RTRS cases per year and follow the health status of all RTRS patients in our hospital. Aggregate data such as counts by RTRS/GENTURIS thematic groups will be summarized to facilitate management and reporting. The strategy presented will allow for a better follow-up of RTRS patients throughout their care in the hospital as well as research on new and improved ways of patient management and monitoring in the scope of the quality management system.

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Genetic Landscape of BRCA1/2 in Urological Oncology: Portuguese Real-World Evidence

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Background: Germline pathogenic variants (gPVs) in *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* are well-established cancer predisposition factors, mainly for breast and ovarian cancer. Beyond these associations, *BRCA2* gPVs are linked to higher-grade and poor prognosis prostate tumors, while *BRCA1* gPVs confer a slightly increased prostate cancer risk, as compared to the general population. However, the impact of these variants on other urological cancers remains largely uncharacterized.

Methods: Retrospective, descriptive study including patients (pts) with urological cancers carrying *BRCA1/2* gPVs and followed at a Hereditary Cancer Risk Clinic. Genetic, clinical, and pathological data were extracted from medical records. Survival outcomes were estimated using the Kaplan-Meier method, and median overall survival (mOS) was compared between *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* carriers with the logrank test.

Results: From 836 families with *BRCA1/2* gPVs, 42 families included pts with urological malignancies: 37 with prostate cancer, four with renal cancer, and seven with urothelial cancer. Most individuals (77%) carried a *BRCA2* gPV.

Among prostate cancer pts with *BRCA1/2* gPVs, all high-grade or metastatic cases occurred in *BRCA2* carriers. These pts were diagnosed at a younger age than both the general population and *BRCA1* gPV carriers. *BRCA2* carriers also exhibited a broader personal cancer history, with breast cancer being the other most frequent neoplasia (32%), a pattern not observed among *BRCA1* carriers. In family phenotypes breast cancer also was the most common malignancy (71% for *BRCA1*; 74% for *BRCA2*), followed by prostate cancer (42% for *BRCA1*; 34% for *BRCA2*).

We identified three individuals with *BRCA2* gPVs mapping to the prostate cancer cluster region (c.7914-3') and eight with

the Portuguese founder variant (c.156_157insAlu), a truncating variant with downstream functional consequences in this region.

In advanced prostate cancer, the mOS was 38 months (95% CI, 5.6–70.3). There was no significant difference in survival between *BRCA1* and *BRCA2* carriers in the overall cohort ($p = 0.408$).

All renal cancer pts (three *BRCA2* and one *BRCA1* carrier) were female, had a personal history of breast cancer, and presented with clear cell histology. Among urothelial cancer pts (one *BRCA1* and six *BRCA2* carriers), most had non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer (71.4%), except for two *BRCA2* carriers who had advanced disease.

Conclusion: This study reinforces the association between *BRCA2* gPVs and aggressive prostate cancer and provides a detailed characterization of other urological cancers in *BRCA1/2* gPV carriers. Recurrent patterns of urological malignancies within families highlight areas for hypothesis generation and future research aimed at quantifying risk and clarifying the clinical significance of *BRCA1/2* variants in urological cancers. This is particularly relevant in Portugal, where *BRCA2* founder variants may contribute to an increased prostate cancer risk, yet population specific evidence remains limited.

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How health system structure shapes RTRS care: lessons from three European models for EU policy

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Rare Tumour Risk Syndromes (RTRS) are inherited conditions that increase lifetime cancer risk. Effective care requires early detection, multidisciplinary coordination, and long-term follow-up. Across Europe, RTRS care remains fragmented, with disparities in funding and unequal access to genetic services. National healthcare systems, centralised, decentralised, or mixed, shape how RTRS care is delivered, affecting access, coordination, and sustainability. As part of the Horizon Europe PREVENTABLE project, we explored how system design influences RTRS care, offering lessons for broader rare disease and health policy contexts.

We conducted a SWOT analysis with three case studies: France (centralised), Spain (decentralised), and Portugal (mixed) to examine how health system structures influence RTRS care accessibility and financing. Methods included desk research, semi-structured interviews, and qualitative data analysis.

Findings show that system structure influences RTRS care. Centralised models offer strong coordination but may lack flexibility. Decentralised systems allow regional adaptation yet struggle with equity. Mixed systems combine elements of both,

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risking fragmentation. Common strengths include specialist expertise and ERN-GENTURIS participation. Shared challenges include limited reimbursement for prevention, data gaps, and uneven access. Opportunities lie in harmonised guidelines, improved funding models, and stakeholder collaboration.

Care for RTRS patients depends on the healthcare system in which it is delivered. Findings highlight the need for EU-level coordination to ensure consistent care standards. These insights apply beyond RTRS and can inform integrated, preventive policies for rare diseases.

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Gastric Cancer Organoid As Model For Therapy Resistance

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Introduction: Gastric cancer (GC) remains a major global health burden and one of the leading causes of cancer-related mortality worldwide. Despite advances in treatment, the prognosis for advanced disease remains poor, with a 5-year survival rate of 20–40%. Combination chemotherapy regimens such as FLOT represent the current standard of care; however, therapeutic response varies considerably, and resistance frequently develops. Increasing evidence indicates that aberrant glycosylation plays a central role in GC progression, immune evasion, and therapy response. Patient-derived organoids (PDOs) offer a physiologically relevant *ex vivo* model for investigating tumor biology and treatment responses. In this study, we aimed to establish gastric cancer PDO models and investigate chemotherapy-induced alterations in glycosylation profiles.

Methods and Results: We established five GC PDO models from primary tumor tissues (n=3) and matched adjacent mucosa (n=2). The normal PDOs displayed typical spherical and cystic morphologies, while tumor PDOs showed more complex structures resembling the original tumor histophenotype. These organoids also exhibited sustained proliferative capacity *in vitro*, enabling comparative studies within the same patient context.

Two gastric tumor PDOs of the intestinal subtype, were exposed to different concentrations of FLOT (5-FU, leucovorin, oxaliplatin, and docetaxel) chemotherapy. Dose-response analyses showed a dose-dependent decrease in cell viability in both PDOs. The IC_{50} value was determined from the FLOT dose-response curve and used to define the optimal treatment condition for subsequent analyses. Glycomic profiling revealed chemotherapy-induced remodeling of the glycosylation landscape, characterized by increased expression of truncated O-glycans and sLe^a, accompanied by reduced sLe^x expression. In parallel, receptor tyrosine kinase analysis indicated alternation in MET and HER2 expression levels following FLOT exposure.

Conclusion: These findings demonstrate that chemotherapy induces glycoprofile remodeling and modulates signaling pathways in GC PDOs. Our preliminary results support the use of PDOs as models to investigate glycosylation-mediated mechanisms of chemotherapy response and may help identify glycan-based biomarkers and therapeutic targets for precision oncology in GC.

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Divergence Between Leukemogenic Basal T-Cell Receptor Signaling and Antigen-Induced Activation in mouse models of T-Lymphoblastic Leukemia/Lymphoma

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T-lymphoblastic leukemia/lymphoma (T-ALL/LBL) is a malignant disorder characterized by development arrest of immature T cells, followed by dissemination of these aberrant T lymphocytes. The T cell receptor (TCR) plays an essential role in T cell development, defining T cell fate during positive and negative selection. Since many T-ALL/LBL cases exhibit TCR on their leukemic cells, we aimed to understand the TCR role in leukemia development, and the impact of leukemic cell antigenic stimulation. To do so, we explored disease development and TCR targeting in transgenic TCR mouse models, namely the Marilyn and OT-I mice.

The Marilyn mice express a transgenic TCR specific for the HY male antigen bound to MHC class II, leading to positive selection of CD4⁺ thymocytes in females and negative selection in males. The OT-I mice bear a transgenic TCR which is responsive to the SIINFEKL chicken ovalbumin peptide (OVA). OTI-expressing T cells are positively selected in both male and females. Thus, Marilyn *Rag2*^{-/-} females but not males developed T cell leukemia that, when transplanted, led to higher tumor burden in recipient mice. Moreover, we found delayed disease progression in recipient mice treated with the male antigen cognate peptide (DBY), which led to leukemic cell death. In addition, antigenic targeting of this transgenic TCR translated into prolonged survival. Around 50% of TCR OT-I *Rag2*^{-/-} mice developed a T-ALL/LBL disease, characterized

mainly by thymic lymphoma, increase of white cells in the bloodstream and leukemic cell dissemination. We also found that mice carrying two copies of the OT-I transgene had increased T-ALL/LBL incidence than mice with a single copy. This malignant transformation appears to be triggered by basal TCR signaling, since the ablation of its interaction with MHC class I (achieved by β 2-microglobulin gene knockout) impaired spontaneous disease development. To confirm their malignant nature, OT-I *Rag2*^{-/-} leukemic cells were injected into *Rag2*^{-/-} mice, which rapidly developed fatal disease. Both leukemic and non-leukemic OT-I *Rag2*^{-/-} T cells were stimulated *in vitro* with OVA to assess their response to activation of the TCR pathway. Surprisingly, most OT-I *Rag2*^{-/-} leukemic cells did not upregulate the CD69 activation marker compared to healthy OT-I *Rag2*^{-/-} thymocytes. To further investigate the possible loss of TCR function, these cells were also stimulated with an antibody targeting surface CD3 and PMA/Ionomycin. Once again, leukemic OT-I cells were less responsive to these stimuli compared to healthy OT-I thymocytes.

These findings show that transgenic TCR OT-I leads to T cell leukemia through basal TCR signaling by presentation of self-peptides to the receptor. However, upon malignant transformation, the transgenic TCR becomes less responsive to antigenic stimulation. Overall, our data demonstrate that transgenic TCR expression leads to T-ALL/LBL development and that strong stimulation of TCR suppresses this disease.

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Effect of inhibitors of sialylation in EGFR-targeted therapy in colorectal cancer

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Introduction: Aberrant sialylation is a hallmark of cancer glycosylation, contributing to tumour progression, immune modulation, and therapeutic resistance. In colorectal cancer (CRC), the impact of sialylation on receptor tyrosine kinase signalling, particularly in the context of EGFR-targeted therapies, remains insufficiently defined.

Aims: Assess the effect of a sialylation inhibitor, 3Fax-Neu5Ac, on CRC cells' malignant features and on the modulation of Cetuximab binding.

Materials and Methods: Three RAS wild-type CRC cell lines with distinct sialylation profiles, SLeX and terminal α 2,6 sialylation, ST6Gall overexpressing model, were treated with a pan-sialyltransferase inhibitor, 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac. The impact on sialylation, as well as the biological consequences and response to therapy were evaluated.

Results: Inhibition of sialylation through 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac resulted in a pronounced decrease in both α 2,3- and α 2,6-terminal sialylation at the cell surface. N-glycomic analysis demonstrated a remodeling in N-glycome with reduced sialylated structures and concomitant increase in neutral glycans. This glycan remodelling selectively impaired cancer cell motility without significant effects on cell viability, indicating a role for sialylation in the regulation of migratory phenotypes. Additionally, 3F_{ax}-Neu5Ac affected the EGFR sialylation profile, influencing Cetuximab binding in a cell line-dependent manner.

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Conclusion: Collectively, these findings demonstrate that EGFR sialylation modulates receptor behaviour and Cetuximab response in CRC cells, highlighting the relevance of glycosylation in shaping therapeutic response. Targeting sialylation may provide a rational strategy to overcome glycan-mediated resistance, while highlighting the need for the development of isoenzyme-specific sialyltransferase inhibitors to enable more precise and effective therapeutic interventions.

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